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DELIVERABLE REPORT

SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACTS OF THE LEPTON COLLIDER-BASED RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

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Abstract:

This report summarises the data, assumptions, methodologies, and outcomes of the socio-economic impact analysis for the initial phase of the FCC research infrastructure - the FCC-ee lepton collider. The analysis covers an approximately 21-years long design and construction phase followed by a 20-year operation and gradual energy upgrade phase.

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(2) This updated version reflects new evidence and assessment carried out between September 2024 and April 2025.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report details the data, assumptions, methodologies, and outcomes of a comprehensive socio-economic impact analysis for the first phase of the **FCC research infrastructure - the FCC-ee lepton collider**, including environmental externalities. It builds upon an initial version of the socio-economic impact assessment - conducted between 2020 and 2023 - which focused on an FCC-ee design with two experiments and was limited to assessing core cost and benefit pathways. A subsequent study - carried out between September 2024 and February 2025 - provided a complementary analysis based on a revised FCC-ee configuration including four experiments, an updated cost structure and project schedule. It refined the cost and benefit estimates from the previous assessment on the basis of updated data and assumptions and expanded the scope to encompass broader socio-economic effects and environmental externalities, both positive and negative. The findings of this latest study are presented in this report. They may be further updated at a later stage as the infrastructure design continues to evolve. Indeed, this report should be considered a step in an **ongoing appraisal, continuously informing and supporting the project's design and implementation**.

The analysis spans the entire lifecycle of FCC-ee, encompassing its design, construction, operation, and gradual energy upgrade phases, with an assumed duration of 41 years from 2024 (first year of analysis) to 2064 (final year of data analysis).

Some features of the proposed infrastructure have the potential to support two particle colliders in sequence: the FCC-ee and the FCC-hh (Future Hadron Collider). However, due to the very long timespan associated with this integrated programme, this study adopts a precautionary approach by focusing solely on the first phase, specifically the construction of the FCC-ee. To address this limitation, the residual value of FCC-ee assets at the end of their operational life has been calculated and presented as an additional potential benefit, with the possibility of being transferred as a legacy to the FCC-hh, should it be built.

In evaluating the FCC-ee project, both costs and benefits are expressed incrementally in comparison to a scenario where the project is not implemented. In this counterfactual scenario, the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) would continue its operation until its anticipated end of life, and no new particle-collider would be constructed at CERN. CERN would continue its operation, exploiting the existing particle accelerators and some experimental infrastructures. This approach is designed to capture the "net" change, focusing on causally related effects that can be specifically attributed to the FCC-ee project.

The methodological approach is based on the latest literature and empirical research on the economic quantification of impacts associated with research infrastructures, and on the ESFRI recommendations for the long-term sustainability of research infrastructures.

Table 1 summarises the results of this analysis, highlighting the expected costs and benefits from the implementation of the FCC-ee. These estimates are based on the FCC-ee design at the time of the analysis, with conservative assumptions applied throughout. Further research can be carried out to estimate sensitivity of the assumptions and the uncertainties of the results, for instance using Monte Carlo simulation.

Table 1: Summary results: costs and benefits of FCC-ee – Baseline Scenario (Million, CHF)

	Share of the total	Not discounted	Discounted
TOTAL COSTS (MCHF)	100%	38,308	20,020
INVESTMENTS (CAPEX)	50.8%	16,215	10,171
OPERATION COSTS (OPEX)	47.1%	21,212	9,423
PERSONNEL COSTS		16,802	7,544
OTHER OPERATIONAL COSTS		4,410	1,879
NEGATIVE EXTERNALITIES	1.7%	653	354
SHADOW COST OF CARBON*		633	341
SOCIAL COST OF IONISING RADIATION		1.3	0.6
SOCIAL COST OF PROJECT-RELATED INDUCED NOISE		0.02	0.02
LOSS OF AGRICULTURAL INCOME, BIODIVERSITY & HABITAT		8	4
SOCIAL COST OF PROJECT-RELATED TRAFFIC-INDUCED AIR POLLUTION		1	1
SOCIAL COST OF PROJECT-RELATED TRAFFIC-INDUCED GHG EXTERNALITIES		10	7
DECOMMISSIONING COSTS**	0.4%	228	72
TOTAL CORE BENEFITS (MCHF)	100%	57,244	24,092
SCIENTIFIC PRODUCTION	11.7%	6,515	2,817
EARLY CAREER RESEARCHER TRAINING	20.7%	20,687	4,986
INDUSTRIAL BENEFITS FOR SUPPLIERS	39.7%	17,577	9,569
OPEN SOFTWARE (EXPERIMENTS AND DETECTORS)	18.2%	7,428	4,375
CULTURAL BENEFITS	9.7%	5,037	2,344
... FOR ONSITE VISITORS		4,807	2,242
... FOR ONLINE VISITORS		229	102
NET PRESENT VALUE (MCHF)			4,071
BENEFIT / COST RATIO			1.20

Notes: Discounted values at 0.028 Social Discount Rate. *Construction of the tunnel and surface sites and the operation phase. GHG emissions associated with the construction of the accelerators are not included. **Since no complete estimation of these costs is available, they were approximated using the dismantling costs estimated at CERN, although being aware that decommissioning costs are generally higher than dismantling costs.

The FCC-ee is conceived as a design-to-cost project, with a total capital investment of approximately **16.2 billion CHF** (including the ttbar radiofrequency system, not discounted). This figure encompasses feasibility studies, civil construction works, creation of technical infrastructures, all particle accelerators (injectors, booster and collider) and all investment costs (including in-kind) related to the four experiment detectors.

Operation costs – amounting to a total of about **21 billion CHF** (over 19 years, not discounted) - include the costs of CERN staff and personnels of the collaborations, irrespective of the institutions employing them but based on their actual dedication to the project, as well as all expenses (both in-kind and outflows) that are needed for running the experiments and operating and maintaining the FCC-ee research infrastructure throughout the entire project duration (e.g. electricity, water, spares and human resources for maintenance and repair). Specifically, **personnel costs** amount to 16.8 billion CHF (over 37 years, not discounted), including the expenses associated to around 258,000 person-years over the entire FCC-ee lifecycle (2024–2064), covering design, construction, operation, and data analysis. The peak workforce is expected to exceed 15,000 individuals in 2060 (headcount). This diverse group includes scientists, engineers, technicians, administrative staff, doctoral and postdoctoral researchers, as well as undergraduate and Master's students, and apprentices. Of the total personnel, approximately 11% will work on particle accelerators and technical infrastructures, while the remaining 89% will focus on detectors and experimental physics (many of them for part time, e.g. because of teaching duties elsewhere). The **other costs** amount to 4.4 billion CHF (not discounted), which is equivalent to a yearly average of 232 million CHF annually over the FCC-ee's operation, from commissioning to the end of its operational phase.

Noteworthy **negative environmental externalities** of the FCC-ee project have been assessed. These include greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions expected to be generated during both the construction of the tunnel and surface sites, as well as during the operation phase. Other externalities related to the construction phase include noise from site preparation, shaft construction, and underground excavation, changes in land use that could impact biodiversity and ecosystems, as well as air pollution, GHG emissions, and congestion caused by the transportation of excavated material by trucks. Additionally, ionizing radiation from particle beam collisions and radioactive waste generated during the operation of the FCC-ee have been considered. The total cost of these environmental externalities is estimated to be around **653 million CHF** (not discounted), with GHG emissions representing the largest share (97%).

On the benefit side, the analysis focuses on the direct benefits currently known and foreseeable based on past factual evidence, particularly from the LHC project.

The first impact pathway assessed is the value (estimated at production cost) from **scientific content production**. It stems from the publication flow generated by scientists and engineers engaged in the collider and its experiments, resulting in diverse scientific products, ranging from journal articles and working papers to conference proceedings and presentations. These products can have a lasting impact, extending beyond the High-Energy Physics community, potentially influencing other knowledge domains, and addressing broader societal challenges. Scientometric techniques were employed to estimate scientific production impact and its propagation from the FCC-ee project. The methodology involved analysing historical patterns observed in comparable high-energy physics research programs like Tevatron, LEP, and LHC. The economic concepts of "opportunity cost" and "value of time" were employed to determine the marginal social value of scientific products, with adjustments to account for large co-authorship practices of international collaborations. This approach considered the time spent by individuals in producing these outputs and valued it based on their average hourly salaries. This method was applied to estimate the social value of scientific products produced by researchers directly involved in the research program (tier 0 products), those citing the initial tier 0 knowledge (tier 1 products), and products citing tier 1 outputs (tier 2 products). Over 38 000 scientific products are expected to be directly produced by researchers within the FCC-ee project, with an additional 500 000 products likely to be impacted through citations until the year 2083. By assuming that scientists collaborating on the project spend 55% of their time on research and scientific output, and that 22% of this effort is dedicated to FCC-related products, the estimated benefit from scientific production is approximately 6.5 billion CHF (not discounted). This valuation accounts for the diminishing value of tier 1 and tier 2 products compared to tier 0

products, as knowledge propagates through waves of production and the initial input from FCC-ee progressively diminishes.

The second impact pathway under consideration is the **value of early career researcher training**, which reflects FCC-ee's role in transferring knowledge, fostering skills development, and building capacities for individuals actively engaged in the research infrastructure program throughout its lifecycle. This analysis specifically evaluated the benefits accrued by apprentices, trainees, technical students, doctoral students, post-doctoral researchers, and associated personnel up to a cut-off age of 30. The analysis did not include the training value for other highly qualified personnel, temporary labour, and contracted works as well as for professionals that move from the project into other industrial domains. The benefit has been quantified by estimating the lifelong career development improvements for participants upon entering the labour market after gaining a working experience within the research program. Previous studies, further validated through a survey involving approximately 2 600 individuals, indicate that the lifetime salary benefit for an early-stage researcher works at FCC-ee would range from a minimum of 2% to a maximum of 10% for the average period of stay within the research infrastructure (3.78 years). The total socio-economic benefit is assessed at around 20.7 billion CHF (not discounted).

The third impact pathway explores the benefits generated by the project for the **industry**. This encompasses advantages for supplier companies engaged in the design, construction, and operation of the new research infrastructure. The benefit stems from increased financial performance of the suppliers resulting from the knowledge gained through close collaboration with the research infrastructure. This knowledge, in turn, contributes to the creation and improvement of new processes, products, and services that suppliers can leverage in other markets and domains. A profit multiplier has been determined, ranging from 1.96 for procurement with low or moderate technology intensity levels to 3.09 for procurement with high technology intensity levels. Applying this multiplier to the capital expenditure, the social benefits of technology procurement are estimated at 17.6 billion CHF (not discounted).

The fourth impact pathway relates to **free and open simulation software** that are likely to be required by FCC-ee for the detectors and data analysis. The socio-economic impacts arising from a new or significantly upgraded detector simulation software, with potential applicability beyond high-energy physics, were estimated (building on previous work for the LHC) as the cost that external users would save by adopting the software made freely available by CERN and other contributors. The estimated value stands at 7.4 billion CHF (not discounted).

The fifth impact pathway pertains to engagement of laypeople. Such kind of activities are directly linked to laypeople interest for scientific research, the technologies employed for this research, and the operations involved in designing and running particle accelerators and experiments. For the purposes of this study, the focus was put on on-site visitors and online/social media users. The impact of these activities was estimated based on actual observations of the LHC programme, measured in terms of increased awareness, interest, and understanding of science by members of society, collectively referred to as "**cultural benefit**". It is estimated that CERN will welcome about 19 million visitors between 2024-2064 period out of which 5.5 million will be attracted by FCC-ee. The benefit for on-site visitors was estimated using the travel cost method, which incorporates the costs borne by visitors to travel to CERN and FCC, the economic value of time spent traveling, along with any local expenditure connected to their visit based on an actual survey carried out over one year at CERN. This benefit is estimated (by the established travel cost approach) at 4.8 billion CHF (not discounted). For virtual visitors engaged through CERN-managed webpages and social media, the benefit was estimated based on the "opportunity cost of time". After estimating the volume of online visits directly associated to the FCC project and valuing the time spent during these visits, the benefit is estimated at 229 million CHF (not discounted). In total, the cultural benefits quantified in this analysis amount to 5 billion CHF (not discounted).

To aggregate the value of measured benefits and compare them with costs, a **Social Discount Rate (SDR)** was estimated specifically for the FCC-ee project. This project-specific rate accounts for the level of development and preferences for consumption and investments in countries contributing to the CERN budget and the very long duration of the project. The assumed SDR value is 2.8 % (close to rates adopted by guidelines of some EU institutions).

Applying the SDR to the benefits, a **total present value of benefits of 24 billion CHF** has been determined. Comparing this value to the 20 billion CHF present value of all costs (capital, operational and environmental costs) yields a **positive net present value of 4 billion CHF**. The **benefit/cost ratio is 1.20**, indicating that the so far quantifiable socio-economic benefits exceed costs by 20%. These findings suggest a positive net contribution of the FCC-ee project to societal well-being. It serves to demonstrate the long-term social profitability of the proposed new scientific research infrastructure.

The analysis conducted so far has identified costs and benefits which are likely to materialise from the implementation of FCC-ee as it is currently designed. Additional benefits may arise if further planning, integration, and appropriate contextual conditions are incorporated into the project design. However, due to uncertainties at this stage, these benefits are not included in the net present value and benefit/cost ratio calculations presented in Table 1, which are prudent and conservative as a baseline. Potential additional benefits include the residual value of FCC-ee assets, assuming the subsequent FCC-hh project is developed. Moreover, the following potential positive environmental externalities have been identified: the provision of excess clean electricity to society resulting from the voluntary goal of supplying the FCC-ee with renewable energy, the ecosystem benefits from mitigation actions aimed at reducing negative environmental impacts, and the savings resulting from the use of heat recovery. Other expected ICT benefits include the development of innovative software (e.g., free digital platform inspired by the experience of the current ones, such as Zenodo and Indico) as well as industrial impacts through the development of spinoffs. Local impacts have also been explored. These include benefits from the reuse of waste heat (e.g., avoided costs of purchasing energy for heating from conventional energy sources such as oil, wood, gas, and electricity), enhanced safety due to emergency preparedness and intervention framework required by FCC-ee at both underground and surface levels, territorial benefits for the host countries (France and Switzerland) generated during the construction and operation phases of the FCC-ee, and regional benefits for all countries through procurement activity across the entire project life cycle.

After presenting the results of this analysis, item by item in terms of costs and benefits, this report concludes with a set of recommendations derived from the findings. The purpose of these recommendations is to ensure that the benefits can be monitored and regularly reported, allowing the updated findings to be integrated into the infrastructure's design, construction, and operation phases.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

BAU	Business-as-usual
CERN	European Organization for Nuclear Research
CHF	Swiss Francs (currency)
CMS	Compact Muon Solenoid
CNAO	National Hadrontherapy Centre for Cancer Treatment
CO ₂ (eq)	Carbon Dioxide equivalent
DB	Decibels (unit of sound)
EBIT	Earnings Before Interest and Taxes
EC	European Commission
EDF	Électricité de France
EIB	European Investment Bank
EOCS	European Open Science Cloud
ESFR	European Synchrotron Radiation Facility
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures
EU	European Union
EUR	Euro (currency)
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
FASER	Forward Search Experiment
FCC	Future Circular Collider
FCC-ee	Future Circular Lepton Collider
FCC-hh	Future Circular Hadron Collider
FELIX	Front-End Link eXchange
FNAL	Fermi National Accelerator Laboratory
GBP	British pound (currency)
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GWh	Gigawatt-hour
Ha	Hectare (unit of area)
HEP	High-Energy Physics
HL-LHC	High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider
HR	Human Resources
HUF	Hungarian Forint (currency)
HV-QF	Hadron Very forward calorimeter, Quartz Fiber option
IAEA	International Atomic Energy Agency
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
ISDI	Installation de Stockage de Déchets Inertes

ISDND	Installation de Stockage de Déchets Non Dangereux
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature
IT	Information Technology
JASPERS	Joint Assistance to Support Projects in European Regions
JHR	Jules Horowitz Reactor
JPY	Japanese Yen (currency)
LARP	LHC Accelerator Research Program
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Electricity
LEP	Large Electron-Positron Collider
LHC	Large Hadron Collider
MCP	Marginal Cost of Production
MoEDAL	Monopole and Exotics Detector at the LHC
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
OPEX	Operating Expenditure
PPA	Power Purchasing Agreement
PPS	Purchasing Power Standard
RF	Radio Frequency
RI-PATHS	Research Infrastructures Pathways towards a Socio-Economic Assessment Framework
SCOAP	Sponsoring Consortium for Open Access in Particle Physics Publishing
SDR	Social Discount Rate
SND@LHC	Scattering and Neutrino Detector at the LHC
Sv	Sievert (unit of radiation dose)
THB	Thai baht (currency)
TOTEM	TOTAL Elastic and diffractive cross section Measurement
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
UK	United Kingdom
USA	United States of America
USAID	United States Agency for International Development
USCMS	US Compact Muon Solenoid
WTP	Willingness To Pay

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. BACKGROUND AND OBJECTIVES

This report details the data, assumptions, methodologies, and outcomes of the updated socio-economic impact analysis for the initial phase of the FCC research infrastructure - the FCC-ee lepton collider. It builds upon a previous socio-economic impact assessment conducted between 2020 and 2023. Such assessment focused on an FCC-ee design featuring two experiments and was limited to assessing costs and core benefit pathways. A subsequent complementary study, carried out between September 2024 and February 2025, provided an updated analysis based on a revised FCC-ee configuration including four experiments. It refined the cost and benefit estimates from the previous assessment and expanded the scope to encompass broader socio-economic effects and environmental externalities, both positive and negative.

The analysis – presented in this report - spans the entire lifecycle of FCC-ee, encompassing its design, construction, operation, and gradual energy upgrade phases, with an assumed duration of 41 years from 2024 (first year of analysis) to 2064 (final year of data analysis).

The report should be understood as a **self-standing document**, providing a comprehensive overview of the methodology applied, input parameters, fundamental assumptions, data sources and quantitative results. However, to keep it as concise as possible, the reader who wishes to know more about the estimation of specific impacts will be directed at additional published articles and technical reports.

The input parameters for the socio-economic impact analysis, in particular the high-level cost and personnel engagement estimates represent a working hypothesis that is necessary to be able to estimate quantitative socio-economic benefits. This hypothesis must not be considered as a single, stable, and precise estimate of the costs and personnel needs. The mathematical model underlying the quantitative socio-economic impact analysis can be parameterised with updated input parameters at later points in time when the knowledge about the FCC design is more mature to perform an update of the quantitative socio-economic impact potentials. The working hypothesis for costs and personnel used in the present analysis and report are based on historical observations and reference class projects and have been agreed with the FCC study management for the purpose of the socio-economic study.

1.2. STRUCTURE OF THE REPORT

The report is structured as follows:

- Chapter 2 outlines the overall approach adopted in the socio-economic impact analysis model and provides an overview of the impacts considered and the fundamental assumptions adopted.
- Chapter 3 presents assumptions on the human and financial resources needed for the FCC-ee project to operate and accomplish its outcomes. It presents, for instance, the data on the expected number of future project participants, the associated personnel costs, and estimates of investment, operation and environmental costs along with their time profile. The total values of the costs associated to FCC-ee are presented at the end of the chapter (Section 3.3).
- Chapter 4 discusses the assumptions, data, and methods for the estimation of the measurable benefits and presents the results of the analysis. The total values of the quantified socio-economic benefits are presented at the end of the chapter (Section 0).
- Chapter 5 reports on the additional benefits which may arise from the implementation of the FCC-ee.
- Chapter 6 summarises the findings of the analyses and concludes.
- Chapter 7 compiles a number of recommendations focused on enhancing data collection and analysis methods. The aim is to ensure a continuous and sustainable monitoring of the impacts throughout the entire project duration.
- Annexes and references compile further detailed information.

2. SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACT ANALYSIS METHODOLOGY

2.1. THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACT MODEL IN A NUTSHELL

Policy makers expect research infrastructures to be essential components of technological and scientific progress (EC, 2010; Technopolis, 2011; ESF, 2013, ESFRI 2020, ESFRI 2017, ESFRI, 2018, ESFRI, 2010;). Traditionally, the appraisal process of research infrastructure projects relied on the scientific community's own internal mechanisms and the policy context. Typically, these mechanisms involve a community-based process that assesses the 'science case', sometimes complemented by a 'business case' or considerations related to the socio-economic impacts (Feller, 2013). This approach is today no longer the only decision basis for new investments in scientific research infrastructure projects. For instance, it does not account for planning a new research infrastructure where all possible socio-economic effects (including on health and environment) are identified from the beginning. For this reason, specific evaluation tools and methods are being developed by associations of national and international funding bodies and this project significantly contributes to this effort.

During the last decade, **a more strategic approach to research infrastructure investments has been promoted at international level**, with the development of roadmaps to prioritise research infrastructures (ESFRI 2021, UKRI 2020, ESFRI, 2008; OECD, 2008; Research Council UK, 2010). Such roadmaps assess research infrastructures according to a set of qualitative and quantitative criteria ranging from scientific and technological excellence to socio-economic impact indicators, governance, and financial aspects. In some cases, also risk factors are considered.

However, **no consensus exists today on a single evaluation model**; instead, a variety of different approaches are used in different countries and economic regions (Catalano 2024, Griniece et al 2020, Florio et al 2016c, Florio 2019; Pozzo et al., 2019; Vignetti, 2021). Various conceptual frameworks have been proposed in parallel by different teams. However, all these frames agree to consider a range of observable direct and indirect effects and longer-term impacts and reflect different information needs of funding institutions, policy and decision-makers and science managers. A heterogeneous set of methods is applied to capture these effects (European Commission 2021, Giffoni and Vignetti, 2019).

This lack of consensus hinders the possibility of systematically comparing the impacts of different projects that may compete for scarce funding, and comparing ex-ante, on-going, and ex-post evaluations, as suggested by the best international practice for project appraisals of major infrastructures (European Commission, 2021).

Against the demand for credible and recognised methodologies to assess research infrastructures, the RIPATH project, funded by the Horizon 2020 programme, aimed at developing a conceptual model describing the socio-economic impacts of research infrastructures and their related financial investments, applying to a wide range of infrastructures and scientific fields (Griniece et al., 2020). The model identifies and describes the different pathways involved in the generation of socio-economic impacts and defines a set of indicators and methodologies to assess them. These **pathways are defined as the non-linear sequence of steps linking a research infrastructure to its direct and tangible outputs, the socio-economic outcomes attributed to that infrastructure, up to more indirect, wider, and not necessarily quantifiable impacts**. The RI-PATHS H2020 project (GA 777563) lists the most relevant indicators used to track the future outputs, outcomes and impacts of a research infrastructure, as well as methodologies for impact measurement. It also recommends the use of different qualitative analyses (narratives, case studies, etc.) to report on the most intangible impacts.

The methodology presented in this report builds on the approach defined by the RI-PATHS project and the results of previous works for the economic quantification of impacts of research infrastructures carried out by CSIL and CERN.¹ Box 1 below provides more details on relevant existing works used in this project.

¹ Evidenced by several publications on this topic in peer-reviewed journals (see list of references in Chapter 9).

Box 1: Main sources of information for the socio-economic impact assessment model

Cost-Benefit Analysis in the Research, Development and Innovation Sector (funded by the EIB University Research Sponsorship programme, 2013-2016, carried out by CSIL and the University of Milan). The project developed a model for assessing the socio-economic impacts of Big Science, including impacts on knowledge production, human capital, technological learning, cultural effects and good public value. The model was tested on an example of a fundamental scientific research infrastructure, the CERN LHC, and an example of applied research infrastructure, the National Centre for Oncological Treatment (CNAO) in Pavia. The evaluation framework is described by Florio and Sirtori (2016), while the evaluation of LHC and CNAO are reported respectively by Florio, Forte and Sirtori (2016) and Battistoni et al. (2016).

RI-PATHS - Charting Impact Pathways of Investment in Research Infrastructure (Horizon 2020 project agreement N° 777563, 2018-2020, carried out by a consortium led by EFIS and including CSIL, ESF, Fraunhofer ISI, CERN, Elixir, Alba and Desy). The project developed a model to describe the pathways of materialisation of the socio-economic impacts of research infrastructures and define a set of indicators and appropriate methodologies to assess them. The framework was developed in a modular manner, adapting it to a broad range of scientific domains and types of infrastructures. It was tested with case studies involving CERN, Alba, Elixir, and Desy. The project's outputs can be consulted at <https://ri-paths.eu/deliverable/>. The web-based modular impact assessment model is available at <https://ri-paths.eu/ri-paths-ia-model/>.

Ex-ante impact assessment of the HL-LHC infrastructures (CERN, 2015-2019, carried out by the University of Milan in collaboration with CSIL and Roma 3 University). The project consisted in evaluating the costs and socio-economic benefits to the scientific community, students and researchers, enterprises, and the general population of the upgrade of the LHC into the High-Luminosity LHC. The results are also mentioned in the FCC Conceptual Design Report published by Springer (<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1140/epjst/e2019-900087-0>) and downloadable from the CERN Document Server (<http://cds.cern.ch/record/2319300>).

Guidelines for the collection of harmonized cost data for Research Infrastructures (technical assistance to the University of Milan, Dept. Physics, for the H2020 StR-ESFRI project "Support to Reinforce the European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures", 2018-2019). CSIL developed a document (StR-ESFRI, 2019) with technical solutions for the collection of harmonised data on the cost related to the life cycle of the research infrastructures of the ESFRI Roadmap. These guidelines provide a conceptual and methodological tool for cost estimation of Research Infrastructures. The final report of this study illustrates general principles and suggests technical solutions when data seem not immediately available or difficult to estimate. It also considers the specificities of different typologies of research infrastructures, which are active in different research domains and adopt different accounting systems.

Source: Authors

The impact analysis model for the FCC-ee rests on the following pillars:

- A **long-term perspective** is taken, covering the entire lifetime of the FCC-ee research programme.
- The values of the most relevant and measurable impacts are quantified in **monetary terms**. A common currency (Swiss francs) is taken to express all monetary values in the same unit of measure and allow comparability (see Section 2.3.3).
- A **Social Discount Rate (SDR)**, estimated following the standard practice in economics, is adopted to estimate the present value of future benefits and to ensure comparability of benefits and costs that occur at different times (see Section 2.3.3 and Annex 8.2).
- **A probabilistic modelling**. This report presents costs and benefits based on a baseline scenario, which reflects the most likely estimates according to the best of our current knowledge. Where sufficient data was available, worst-case and best-case scenarios are also included. A future revision of this analysis will incorporate a Monte Carlo simulation to estimate the probability distribution of the net present value, identify the key factors that most critically influence this distribution, and determine the minimum threshold at which the benefit/cost break-even point can be achieved with high probability.
- **Prudence and transparency** are key requirements for the entire model development. The aim is to provide a solid and realistic estimate of costs and benefits, focusing on measurable impacts that can be causally attributed to the FCC-ee project.
- **An analysis oriented at the long-term sustainability of the FCC-ee project**. The ESFRI Working Group on the long-term sustainability of research infrastructure stresses the importance of scientific excellence and outstanding quality services as necessary conditions for sustainability throughout the entire research infrastructure lifecycle, but also the need to incorporate the economic and social value of research infrastructures into science-policy-society dialogue (ESFRI, 2017). In line with this recommendation, the **long-term sustainability of a new mission-oriented research infrastructure can be achieved by ensuring that public spending creates at least some measurable wealth for as many members of society as possible**. In this case, the results of the socio-economic impact analysis are to be used to inform decisions about the design and operation of FCC-ee, helping to maximise the number of potential users/beneficiaries, the value they may get out of the infrastructure, the existing risks, and, ultimately, social acceptability for the project.

2.2. IMPACT PATHWAYS

In line with the standard practice of impact assessment applied to research infrastructures and other major investment projects (Catalano 2024, Griniece et al. 2020, Florio 2019, Florio, Forte, and Sirtori, 2016, European Commission, 2021 and 2014), the identification of the impact areas of a project requires first the **identification of the project's potential beneficiaries**, i.e. the groups of the population that would directly benefit from the project. Once the impact areas associated to a specific RI are identified, the spreading of effects to its related stakeholders can be described by means of impact pathways. Each pathway represents the chain of events according to which RI's research-related activities might generate effects on its stakeholders' ecosystem. It entails resources, activity, outputs, outcomes and later impacts.

The impact pathways considered for this analysis include:

- **The value of scientific contents production**. This impact originates from the flow of knowledge generated by scientists working at the collider and its experiments. This knowledge is captured in a wide range of scientific products, ranging from scientific publications, books, and working papers to conference and workshop proceedings and presentations. Scientific products can be cited and eventually become part of a new body of knowledge that can also find recognition or interest beyond the particle physics and High-Energy Physics (HEP) community. Ultimately, newly generated knowledge may further spread into other

areas, such as industrial domains, and it may be used to help address grand societal challenges. However, such impacts are not programmable and are unforeseeable and can therefore not be included in an ex-ante socio-economic impact estimation.

- **The value of training.** This impact refers to the project's contribution to the transmission of knowledge and know-how, skills development and capacity to persons who actively participate in the research infrastructure programme during all lifecycle phases. This study considers only the benefit created for apprentices, trainees, technical students, doctoral students, post-doctoral researchers, associated members of personnel up to a cut-off age. The benefit is measured via the estimation of the lifetime career development improvements when participants enter the labour market after a minimum duration full-time working experience spent in the research programme.
- **Industry benefits for suppliers.** This is the impact that the programme generates on companies that participate in the design, construction, and operation of this new research infrastructure. It is estimated by measuring the effects of technological and knowledge spillovers on the suppliers' financial performance, which materialise via procurement activities, during which suppliers interact with the research infrastructure's scientists and engineers. When supplier companies work closely with the research infrastructure to develop and improve technologies, there is an exchange of knowledge and experience between parties, which feeds the creation and improvements of new processes, products, and services that suppliers leverage for other markets and domains of activity, improved techniques and processes or even new products and services.
- **The value of ICT innovative software.** This impact captures the socio-economic benefits generated by free and open-source software, systems and platforms that can be causally linked to the research programme and the dissemination of open data by the research infrastructure. This impact ramifies into many possible branches depending on the conditions under which the products and services are delivered to other members of the society (free or paid, open access, public, restricted), the extent of their usage and the type of organisations and individuals who use the technologies (firms, researchers, other institutions, third sector entities, schools, individuals, etc.). Since it is extremely challenging to predict the magnitude and nature of future software products and services, this study adopts a prudent approach and quantifies the socio-economic impacts of only a development and simulation software that is expected to be required for the project and for which measurable historic data with adequate quality for relevant periods of time could be identified as a basis for model building.
- **Cultural benefits.** They refer to the activities implemented by the research infrastructure to engage a wide audience of laypeople. These activities can be directly related to scientific research activities, the technologies used for this science, and the activities to design and operate the particle accelerators and experiments. In this study, only on-site visitors and web and social media users are considered. The ultimate impact is in terms of awareness-raising, increased interest and understanding of any member of the society towards science. The research infrastructure can affect societal culture in many other ways. An example is the way how new scientific discoveries could influence the education curricula in particular fields, improving human knowledge about the functioning of the universe. However, the causal link between these benefits and the FCC-ee project would be difficult to prove. Hence, in line with the prudence and transparency principles, this study is limited to the estimation of money that on-site visitors spend during their visits and the quantification of the consumed time value according to internationally accepted time-value estimation guidelines. Some societal benefits are, however, incorporated into the project's wider impacts.

This report focuses on the quantification and monetisation of the above-mentioned direct impacts. It outlines the costs and benefits that are likely at this stage. Additional and more indirect benefits, explored in previous studies, are also mentioned but not included in the project performance estimation due to their uncertainty. The report does not account for intangible impacts that cannot be reliably quantified (e.g. scientific knowledge gain²,

² Beyond what can be measured through publications and other immediate scientific products.

impacts related to science diplomacy, ethics, and trust in science, impacts on policies, etc.). The potential long-term impacts of scientific discoveries and knowledge gain can also not be predicted.

The reported cumulative value is the incremental benefit that the project will generate *at least* for society, compensating the combined capital and operation expenditures as well as negative environmental externalities associated to the project. It serves to demonstrate the long-term sustainability of the proposed new scientific research infrastructure.

2.3. ASSUMPTIONS

2.3.1. Option analysis and project identification

Since several decades, the particle physics community has been discussing and considering different post High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC) scenarios, all aiming at further exploring the Higgs mechanism and providing knowledge advancement in fundamental physics. These scenarios are quite different in terms of technical features (e.g. scientific research programme, performance, particle accelerator type and size, number of experiments, location, leveraging of existing assets such as pre-existing particle accelerators etc.). **A strategic options analysis has been implemented by the international scientific research community as a first step of the socio-economic impact analysis** to identify the priorities, as recommended by the European Commission (2021 and 2014). The rationale for this analysis comes from the awareness that any investment entails the decision of not undertaking another option. Therefore, the impact analysis model considers **the impacts expected to be generated by the FCC-ee only**. To present the *net* direct and incremental impacts of the project, this analysis will include a comparison of the estimated impacts of the FCC-ee with a “without-the-project scenario” (counterfactual scenario), which is discussed in Section 2.3.4.

The FCC-hh project, the second phase of the FCC integrated programme, which extends the scientific research programme until the end of the 21st century is not considered in the analysis. It is not possible to make credible socio-economic estimates with a meaningful level of detail and degree of confidence on such timescales.

Finally, **the socio-economic impact analysis presented herein assumes an FCC-ee project with four major experiments.**

2.3.2. Time horizon and schedule

Figure 1 outlines the hypothetical project schedule considered for the socio-economic study. It ranges from the design of the infrastructure to the end of the operation phase of the FCC-ee. According to the latest FCC timeline, pre-investment feasibility studies began in 2021 and are expected to continue until 2028. The first investment costs are planned for 2029. The design and construction of the technical infrastructure, injector, collider, and experiments will proceed in parallel, each following its own timeline (as described in the Table 2 below).

Table 2: Detailed timeline

	Design phase	Construction phase
Civil engineering and technical infrastructure	January 2027 - December 2032	January 2033 - June 2042 (technical infrastructure installed)
Injector	January 2028 - December 2031	From January 2032 to December 2040, with hardware (HW) commissioning completed by December 2041 and beam commissioning (start of experimental physics with injector) by January 2042
Collider	January 2032 - December 2038	Procurement, implementation, and installation will take place between January 2039 and December 2044
Experiments	January 2034 - December 2038, after a collaboration-building period from 2029 to 2031	Construction from January 2039 to June 2042, with installation conducted from June 2042 to December 2044

Source: Authors

The particle collider and experiments are foreseen to transit from construction to operation by 2045, with a commissioning period in 2046 and 2047 and initial particle collisions occurring in 2048. The final year of operation is 2062, with the following two years expected for further data analysis. The operation phase is assumed to last until 2062 with data analysis to occur for two years more, until 2064. In total, **the observed time horizon for the socio-economic impact study covers 41 years, from 2024 to 2064**. Past costs – related to pre-investment feasibility studies and incurred before 2024 - have been capitalised (using the GDP deflator) and included in the first year of analysis (discussed in Section 3.1.2).

Figure 1: FCC-ee schedule used for the socio-economic impact analysis

Source: Authors

2.3.3. Expressing benefits in monetary terms: currency and the Social Discount Rate

2.3.3.1. Unit of measure

To compare the value of benefits among each other and with costs, they have to be expressed using the same unit of measure. In principle, any accounting unit (also called "numeraire" in the literature³) can be used.

For this analysis, costs and benefits are reported in Swiss Francs (CHF). They are all expressed in real (constant) and non-inflation and purchasing power adjusted term, in line with the European Commission guidelines (see European Commission 2021 and 2014).

All costs and benefits are expressed in 2024 prices and an average exchange rate over the year 2024 between CHF and all other currencies used in the analysis has been applied when currency conversion was needed (see the tables with exchanges rates used in Annex 8.1). Monetary values do not represent financial cash flows but rather social welfare metrics typically used in CBA which capture changes in agents' utility.

2.3.3.2. Social Discount Rate

Costs and benefits occur at different points in time and are spread over different and long periods. Therefore, a way must be found to express them consistently and comparably at the time at one specific point in time. The Social Discount Rate (SDR) is a parameter used in the economic analysis of investment projects when inter-temporal investment decisions⁴ have to be taken (see Annex 8.2 for more details). The social discount rate has been calculated based on the Social Rate of Time Preference (SRTP), which considers the social preferences and welfare of both current and future generations. Specifically, the following formula has been applied.

$$SDR = SRTP = p + \varepsilon * g$$

The table below summarises the source of data used for each variable entering this formula. More details on the values used for calculation are presented in Annex 8.2.

Table 3: Input for SDR calculation

	Variable	Sources
p The pure time preference	It is proxied with the annual mortality rate of the population, assuming that consumption is anticipated when the risk of death or human race extinction increases	Eurostat value for 2022-2041 or the world bank value for 2021-2040 as alternative
g The expected per-capita growth rate of consumption	It is proxied by the real growth rate of the per-capita GDP under the assumption that the GDP properly reflects the dynamics of consumption over time	Forecasts by the OECD - covering the period 2022-2041 when available, the past growth 2000-2019 rate provided by the world bank as alternative
ε The elasticity of marginal utility of consumption	It is proxied by using social preferences revealed by taxation	OECD taxation database for 2022, or when not available, the value estimated through value transfer (average between the regression and ml estimate considering data for 2000-2019)

Source: Authors

³ Florio, M. and Pancotti C. (2023).

⁴ When decision is taken today about using resources that are not available now, but will be in a future time.

By applying the formula above, we estimated the SDR in each country that contributes to the CERN budget today, including CERN Members States and Associated Countries. Then, we estimated the average of the SDR in each country, weighted by the respective contribution to the CERN budget.⁵

The resulting **SDR value determined by this calculation is 2.8%**. It was used to calculate the discounted value of costs and benefits preliminary presented in this document.

2.3.4. Counterfactual scenario

2.3.4.1. Context, definition, and rationale

The socio-economic impact model serves to estimate the incremental benefits of the FCC-ee. This means that **both the costs and benefits of the project are expressed in incremental terms and not in absolute terms compared to a scenario in which the project is not implemented. This scenario is called the “counterfactual scenario”** (Florio M. and Pancotti, C. 2023). It is prescribed for use by different national and international operative guidelines that foresee an incremental impact assessment approach for the evaluation of public investments in different sectors, such as environment, road transport, and others. Countries with the longest traditions of project appraisal include the UK (HM Treasury, 2018), France (Quinet, 2007, 2013) and the United States of America (US General Accounting Office, 2007).

This method aims to grasp the “net” change, i.e. the causally related changes that can be specifically attributed to the project. The changes can be positive or negative.

The choice of the counterfactual scenario requires a careful examination and implies defining what would happen in the absence of the project. Different options are available. In some cases, when the facility is completely new (a so called "green field" investment), the without-the-project scenario can be a ‘zero-based’ scenario. In other words, the incremental scenario coincides with the ‘with-the-project’ scenario. Examples of *green field* research infrastructures are the National Hadrontherapy Centre for Cancer Treatment (CNAO) based in Pavia (Italy) and the Jules Horowitz Reactor (JHR) built on the Cadarache site in France. In other cases, when investments are made to either substantially upgrade or reconvert an existing facility, use or leverage existing infrastructures, the counterfactual scenario should include the costs and benefits to operate and maintain it at a level that keeps it operable. This scenario is referred to as ‘business as usual’ or ‘do-nothing’ with minor investments that are programmed to avoid interruption of the service (do-minimum). Examples of *incremental* research infrastructures are the High Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC) at CERN and the upgrade of the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF) in Grenoble. The FCC-ee project also responds to the definition of incremental infrastructure: while it is a completely new research infrastructure, it requires and leverages CERN's existing assets (e.g. land, electricity and water distribution infrastructures, offices, workshops, telecommunications, particle accelerators, collaborative working spaces, conference and meeting facilities, visitor centres, administrative infrastructures, legal and operative frameworks, collaborations and personnel put in place by CERN over several decades).

⁵ Latest information gathered by 2023 CERN budget <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2888205/files/English.pdf>

2.3.4.2. Business as usual scenario

The results of the discussions with members of the particle physics, particle accelerator and high-energy physics community, with project external scientists and economists led to the preference of selecting the **“Business-as-usual” (BAU) continuation at CERN scenario as the most credible counterfactual scenario for the FCC-ee** (even if other accelerator concepts and scientific programmes are a matter of ongoing discussion in the physics community). When analysing the costs and benefits of the project, we assume that the HL-LHC will continue its operations until its expected end of life, estimated around 2040 (Bastianin and Florio, 2018), - with no new particle collider constructed afterwards. The possibility to continue with minor capital investments to the existing infrastructure to further prolong its lifetime has been considered not credible, since the science opportunities through extended operation would be negligible, but the maintenance and operation costs would be significant, thus leading to an unsustainable scenario. Nevertheless, the counterfactual scenario may change in the future if feasible alternatives to FCC-ee would be considered within the global scientific community

The BAU scenario adopted for the socio-economic impact assessment is coherent with the “evolution without-the-project scenario” applied for the environmental evaluation.

In the estimation of all benefits for the FCC-ee project, we paid attention to consider only those ones that would be generated by the FCC-ee project, but that are not already directly attributed to the HL-LHC. For instance, the cost-benefit analysis of the HL-LHC (Bastianin and Florio, 2018) identified some benefits that would materialise after the project’s end of life, until 2080 (for instance, cultural and educational benefits). These benefits were not attributed to the FCC-ee project, even if they occur during the same time period.

No costs for the dismantling and disposal of the LHC included in the FCC-ee project scenario. The LHC is assumed to remain in place even if no longer operational. Some additional costs will be necessary to make the machine and the tunnel suitable for the next generation FCC-hh project, but they remain out of the scope of this analysis. The no longer used particle accelerator and some of the experiments are assumed to serve as additional science tourist attractions based on the strong and persistent interest of CERN visitors to actually see the tunnel, the caverns, the particle accelerators and the detectors.

Decommissioning would take place in the scenario without FCC-hh. It entails the complete shutdown and safe disposal of all FCC-ee-related infrastructure. Since there is currently no cost estimation for this activity, in the baseline scenario – see Table 1 (Executive Summary) - it is assumed that these costs are at least equal to the dismantling costs estimated by CERN for the FCC-hh scenario (see Section 3.1.4 for details).

3. FCC-EE PROJECT COSTS

3.1. CAPEX AND OPEX

3.1.1. Assumptions

A socio-economic impact analysis relies on an estimate of resource engagements within the scope of the analysed project. Today, at an early exploratory stage of the feasibility study, the level of detail of the research infrastructure design is expected to continue evolving. Therefore, a pragmatic approach has been taken to establish a working hypothesis of estimated resource engagements and costs based on the concept of Reference Class Forecasting, a well-established and remarkably reliable approach that is by now established best practice in managing successful megaprojects (Lovallo and Kahneman, 2003; Flyvbjerg 2008 and 2011). The methodology adopted to structure the estimates was developed following the StR-ESFRI "Guidelines on cost estimation of research infrastructures" (2019) and the European Commission's "Guide to Cost-Benefit Analysis of Investment Projects" (2021 and 2014). These documents provide a reference framework for the identification and measurement of costs of any research infrastructure.

The following main assumptions are made:

- **Time profile:** Costs estimates are provided over the observation period of 41 years, from 2024 (assumed starting year for this analysis) until 2064 (assumed last year of exploitation of the FCC-ee results).
- **Unit of measure:** Values are expressed in CHF at 2024 prices.
- **Cash flow approach:** The cost accounting follows a cash flow method. Depreciation, reserves, price and technical contingencies and other accounting items which do not correspond to actual flows are disregarded. For in-kind contributions, their corresponding economic value has been considered.
- **Scenarios:** Costs estimates are produced for a baseline scenario.
- **Cost items considered:** A distinction between investment (CAPEX) and operation (OPEX) costs is made. Investment costs relate to the acquisition and development of durable, tangible and intangible, assets, necessary to enter the operation phase. They include pre-investment costs, including feasibility studies and design activities. Operation costs include all disbursements (both in-kind and outflows) needed to operate, maintain and repair the FCC-ee research infrastructure elements during the entire project time horizon. As part of the baseline scenario presented in Table 1 (see Executive Summary), decommissioning costs have been considered to take into account the costs needed to ensure the complete shutdown and safe disposal of all FCC-ee-related assets at the end of its lifetime. Moreover, costs related to environmental externalities have been quantified.

3.1.2. Investment costs

For this analysis, the FCC-ee project is conceived as a design-to-cost project, with a **total investment of around 16.2 billion CHF (not discounted) in the baseline scenario**, including both the machine, radiofrequency for ttbar operation⁶ and total costs of four experiments. Table 4 below shows the different investment cost items, their foreseen years of occurrence and the total value expressed as an average expected cost.

Table 4: Investment costs: structure and assumptions (not discounted)

Item	Domain	Start year of investment	Years of investment	Year of completion	Average expected cost [CHF]
Pre-investment and pre-construction studies	Studies	2021	11	2032	200,000,000
Collider magnets	Accelerator	2038	6	2044	915,000,000
Collider radiofrequency	Accelerator	2038	6	2044	580,000,000
Collider vacuum chambers	Accelerator	2038	6	2044	921,000,000
Power converters	Accelerator	2038	6	2044	701,000,000
Power converters for ttbar	Accelerator	2054	3	2057	5,000,000
Element support and alignment	Accelerator	2038	6	2044	230,000,000
Beam transfer elements	Accelerator	2038	6	2044	65,000,000
Beam intercepting devices	Accelerator	2038	6	2044	117,000,000
Beam intercepting devices for ttbar	Accelerator	2054	3	2057	32,000,000
Beam instrumentation and diagnostics	Accelerator	2038	6	2044	207,000,000
Protection and interlock systems	Accelerator	2038	6	2044	61,000,000
Controls	Accelerator	2038	6	2044	33,000,000
Machine-Detector Interface	Accelerator	2040	5	2045	28,000,000
Machine-Detector Interface, 2 additional interaction points	Accelerator	2040	5	2045	28,000,000
Polarisation and energy calibration	Accelerator	2040	5	2045	21,000,000
ttbar main and top-up ring RF + cryo + technical infrastructure	Accelerator	2049	8	2057	1,139,000,000

⁶ Radiofrequency for $t\bar{t}$ operation refers to the use of electromagnetic waves to accelerate and control protons in a particle accelerator. The RF system provides energy to the protons, keeping them in stable bunches and increasing their speed for high-energy collisions, which are necessary to produce top-antitop ($t\bar{t}$) quark pairs in experiments like those at the Large Hadron Collider.

Linear accelerator	Injector	2034	6	2040	247,000,000
Positron production	Injector	2034	6	2040	34,000,000
Damping ring and beam lines	Injector	2034	6	2040	72,000,000
Technical infrastructures	Injector	2032	4	2036	80,000,000
Transfer lines	Injector	2041	2	2043	152,000,000
Cryogenics	Infrastructure	2036	8	2044	207,000,000
Cryogenics, additional 2 interaction points	Infrastructure	2036	8	2044	3,000,000
Electricity infrastructure and energy management	Infrastructure	2036	6	2042	650,000,000
Electricity infrastructure, 2 additional interaction points	Infrastructure	2036	6	2042	6,000,000
Cooling and Ventilation	Infrastructure	2036	6	2042	827,000,000
Transport and logistics	Infrastructure	2035	5	2040	176,000,000
Transport and logistics, 2 additional interaction points	Infrastructure	2035	5	2040	11,000,000
Computing, data services, fibres	Infrastructure	2036	6	2042	85,000,000
Geodesy and survey	Infrastructure	2034	8	2042	373,000,000
Access, safety, radiation & environment monitoring	Infrastructure	2038	4	2042	200,000,000
Subsurface civil engineering	CE	2033	8	2041	4,310,000,000
Subsurface structures, 2 additional interaction points	CE	2033	3	2036	0
Surface structures	CE	2040	5	2045	504,000,000
Excavated materials management	CE	2033	8	2041	770,000,000
CE planning, management, architecture, landscaping	CE	2031	14	2045	704,000,000
400 kV connection to grid in France	Territorial development	2030	10	2040	30,000,000
20 kV connections	Territorial development	2028	5	2033	30,000,000
Land plot, agriculture and environment-related costs	Territorial development	2039	10	2049	35,000,000

Access related costs	Territorial development	2028	5	2033	52,000,000
Water transport-related costs	Territorial development	2037	5	2042	4,000,000
Administrative processes	Territorial development	2027	6	2033	40,000,000
Experiment 1	Experiment	2039	7	2046	365,000,000
Experiment 2	Experiment	2039	7	2046	365,000,000
Experiment 3	Experiment	2039	7	2046	300,000,000
Experiment 4	Experiment	2039	7	2046	300,000,000
TOTAL					16,215,000,000

Note: these costs have been provided by a cost review panel to FCC study management which ensures they are valid for approximately five years. It is based on various construction, materials, and equipment price trends observed over the past 15 years. **Source:** Authors.

Investments will be made gradually after the decision to construct from ca. 2028 to 2040. Some reinvestments will be made during the operation. Pre-investment costs are also included in the estimation

According to European Commission guidelines (2014 and 2021), any residual value of assets should be accounted for—with a negative sign—in the last year of the infrastructure’s life, reflecting that the assets retain value beyond their operational life and may have a potential market for reuse. While recognizing that this infrastructure is designed to support two particle colliders in sequence—the FCC-ee and the FCC-hh—this study adopts a precautionary approach by focusing exclusively on the first phase of the integrated program, namely, the construction of the FCC-ee. Therefore, the residual value of the FCC-ee assets has not been included in the baseline scenario estimation, as the decision to proceed with the FCC-hh cannot be assumed as granted at this stage. An estimation of this value has been provided as an additional benefit in Section 5.1, should the FCC-hh be built.

Box 2: Excavated materials management

The construction of a new underground infrastructure to host the FCC machines is expected to generate about 8.2 million cubic meters (m³) of materials after excavation, with a distribution of about 95% molasse, 2% calcareous deposits (limestone) and 3% quaternary post-glacial and interglacial deposits.

According to the MATEX Cost Estimate Review⁷, three scenarios have been identified for the disposal or reuse of excavated materials: A, B and C, specifically:

- For scenario A, all the material (polluted and non-polluted) is transported by truck to disposal facilities and quarries without any treatment on-site or local valorisation. The distance of treatment centres in Switzerland is 70 km (for type B material) and 15 km (for type E and type A material). In France, polluted materials are sent to ISDND (100km), and non-polluted materials to ISDI in priority and then quarries (35 km). This scenario is expected to cost around 698 MCHF, undiscounted⁸.
- For scenario B, French non-polluted material is sent to quarries at the proximity of the shaft (35 km away). French polluted material is treated on site. After de-pollution on-site, the material is sent by trucks to quarries for backfilling (no local reuse) at a distance of 65 km. The distance of treatment centres in Switzerland is 70 km (for type B material) and 15 km (for type E and type A material). This scenario is expected to cost around 684 MCHF, undiscounted⁹.
- For scenario C, all polluted and non-polluted material is treated on-site. Specifically, French material from experiment sites (PA, PD, PG, PJ) is reused in the vicinity of the shafts; non-polluted material from these sites is also used for landscaping. Material from technical sites (PF, PH, PL) is sent towards quarries in the proximity of the shaft for landfilling purposes (25km away). The distance of treatment centres in Switzerland is 70 km (for type B material) and 15 km (for type E and type A material). This scenario is expected to cost around 448 MCHF, undiscounted¹⁰.

According to discussion held with FCC study management, scenario A would not comply with the current French legislation, which mandates that a certain percentage of excavated material is reused. As a result, it was decided to exclude scenario A from the cost estimation and to use the weighted average of the overall costs for material transport, disposal and the construction of the treatment facilities in scenarios B and C as the baseline (i.e. 600 MCHF). On top of the costs related to the transportation and the construction of the treatment facilities, an additional 170 MCHF of energy consumption, maintenance costs, and manpower for the sorting facilities need to be added to obtain the final estimate. The best-case and worst-case scenarios correspond to scenarios B and C, respectively. Considering the additional 170 MCHF of manpower, energy, and maintenance costs needed to sort materials, the best-case and the worst-case scenarios become 618 MCHF and 854 MCHF respectively.

Source: Authors

⁷ FCC-2411231450-LUL-MATEX_Cost_Estimate_Review-V000.3 approved by CERN on 09/01/2025

⁸ These costs do not include energy, manpower and maintenance of the disposal facilities, which is added at a later phase

⁹ Ibid

¹⁰ Ibid

Figure 2 below depicts the time profile of FCC-ee total investment costs. It was developed by distributing the total expected investment costs over time based on when investments for each subsystem are expected. Specifically, the distribution accounts for a gradual ramp-up of expenses, following a realistic scheduling scheme, and incorporates a two-year payment delay relative to the expected completion of investments for each item (excluding pre-investment studies). This delay is typical when payments are tied to the acceptance of deliverables. It is worth pointing out that this curve represents the annual investment costs. The actual cash inflow to CERN as well as the actual outflow to contractors, may differ—and likely will. However, this is not intended to be a financial planning study.

Figure 2: Time profile of FCC-ee total investment costs – Baseline Scenario (CHF, not discounted)

Source: Authors

Table 5: FCC-ee total estimated investment cost – Baseline Scenario (Million, CHF).

Investment costs	Not Discounted	Discounted
Baseline scenario	16,215	10,171

Source: Authors

3.1.3. Operation costs

Operation costs include all disbursements (both in-kind and outflows) needed to operate, maintain, and repair the FCC-ee research infrastructure during the entire project time horizon. As highlighted by the StR-ESFRI guidelines (2019), operation costs tend to be constant when the project is running at full capacity. Typical operation costs of a research infrastructure which are considered for the FCC-ee analysis include personnels and other costs needed to ensure the proper functioning of the facility.

Personnel

The current FCC-ee design foresees four experiments and is planned to involve a **cumulative number of approximately 258,000 person-years** over its lifetime - encompassing design, construction, operation, and data analysis phases. This diverse group consists of scientists, engineers, technicians, administrative staff,

doctoral and postdoctoral researchers, undergraduate and Master’s students, and apprentices¹¹. Of the total personnel, around 11% are expected to work on particle accelerators and technical infrastructures, while the remaining 89% will focus on detectors and experimental physics. Table 6 below outlines the estimated number of personnels in FCC-ee projects, distinguishing between the two main project segments: collaborative experiments and particle accelerator & technical infrastructures. These estimates were provided by FCC study management and rely on a conservative scaling of LHC experiments and CERN’s historical human resource data (1993–2024).

Table 6: Number of person-years, summary results

2024-2064	Accelerator & infrastructure	Experiments (1+2+3+4)	Total
Scientists	3,320	33,783	37,103
Post docs	6,690	61,453	68,143
Engineers	2,420	47,735	50,155
Technicians	7,489	16,270	23,759
Administration	1,303	2,124	3,427
Doctoral students	3,735	44,142	47,877
Other students	1,850	24,406	26,256
Apprentices	788	600	1,388
Total	27,594	230,513	258,107
SHARE	11%	89%	100%

Source: Authors

As shown in Figure 3 below, these personnel will be involved in the FCC-ee programme since 2028 and will follow a ramp-up phase, increasing from a minimum of 495 persons in 2028 to a maximum of 15,428 in 2060 during the operational phase.

¹¹ These personnel estimates do not consider persons participating in civil engineering construction activities and persons who are directly employed by contractors. Those are under the responsibility of those companies and bidder groups.

Figure 3: Number of personnel per year involved in the FCC-ee programme by phase

Source: Authors

Two major FCC-ee experiments will have the potential to attract at least as many scientists and engineers as the two major LHC experiments, ATLAS and CMS. The other two experiments are expected to involve personnel numbers comparable to a single large LHC experiment, similar to ALICE and LHCb. Figure 4 below illustrates the number of personnel involved in the FCC-ee experiments. In total, approximately 162,000 personnel will be engaged in the two largest experiments (81,500 each) over 2028-2064 period while the two smaller experiments will involve a total of 67,500 personnel.

Figure 4: Number of personnel per year involved in the FCC-ee by experiments

Source: Authors

The Figures below provide details on the number of personnel involved in the FCC-ee programme by distinguishing by categories and the two project segments (collaborative experiments and particle accelerator & technical infrastructures).

Figure 5: Number of personnel per year involved in the FCC-ee programme by categories

Source: Authors

Figure 6: Number of personnel per year involved in the FCC-ee accelerator and infrastructure by categories

Source: Authors

Figure 7: Number of personnel per year involved in the FCC-ee experiments by categories

Source: Authors

Of the total personnel-year count (258,107), approximately 21% (55,000) consists of CERN staff, who are predominantly based at CERN and actively involved in both the accelerator and infrastructure segments, as well as in the experiments. The remaining 79% (203,000) members of the collaborations, employed by partner institutions - located across high-income, middle-income, and low-income countries - and working to a larger extent on experiments and mostly for limited time period (specifically scientists and post-doc). These

institutions actively contribute to CERN’s experiments by providing expertise, resources, and personnel as part of international collaborative efforts.

Table 7 summarizes the number of personnel-years involved in the FCC-ee program, distinguishing between project’s segments and identifying those managed by CERN and those affiliated with other institutions (see also Table 91 in Annex 8.3 for more details). Figure 8 below illustrates the time evolution of personnel, distinguishing between employer institutions.

Table 7: Number of personnel-years managed by CERN and by other institutions, summary results

	Total cumulative number of personnel involved in the FCC-ee programme	Total cumulative number of personnel involved in the FCC-ee programme paid by CERN	Total cumulative number of personnel involved in the FCC-ee programme paid by Other Institutions
Accelerator and Infrastructure	27,594 (11%)	21,460 (39%)	6,135 (3%)
Four experiments	230,513 (89%)	33,661 (61%)	196,852 (97%)
Total	258,107 (100%)	55,121 (100%)	202,986 (100%)
Share on the total	258,107 (100%)	55,121 (21%)	202,986 (79%)

Source: Authors

Figure 8: Number of personnel per year involved in the FCC-ee managed by CERN versus other institutions

Source: Authors

To accurately estimate personnel costs, a clear distinction was made between CERN staff and personnels employed by external institutions. This approach assumes that personnel costs should reflect i) the diverse economic contexts of their respective countries and ii) the actual time dedicated to CERN-related activities. To

account for the different economic contexts, two different average annual gross salaries were applied, as shown in the table below.

For personnel managed by CERN—particularly Scientists, Engineers, Technicians, and Administrative staff—we relied on salary estimates from a study carried out by Deloitte¹². For other personnel categories, such as Doctoral students, Postdocs, Undergraduate students (including Master’s students), and Apprentices, we used CERN’s own salary data.

For personnel managed by external institutions, we consulted various sources¹³ which indicate that these salaries are, on average, 20% lower than those applied to personnel managed by CERN.

Table 8: Total assumed labour costs per person by job category (CHF)

	CERN (CHF)	SOURCE	OTHER INSTITUTIONS (CHF)
Scientist	211,915	CERN's current salary scale.	169,532
Post-doctoral student	84,318	Salary values outlined in the STATUT ET RÈGLEMENT DU PERSONNEL (updated on January 1, 2025), Page 72.	67,454
Engineer	129,870	Deloitte study’s estimation	103,896
Technician	78,681	Deloitte study’s estimation	62,945
Administration	58,725	Deloitte study’s estimation	46,980
Doctoral student	43,515	Bases on https://careers.cern/salary-conditions . 25% overheads were excluded for this analysis.	34,812
Undergraduate students	38,835	Bases on https://careers.cern/salary-conditions . 25% overheads were excluded for this analysis.	31,068
Apprentices	12,885	Based on CERN’s data. The salary is paid by CERN, and it does not include overheads	10,308

Source: Authors

In addition, for scientists managed by external institutions, we applied the following assumptions to accurately attribute their personnel effort to FCC-ee:

- In line with Nature’s 2016 jobs survey¹⁴, we assumed that scientists allocate approximately 55% of their time to scientific research and writing articles, while the remaining 45% is dedicated to administrative duties, teaching, grant writing, outreach, and other activities¹⁵ in their home institution.
- Within the time dedicated to research and based on expert opinions validated by FCC study management, only a portion (22%) of their research effort is devoted to FCC-ee-related activities, with the rest allocated to other experiments. In line with that, the share was estimated by considering the LHC-related

¹² Provision of corporate development organisational, financial, legal and tax consultancy services at CERN”, Deloitte, 6 Place de la Pyramide, 92800 Pteaux, France, CERN Purchase Requisition 10697471, June 2024

¹³ Morretta V., Vurchio D. and Carrazza S. (2022), Eurostat, OECD, Glassdoor.

¹⁴ <https://www.chemistryworld.com/careers/time-after-time-how-academic-researchers-spend-their-working-life/2500016.article>.

¹⁵ Giffoni, F., Sirtori, E., & Colnot, L. (2024) suggest 65%. The uncertainty related to this parameter will be treated with a Monte Carlo analysis.

products produced by scientists as compared to their total scientific output, basing on Giffoni, F., Sirtori, E., & Colnot, L. (2024).

Since the analysis is conducted in real (constant) terms, inflation is excluded from the cost calculations. As a result, the annual labour costs were assumed to remain constant throughout the entire project duration.

Table 9 provides a summary of the total costs of the personnel over the period 2028-2064.

Table 9: Personnel costs, summary results (CHF)

2028-2064	Discounted	Not Discounted	Share
Personnel cost for the entire FCC-ee programme (A+B) or (C+D)	7,544,201,718	16,802,168,088	
(A) Personnel cost managed by CERN	2,383,709,068	4,903,561,514	29%
(B) Personnel cost managed by other institutions	5,160,492,650	11,898,606,574	71%
(C) Personnel cost accelerator & infrastructure	1,205,071,940	2,248,083,533	13%
(D) Personnel cost experiments (1+2+3+4)	6,339,129,778	14,554,084,555	87%

Source: Authors

The figures below show the estimated trend of personnel costs.

Figure 9: Labour costs covered by CERN and by the worldwide collaborations (CHF, not discounted)

Source: Authors

Figure 10: Labour costs for Accelerator & Infrastructure versus Experiments (CHF, not discounted)

Source: Authors

Other operational costs

In addition to personnel, the following operational costs are included in the analysis:

- **Maintenance and repair:** they include the equipment and materials costs necessary for keeping the buildings and the facilities in good condition including expenditures to fix broken parts and replacement of spare parts. In addition to ordinary maintenance costs, they include some costs that will occur during the operation phase for the replacement and upgrade of some fixed assets. For instance, they include the repair and maintenance of tunnels and buildings, maintenance and repair of cryogenic systems, maintenance and repair of magnet systems, and maintenance and repair of 4 experiments (covered mainly by other institutions). These costs have been estimated by CERN based on the latest data available from CERN financial statement 2023.
- **Goods and services:** they refer to any raw or (semi)processed materials and components necessary for the project operation, including their transport costs from the source of supply to the facility. For the FCC-ee they refer to consumables related to electronics and electrical engineering, IT radiation monitoring and protection equipment, radiofrequency equipment, office materials and other materials that are needed for day-to-day operation. Insurance costs and other industrial service contracts are included. All these costs are estimated by considering the historical CERN operational expenditure for the years 2019-2023 and the quantity of goods and services expected to be consumed by the project.
- **Communication, meetings, and events:** it includes promotional campaigns, the organisation of scientific conferences and workshops and other outreach expenditures associated with the FCC-ee project
- **Cryogenics:** consumables used by the FCC-ee project include the liquid helium (LHe) and nitrogen (LN) used as cryogenics. They are estimated by considering the historical CERN operational expenditure for the years 2019-2020 and the quantity of cryogenics expected to be consumed by the project. According to information shared by FCC study management, FCC-ee is not expected to make extensive use of gases.
- **Electricity and Water:** they are estimated by considering the estimated unit prices of the goods and the quantities expected to be consumed by the project. Specifically, as for electricity, following the FCC Sustainable Energy Supply concept developed by CERN, it is assumed that renewable energy sources would supply the major share of electricity with a price ranging from 75 to 85 EUR per MWh. As for water, the quantities have been updated to reflect newer, more accurate estimates. The baseline scenario corresponds to roughly 1.28 million m³/y¹⁶. The price considered is 0.85 CHF/m³.

The table below shows the average annual operation costs by domain, excluding the personnel costs.

¹⁶ This amount corresponds to the baseline waste heat scenario estimated by the FCC study management (5 km area, along with an adaptation of the schedule to meet the needs). Two additional scenarios (best and worst cases) have been proposed and will be used for the Monte Carlo simulation in a future revision of this analysis.

Table 10: Annual operating costs of FCC-ee by domain excluding personnel costs (CHF, not discounted).

	CHF	%	NOTES
Civil engineering and buildings	3,500,000		Based on CERN financial statements for 2023 and the assumption that the FCC buildings are all new.
Low temperature	1,300,000		Based on CERN financial statements 2023
Magnets	606,667		Based on CERN financial statements 2023
Particle detectors	10,000,000		Based on CERN financial statements 2023
Subtotal maintenance and repair	15,406,667	7%	
Electronics and electrical engineering	11,600,000		Based on CERN financial statements 2023
Health, safety and environment	2,267,667		Based on CERN financial statements 2023, assumed at 50% of CEPS
Information technology	12,000,000		Assumed at 80% of 2023 values (collaborations will cover at least part of them)
Measuring instruments	1,600,000		Assumed at 80% of 2023 values provided by CERN financial statements 2023
Mechanical engineering and raw materials	15,000,000		It includes a cooling and ventilation system. It is assumed 1.5% annually of 1 billion of investment
Office supply and equipment	1,200,000		Assumed at 80% of 2023 values provided by CERN financial statements 2023
Optics and photonics	450,000		Based on CERN financial statements 2023
Other supplies	200,000		Based on CERN financial statements 2023
Radiation equipment	15,000		Assumed that 50% of 2023 value will be accounted to FCC-ee
Radiofrequency systems (electrical, mechanical, electronics)	21,000,000		It is assumed 3% of the 700 million investment
Transport, handling and vehicles	1,200,000		Assumed at 80% of 2023 values provided by CERN financial statements 2023
Vacuum and particle detection equipment/supplies	2,800,000		Assumed at 80% of 2023 values provided by CERN financial statements 2023
Service contracts	42,400,000		Based on CERN financial statements 2023
Insurance	3,000,000		2019-2023 value
Transport	500,000		2019-2023 value
Subtotal goods and services	115,232,667	50%	

Communication	1,000,000		2019-2023 value
Training	1,000,000		2019-2023 value
Visits and conferences	2,910,000		2019-2023 value
Subtotal communication, meetings, events	4,910,000	2%	
Gases and chemicals	110,000		2019-2023 value
Subtotal cryogenics	110,000	0.0%	
Subtotal electricity	95,368,421	41%	Consumption and prices based on data provided by CERN (GHG emissions, OPEX). 22.65 TWh at 80CHF/MWh.
Subtotal water	1,088,631	0.5%	Based on waste heat scenarios. 24.3 mln m ³ at 0.85 CHF/m ³
TOTAL	232,116,385	100%	

Source: Authors

The costs are expected to fluctuate throughout the project's operation, depending on the operational phase. As illustrated in Figure 11 below, a slight decrease is observed in 2057. This is due to the absence of cryogenics-related costs that year, as the machine is planned to undergo an upgrade.

Based on these assumptions, other operational costs are estimated to be 4.4. billion CHF (not discounted) for the period 2046-2064.

Figure 11: FCC-ee other operational costs (CHF, not discounted)

Source: Authors

The total operation costs are expected to be around 21.2 billion CHF (not discounted) for the period 2028-2064. The majority of this amount (79%) - nearly 16.8 billion CHF (454 million CHF on average per year¹⁷) - are accounted for personnels. About 4.4 billion CHF (not discounted, on average 232 million CHF per year over a period of 19 years of operation¹⁸) are accounted for other operation expenses. The present value of the total operation costs after applying the discounting formula at 2.8% social discount rate is about 9.4 billion CHF for the entire period.

Figure 12: FCC-ee operation cost splitting working hypothesis.

Note: The breakdown is calculated by considering the total undiscounted value of costs by category over the entire FCC-ee time horizon. **Source:** Authors.

Figure 13 below shows the estimated trend of the total operating costs, including both personnel and other operational expenditures.

¹⁷ Personnel costs are distributed over 30 years, from 2028 to 2057/2064.

¹⁸ Other operating expenses are distributed over 19 years, from 2046 (the expected year of start of operation) to 2064.

Figure 13: Time profile of the total FCC-ee operating cost (CHF, not discounted).

Source: Authors

Table 11: Total FCC-ee operating costs (CHF).

Operating costs	Not discounted	Discounted
Baseline scenario	21,212,379,404	9,423,202,565

Source: Authors

3.1.4. Decommissioning costs

The baseline scenario presented in Table 1 (Executive Summary) focuses solely on the FCC-ee and does not take the decision of building FCC-hh for granted at this stage. Therefore, as part of the cost analysis, we have estimated the decommissioning costs required for the complete shutdown and safe disposal of all FCC-ee-related infrastructure at the end of its lifetime. Since no direct estimation of these costs is available, we have approximated them using the dismantling costs estimated at CERN¹⁹, although being aware that decommissioning costs are generally higher than dismantling costs.

Dismantling costs refer to the expenses required if the FCC-hh is built, covering the preparation for the subsequent infrastructure installation. These costs are estimated at approximately 216.2 MCHF (at 2023 prices) and are expected to be incurred in 2065 and 2066, following two final years of data analysis. CERN estimated these figures in November 2024 based on the dismantling costs of LEP. When adjusted to 2024 prices and evenly distributed across the two years, the total undiscounted cost amounts to 227.9 MCHF, with a discounted cost of 72.4 MCHF.

Table 12: Total FCC-ee decommissioning costs – (CHF, 2024)

	Not discounted	Discounted
Decommissioning costs	227,874,800	72,447,506

Source: Authors

¹⁹ FCC-2409231200-JPO-FCC-ee Dismantling-eng-V0100

3.2. NEGATIVE EXTERNALITIES

As part of the cost analysis associated with FCC-ee, the following negative environmental externalities have been identified and included in the assessment:

- Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions expected to be generated during both the construction of the tunnel and surface sites, as well as during the operation phase.
- Ionizing radiation that will be produced when particle beams collide with matter.
- Radioactive radiations that will be generated in the vacuum chamber as well as by beam scrapers, collimators, shields, bremsstrahlung main beam dumps and, to some extent, the magnet.
- Noise pollution expected to be generated during the construction.
- Changes in land use that could impact biodiversity and ecosystems
- Air pollution, GHG emissions, and congestion caused by the transportation of excavated material by trucks.

Overall, the total costs associated to these environmental externalities is expected to be around **653 million CHF** (not discounted), out of which the GHG emissions represent the largest share (97%).

Figure 14: Total FCC-ee environmental costs (CHF, not discounted)

Source: Authors

3.2.1. GHG emissions and shadow cost of carbon

Introduction

The negative externality is given by the **greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions** expressed in CO2 equivalent (CO2eq) generated by the FCC-ee project during both the construction of the tunnel and surface sites as well as the operation phase.

Estimation

➤ STEP 1 – Quantifying the GHG emissions

The quantities of CO₂ equivalent generated during the construction of the subsurface (the tunnel) and the surface sites (comprising four experimental and four technical sites) of FCC-ee were estimated in the context of an LCA study²⁰ conducted by WSP on behalf of CERN. The quantities are summarized in the table below. It is worth noting that the study did not include the GHG emissions associated with the construction of the accelerator itself. The estimated total emissions were distributed over the construction period according to the workflow.

Table 13: Tons of CO₂(eq) for the construction of the subsurface and the surface sites

Stage	Sub-surface	Experimental site*	Technical site*	Total*
A1 - A3 (Products)	364,301	6,716	2,153	399,777
A4 (Transport)	68,318	242	78	69,596
A5 (Construction)	44,771	204	173	46,279
B3 (Repair)	0	0	0	0
B4 - B5 (Usage)	0	282	12	1,177
B6 (energy)	0	0	0	0
C1 - C4 (decommissioning)	0	489	1,972	9,842
Total	477,390	7,934	4,387	526,671

Note: * the values for experimental and technical sites refer to a single site in the column with a total of four technical sites, and four experimental sites were considered. **Source:** Authors based on LCA study performed by WSP.

According to FCC study management, during operation, the FCC-ee will consume a total of 22.65 TWh of electricity, 80% of which is supplied by renewable energy sources (RES), assumed to be covered by wind power and solar PV.²¹ The remaining 20% will be purchased from the grid. It is assumed that this portion will be supplied by the French electricity grid, as is currently the case for the LHC. In the best-case scenario, the percentage of electricity from RES would increase to 95%, while in the worst-case scenario, it would decrease to 60%.

Some GHG emission optimization measures are planned for both the construction and operation phases. In the construction phase, GHG emissions are primarily driven by concrete and reinforced steel production. This creates opportunities for emission reduction through the establishment of new technical requirements, careful material selection, optimization of construction processes and improvements in energy efficiency. Overall, the FCC study management is confident in achieving a 2% reduction in emissions during construction. In the operation phase, reduced cooling needs due to waste heat re-use, improved design of certain accelerator components, and other targeted interventions are expected to reduce energy consumption by around 20%. These emissions reductions are reflected in the calculations.

²⁰ Carried out in line with the European standard Norm EN 17472, which provides requirements and guidelines for calculating and reporting GHG emissions associated with infrastructure projects

²¹ The feasibility of such endeavour has been explored in two high-level exploratory studies prepared by external consultants in 2023 (Accenture, McKinsey).

To quantify the CO₂eq emissions, appropriate emission factors are applied. Different energy sources produce different quantities of GHG emissions. For the share of RES electricity, the emission factors for off-shore wind and photovoltaic production are used, while for the share of mixed-sources (grid) electricity, the emission factor for electricity consumption in France is adopted. The table below shows the respective factors and the combined weighted factor. In line with the objective of achieving carbon neutrality by 2050, France plans to further reduce the carbon intensity of its electricity production by a factor of almost three by 2050²². In other words, the emission factor for the consumption of the French electricity grid is expected to decrease over time. Accordingly, a constant annual decrease is assumed in the baseline scenario (4%), in the best-case scenario (5%), and in the worst-case scenario (3%) until 2050.

 Table 14: CO₂(eq) intensity of FCC-ee electricity consumption during the operational phase

	Share	gCO ₂ eq/KWH (2024)	gCO ₂ eq/KWH (2046)	gCO ₂ eq/KWH (2050)
Baseline scenario				
Off-shore wind	60%	15.60	15.60	15.60
Photovoltaic	20%	25.20	25.20	25.20
Grid mix	20%	58.00	23.68	20.07
Combined factor	100%	26.00	19.10	18.41
Best-case scenario				
Off-shore wind	75%	15.60	15.60	15.60
Photovoltaic	20%	25.20	25.20	25.20
Grid mix	5%	58.00	18.76	15.28
Combined factor	100%	19.64	17.68	17.50
Worst-case scenario				
Off-shore wind	40%	15.60	15.60	15.60
Photovoltaic	20%	25.20	25.20	25.20
Grid mix	40%	58.00	29.68	26.27
Combined factor	100%	34.48	23.15	21.79

Source: ADEME Base Carbone for emission factors of off-shore wind, photovoltaic and FR consumption mix in 2024.

 Table 15: Total tCO₂(eq) emissions of FCC-ee

	Baseline	Best-case scenario	Worst-case scenario
Emissions related to the construction of the subsurface and surface structures	526,671	526,671	526,671
Scope 2 emissions related to operation	418,195	396,745	495,698
TOTAL	944,866	923,416	1,022,369
TOTAL OPTIMISED	850,693	833,534	912,696

Source: Authors

²² I. Tiseo, Carbon intensity outlook of the power sector in France from 2020 to 2050.

Figure 15: Total GHG emissions from the project during construction and operation

Note: The Figure refers to in the baseline scenario, non-optimised, in tCO2eq, 2030-2064. **Source:** Authors

➤ **STEP 2 – Monetisation**

The most recent estimate of the socio-economic value of one unit CO2eq is provided by the European Commission (2021) Vademecum for the economic appraisal.²³ One ton of CO2eq has a value of 148 EUR in 2024 (expressed in 2016 prices), equivalent to 144 CHF, increasing over time to reflect the increasing marginal cost for society from the production of an additional emission unit. By 2050, it is estimated at 800 EUR/ton (expressed in 2016 prices), equivalent to 777 CHF/ton. This value is then assumed to remain constant until the end of the time horizon.

By adjusting the 2016 prices with the GDP deflator, one ton of CO2eq has a value of 192 EUR in 2024 (expressed in 2024 prices), equivalent to 183 CHF. By 2050, it is estimated at 1,037 EUR/ton (expressed in 2024 prices), equivalent to 988 CHF/ton.

Results

Table 16 below presents the total externality (covering both the construction and operation phases) from GHG emissions attributable to the FCC-ee project. As noted in a previous paragraph, the present calculation of the total externality does not include the GHG emissions associated with the construction of the accelerator. In the baseline scenario, **the total externality amounts to 633 million CHF (undiscounted). The discounted present value of the externality is 341 million CHF.** In the worst-case scenario, the discounted value rises to 367 million CHF, while in the best-case scenario, it decreases to 334 million CHF.

²³ The French value (available in the 2020 *Complément opérationnel D* of the *Guide de l'évaluation socioéconomique des investissements publics* by France Stratégie) was also considered. However, we opted to use the more recent estimates from the EIB as reported by EC 2021. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that the two sets of estimates are similar. For reference on the French values estimated in 2019 by the commission chaired by Alain Quinet, see France Stratégie (2019).

Table 16: Total estimation - under different scenarios (CHF)

Scenario	Not discounted	Discounted
Baseline	633,079,473	341,308,153
Worst-case scenario	693,661,167	366,863,543
Best-case scenario	616,349,004	334,208,664

Source: Authors

3.2.2. Ionising radiation

Introduction

The FCC-ee will generate ionising radiation during the collision of particle beams with matter. Despite the modest contribution of the FCC-ee in terms of radioactive emissions compared to the natural amount of radiation already present in the environment, the cautionary approach, recommended by various guidelines²⁴, suggests the adoption of a linear dose-response curve with no threshold, thus including also very small increases in radiation.²⁵

Estimation

➤ STEP 1 – Quantifying the radioactive emissions

The Man-Sievert metric was chosen to quantify the exposure of individuals to ionising radiation. Measuring ionizing radiation in Man-Sievert allows measuring the biological impact of a collective dose of radiation for a group of people. For example, a collective dose of 1 Man-Sievert corresponds to 100,000 persons who receive 10 μ Sievert per year. This metric is widely adopted by the International Atomic Energy Agency and is the method used in France to estimate the radiological component of the environmental impact of nuclear power plants.

While the annual dose limit for public exposure from artificial sources in Europe is 1 millisievert (mSv), CERN commits to keeping its contribution below 0.3 mSv per year. The radiation emissions attributable to existing particle accelerators are even lower, estimated to be less than 0.01 mSv/y, equivalent to 10 microSievert/year (μ Sv/y)²⁶. The latter is the amount of exposure that is used for the quantification of ionizing radiation externalities. For context, the natural background level of ionizing radiation in the municipalities surrounding CERN ranges between 0.6 and 0.9 mSv/y.

To estimate the negative externality associated with radioactive emissions, the population affected by ionising radiation from FCC-ee has been identified, i.e. those residing and working near the emission source. CERN staff (occupationally exposed) were not considered because the number of people (without risking double-counting) remains uncertain. Moreover, they can be legally exposed to a higher regulatory limit of 6 mSv/year²⁷,

²⁴ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, ExternE – Externalities of Energy. Volume 5, Nuclear, Publications Office, 1995; INTERNATIONAL ATOMIC ENERGY AGENCY, Approaches to Cost-Benefit Analysis of New Nuclear Power Projects, IAEA Nuclear Energy Series No. NG-T-4.8, IAEA, Vienna (2024)

²⁵ The following analysis calculate the externality associated to the population exposure, while the exposure of fauna and flora is not considered, as it would be negligible given the already minimal radiation levels associated to the local population.

²⁶ See CERN. (2023).

²⁷ while the majority of radiation workers are subject to a regulatory limit of 6 mSv/year, a limit of 3 mSv/year is applied in practice. According to information produced by CERN (i.e. CERN environmental report 2023), there are no instances

and their salary generally accounts for the additional risks or inconveniences associated with the job (i.e. salary internalise, at least partially, the negative effects of radiation).

To estimate the number of persons exposed to ionizing radiation, a 300-meter radius from the 8 sites of the FCC infrastructure was drawn in every direction. This distance was chosen because, by applying the inverse square law, the intensity of the radiation decreases quadratically with the distance in meters from the access shaft. Assuming a maximum of 10 μSv (0.01 mSv) at the ventilation exit, therefore, gives 0.0001 μSv (0.000001 mSv) at 300 meters (a negligible exposure).

For each house and apartment building found within the 300m radius, the total amount of residents was calculated using data from the *Swiss Federal Statistical Office* and the *French National Institute of Statistics and Economic Studies*. The number of workers was obtained by estimating the number of employees for each economic activity found within the 300m radius. We assumed that residents spend 70% of their time at home while workers spend 33% of their time at their workplace. The total amount of people affected by radiation is estimated to be 1,522.

Table 17: Total number of inhabitants and workers potentially affected by radiation.

Site	Number of inhabitants (70%)	Number of workers (33%)	Total
PA, Ferney-Voltaire	689	437	1,126
PB, Presinge (CH)	15	0	15
PD, Nangy	50	79	129
PF, Eteaux	172	45	217
PG, Charvonnex/Groisy	8	2	10
PH, Marlioz	19	0	19
PJ, Dingy-en-Vuache et Vulbens	0	0	0
PL, Challex	7	0	7
Total	960	562	1,522

Source: Authors

of workers receiving a dose higher than 1,3 mSv/year in the 2021-2022 reporting period, and 91% of the workers registered a null dose (0 mSv). As a reference, the mean annual exposure to natural and artificial sources in Switzerland is 6 mSv per person per year.

➤ STEP 2 – Monetisation

Most nuclear regulatory authorities and utilities worldwide have adopted a single or a system of monetary values of ionising radiations, expressed in terms of €/man.Sv. This “reference monetary value of the man sievert” is constantly updated to reflect the state-of-the-art methodology in calculating the Value of Statistical Life. In 2020, the EDF²⁸ updated its reference monetary value to account for the most recent recommendations from the International Commission on Radiological Protection and the French State administration. The new reference value was estimated to be **4,500 €2017/man.mSv**.²⁹ This value applies to all levels of radiation exposure, contrary to the EDF’s previous approach of providing increasing values for increasing levels of absorbed doses.

Results

By multiplying the above reference monetary value of the man sievert with the annual dose of radiation exposure and the number of affected persons, it is possible to obtain the ionizing radiation-related externality. For each year of operation, the FCC-ee will cause a yearly negative externality of EUR 83,241.98. By multiplying this value by the number of years of operation — from 2047 to 2062, including one year of transition—a value of EUR 1,331,872 (or CHF 1,268,714) is obtained. The discounted value instead is estimated to be EUR 578,343 (or CHF 550,930).

Table 18: Total estimation – Baseline Scenario (CHF)

Scenario	Not discounted	Discounted
Baseline	1,268,741	550,930

Source: Authors

3.2.3. Radioactive waste

Introduction

The synchrotron radiation emitted by the high-energy leptons will strike the localised absorbers in the vacuum chamber and will induce radioactivity. Other areas expected to become radioactive are beam scrapers, collimators, shields, bremsstrahlung main beam dumps and, to some extent, the magnets. Elements that absorb a high fraction of the beam power will need to be considered as radioactive waste.

The disposal of radioactive waste is governed by the tripartite agreement on radiation protection and radiation safety between CERN and its Host States. Article 7 of this tripartite agreement, which defines the principles governing CERN's elimination of radioactive waste, allows CERN to eliminate radioactive waste in the two Host States by using the most technically and economically advantageous pathways in both countries.

Estimation

➤ STEP 1 – Quantifying the radioactive waste volume

None of the existing CERN accelerator facilities is required to be modified or dismantled ahead or for the FCC-ee construction and operation, which would lead to the production of radioactive waste. Therefore, no production of radioactive waste linked to the construction of the FCC-ee is expected.

FCC-ee will be operated in four phases (Z, W, H, and t \bar{b}) that are separated by shutdown periods to implement the required upgrades for the accelerator and the experiments. As FCC-ee will be an entirely new machine

²⁸ Électricité de France S.A.

²⁹ Andresz, S., Jobert T. and Schieber C. (2022).

designed to run without the need to replace large quantities of equipment during its operational lifetime, the expected volumes of radioactive waste generated during the operation of the FCC-ee, including its injector complex, should be small compared to the absolute size of the facilities.

As discussed in previous sections, this study focuses exclusively on the FCC-ee and does not assume a decision has been made to construct the FCC-hh. Based on this, it is expected that after the completion of the FCC-ee physics programme, a decommissioning phase for the FCC-ee booster and collider will begin. Since no direct estimate of the costs associated with this phase is currently available, we have approximated them using dismantling cost estimates provided by CERN, while acknowledging that decommissioning costs are generally higher than dismantling costs (see Section 3.1.4 for details). It is important to note that these decommissioning costs do not include the management of radioactive waste after the completion of FCC-ee. A rough estimate - amounting to approximately CHF 13.5 million³⁰ - is available but it was not included for the sake of prudence. A more accurate estimate will only be possible once the design is more detailed, and material specifications are defined³¹.

The table below summarises the roughly estimated volumes of radioactive waste for the different classes in this preliminary study phase of the FCC-ee.

Table 19: Estimates of radioactive waste volume for FCC-ee during the operation phase and dismantling

	Negligible activation (CL)	Very low activation (TFA)	Low and intermediate activation with short half- lives (FMA-VC)	Low and intermediate activation (FA- MA)
Operating phase				
Injector complex	< 50 m3 per year	< 5 m3 per year	< 1 m3 per year	-
FCC-ee accelerator	< 200 m3 per year	< 20 m3 per year	< 1 m3 per year	-
FCC-ee experiments	< 50 m3 per year < 100 m3 per LS	< 5 m3 per year < 10 m3 per LS	< 1 m3 per year < 5 m3 per LS	-
Total (15 years, 3 LS)	< 5000 m3	< 500 m3	< 60 m3	-
Dismantling phase				
FCC-ee accelerator	< 11,000 m3	< 8,000 m3	< 130 m3	< 10 m3
FCC-ee experiments	< 2,000 m3	< 1,000 m3	< 10 m3	-
Total	< 13,000 m3	< 9,000 m3	< 140 m3	< 10 m3

Source: Authors Note: LS stands for long shutdown.

➤ STEP 2 – Monetisation

The cost estimate for the disposal of radioactive waste from CERN's facilities is based on an inventory indicating the amount and radiotoxicity of present and future radioactive waste, i.e. waste stored at CERN and waste that will be produced by preventive and corrective maintenance or by the upgrade of CERN's facilities or experiments. Based on the information shared by the FCC study management, **the estimate for the elimination cost of future radioactive waste during operation (see table below) is already included in the operation budget (i.e. OPEX)**. This aligns with the approach suggested, for example, by the IAEA guide

³⁰ CERN, December 2024, Technical Note on Radioactive Waste Estimates for the FCC-ee, prepared by Occupational health, safety and environmental protection unit.

³¹ FCC-2409231200-JPO-FCC-ee Dismantling-eng-V0100

(2024), which foresees that all costs for the treatment and disposal of radioactive waste are typically ‘internalized’ as part of the operating costs of a nuclear power plant.

Table 20: Estimates for the elimination costs of radioactive waste produced by FCC-ee (CHF)

Total	Negligible activation (CL)	Very low activation (TFA)	Low and intermediate activation with short half-lives (FMA-VC)	Low and intermediate activation (FA-MA)
Operating phase				
2,200,000*	-	<500,000*	<1,700,000*	-

*15 years, 3 LS. **Source:** Authors

3.2.4. Induced noise

Introduction

FCC-ee is going to generate noise during both the construction and operation phases. The presence of noise in the vicinity of the construction sites carries a non-auditory cost on society, which is mainly related to sleep disturbance and annoyance. Other effects of noise include hypertension and loss of productivity.

Estimation

➤ STEP 1 – Quantifying the negative noise externality

Estimating the negative noise externality requires quantifying both the number of affected individuals and the intensity of the noise (noise levels) for the construction phase and for the operation phase. During construction, noise emissions primarily stem from the preparation and construction of the surface sites, the construction of the shaft, and the excavation of the underground infrastructure. During operation, the noise is mainly caused by the ventilation system for the underground structures.

To quantify the number of people exposed to noise from the FCC’s construction and operation, the number of inhabitants within 100-meter and 200-meter radii (the same distances as those used by the experts to measure background noise levels around each site) were estimated by counting the apartments within each area and multiplying by the average occupancy per home for each municipality using INSEE data. Similarly, the number of workers was estimated based on the number of employees in each activity within the area. To quantify noise levels, CERN collaborated with expert companies to conduct background noise measurements as part of the FCC environmental initial state analysis. Noise levels were recorded separately for day and night during different time periods. These background noise measurements are crucial for assessing if the additional noise generated by construction and operation activities is relevant or not. Subsequently, the FCC-ee noise levels during construction and operation near-surface sites were modelled by CERN experts, leveraging past measurements from CERN for the HL-LHC construction and LHC operation.

After accounting for commonly used mitigation measures at construction sites in inhabited areas, the expected noise levels are estimated to be 45 dBA at a distance of 100 m and 40 dBA at 200 m. These expected noise levels were then compared to the background noise levels at each site, as only the cost associated with the additional noise caused by the FCC-ee is considered for monetization purposes. The noise during operation, thanks to some mitigation measures, remains well below the 40 dBA threshold, both during the day and at night.

Table 21: Amount of noise expected in the main construction sites after accounting for commonly used mitigation measures

Site	Acoustic measurement point – L90	Construction noise [DB]	Operation noise [DB]	
			7h-22h	22h-7h
PA, Ferney-Voltaire	PA-PF01 (200m)	40.0	28.0	21.0
	PA-PF03 (300m)	40.0	26.0	19.0
	PA-PF02 (200m)	40.0	28.0	21.0
PB, Presinge (CH)	Point 3 (100m)	45.0	19.0	14.0
PD, Nangy	PD-PF48 (200m)	40.0	28.0	21.0
	PD-PF47 (200m)	40.0	28.0	21.0
PF, Eteaux	PF-PF38 (200m)	40.0	16.0	11.0
	PF-PF40 (200m)	45.0	19.0	14.0
	PF-PF43 (200m)	40.0	15.0	9.0
PH, Marlioz	PH-PF25 (100m)	45.0	35.0	34.0
	PH-PF28 (200m)	40.0	32.0	31.0
PL, Challex	PL-PF11 (200m)	40.0	32.0	31.0
	PL-PF22 (300m)	40.0	30.0	29.0

Source: Authors

The health effects of noise are generally considered relevant only above certain thresholds. This threshold varies depending on the guidelines adopted, as there is no consensus at the international level. More conservative estimates set the threshold at 40dB³², while other agencies place it at 45dB or higher³³.

The number of individuals affected by noise within a 100-meter radius of PH Marlioz and PB Presinge —the only two sites where construction noise is expected to have an impact exceeding 40dB — is 19. Since all these individuals are residents, it is assumed that they will spend 70% of their time at home (similar to the assumption made for radiation exposure), resulting in an estimate of around 13 people exposed to the noise.

➤ STEP 2 – Monetisation

For monetisation purposes, only those sites where a significant increase in the level of noise (+5 dB L90³⁴) is expected and the 45dB threshold is surpassed (see the red cells in Table 21) were considered. As illustrated in the previous section, in most cases, the mitigation measures are expected to reduce the noise. In a few cases, the expected increase in noise levels before and after construction operation is negligible. Concerning

³² See Meurisse, B. et al 2022.

³³ See Meurisse, B. et al 2022 and DEFRA 2014.

³⁴ Unit of measure of noise: it measures the amount of noise exceeded 90% of the time during the measurement period.

operation activities, the mitigation measures are expected to always reduce noise emissions to levels below 40 dB. For this reason, the noise emitted during the operation phase is not taken into account for monetization purposes.

The monetary value for noise was taken from a technical note on the social cost of construction noise from the French Ministry of Ecological Transition³⁵. This note specifically addresses construction-related noise within the French context, and it includes a lower threshold for measuring effects, down to levels below 50 dB, unlike most other studies. The note relies on the literature and proposes different monetary values dependent on noise levels which is applicable to any construction site. It does so by estimating first an annual cost (€₂₀₁₈2,620) related to a loss of well-being for an exposed individual, which is the result of applying a 2% disability coefficient to the value of a year of healthy life set at €₂₀₁₈131,000³⁶. The final value is then obtained by multiplying the annual cost by the number of people exposed to each level of noise by using the dose-response curves for annoyance shown in

Figure 16.

The noise from construction sites, especially during activities like demolition or heavy machinery operation, generates both low-frequency noise (e.g., engine sounds) and high-frequency noise (e.g., hammering). This noise is often intermittent and can create peaks in sound levels. The construction noise is therefore considered to have similarities to both road and rail traffic noise, as both sources also generate significant, varying noise levels. This approach is also acknowledged in technical note on the social cost of construction noise by French Ministry of Ecological Transition³⁷. For this reason, the midpoint between road and rail traffic noise externality values is chosen to reflect the varying nature of construction noise. In particular, at 45dB, the loudest construction site of FCC-ee, the cost of annoyance from road traffic is €₂₀₁₈208, while for rail, it is €₂₀₁₈88. Taking the midpoint results in obtaining a value of €₂₀₁₈148, or €₂₀₂₄185.37. These figures are based on the aforementioned technical note by the French Ministry of Ecological Transition.

Figure 16: Dose-response curves for annoyance caused by transport noise (road, rail, air)

Source: [Bruitparif, d'après OMS \(2018\)](#)

³⁵ Ministère Aménagement du territoire Transition écologique (2022) Le coût des nuisances sonores des chantiers: quelle intégration dans les évaluations socio-économiques de projets

³⁶ See Commissariat Général à la Stratégie et à la Prospective (2013).

³⁷ Ministère Aménagement du territoire Transition écologique (2022) Le coût des nuisances sonores des chantiers: quelle intégration dans les évaluations socio-économiques de projets ?

³⁸ The Lden (Level day evening night) is a weighted average of noise levels over 24 hours, adjusted for sensitivity to noise during three periods (6 a.m.–6 p.m., 6 p.m.–10 p.m., 10 p.m.–6 a.m.).

Results

The €₂₀₂₄185.37 figure represents the cost of annoyance per exposed person per year.

Multiplying the number of exposed persons by the annual cost per exposed person generates a yearly cost of around € 2,462, which, multiplied by the entire construction period, results in a total cost of around € 24,616 (or CHF 23,449). The discounted figure is instead around € 17,008 (or CHF 16,202).

Table 22: Total estimation – Baseline Scenario (CHF).

Scenario	Not discounted	Discounted
Baseline	23,449	16,202

Source: Authors

3.2.5. Loss of agricultural income, biodiversity and habitat

Introduction

The FCC project involves the construction of buildings and roads on predominantly agricultural and forested land. Consequently, the implementation of the project will result in **changes to land use** and activities conducted on it, thereby **impacting existing biodiversity and ecosystems**. While the integration of biodiversity and ecosystem services analysis into socio-economic evaluations remains a relatively limited practice, there is growing consensus on their importance both in France³⁹ and at the international level⁴⁰. Accordingly, in the context of this study, the **negative externalities** arising from the **loss of ecosystems' services value** due to the implementation of the FCC project have been evaluated.

Over 92% of the projected area presently reserved for the project is in France and 8% in Switzerland. France's Legal Framework mandates compulsory measures to compensate for forest clearance as well as for agricultural economy losses of a territory⁴¹ (Swiss law is comparatively stricter for forest protection, but presently, no forest clearance is planned on Swiss land). Additionally, in France, the Environmental Code, which focuses on biodiversity protection, requires the application of the "**Avoid-Reduce-Compensate**"⁴² (ERC) sequence during the design phase of any project impacting biodiversity (the principles of agricultural and forestry compensation do not fall under the Environmental Code but are governed respectively by the Rural and Maritime Fishing Code and the Forestry Code. Financial measures are possible in these cases, unlike biodiversity compensation, which must necessarily be carried out in kind). To implement this approach, CERN commissioned a study based on an ecological expert's judgement and IBP score attribution⁴³ to assess biodiversity presence on the target land. The study mapped and categorized the areas by the following type: very high/high/medium/low/very low biodiversity risk⁴⁴.

As the ERC approach requires ecological equivalence (=biodiversity gains at least equal to the biodiversity losses caused by the project), the residual impact on biodiversity to consider in the Cost Benefit Analysis is expected to be negligible once the design of the project is finalised (compensatory measures are currently under planning) and, at least **some of the ecosystem services losses are expected to offset as a result**. That said, in

³⁹ See Bernard Chevassus-Au-Louis, Jean-Michel Salles, Jean-Luc Pujol, Sabine Bielsa, Gilles Martin, et al (2009) and Ministère de l'Économie, des Finances et de la Relance - Direction Générale du Trésor, Évaluations économiques des services rendus par la biodiversité, 2021.

⁴⁰ See EIB 2023 (Chapter 5) and OECD, 2018 (Chapter 13), Compensations environnementale, forestière et collective agricole: évaluation et mise en cohérence, Rapport CGEDD n° 013246-01, March 2021.

⁴² <https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/politiques-publiques/eviter-reduire-compenser-impacts-lenvironnement>

⁴³ <https://www.cnpf.fr/ibp-index-biodiversity-potential>

⁴⁴ No "protected areas" were mapped within the project's perimeter

the context of this study, the negative externalities were assessed based on the information currently available on the project design.

The adopted ecosystem's services classification is based on the one introduced by TEEB – the Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity – Initiative in 2010 and then taken up in existing literature⁴⁵.

- Provisioning services (*which are the products obtained from ecosystems, including food, fresh water, fuel, fibre, biochemicals, and genetic resources*). The FCC project implementation will lead to the loss of provisioning services due to the cessation of agricultural and forestry activities on the total cadastral area planned to be acquired⁴⁶. As a result, raw materials and products (wood, agricultural products) from these areas will no longer be available.
- Regulating & habitat services (*which are the benefits obtained from the ecosystem's natural regulating process, including climate regulation, carbon sequestration, disease regulation, water regulation, etc.*), including biodiversity, which is in the literature often considered a supporting service, as it underpins the functioning of ecosystems (greater biodiversity generally translates into enhanced ecosystem resilience and a broader range of ecosystem services). The FCC project implementation will result in a change of land destinations. The most relevant regulating & habitat services loss derives from soil sealing due to construction activities.
- Cultural services (*which relate to the experiences that people enjoy as a result of interactions with nature (e.g. recreation), as well as more intangible pleasures arising from knowledge about the existence of nature or its spiritual value*). In the context of FCC, they were not considered for two main reasons: i) no significant recreational activity is currently present or planned on the land, and ii) the high level of discretion and variability (greater than the average of other ecosystem services) in value attribution of these services in existing studies and literature.

Estimation

➤ STEP 1 – Quantifying the negative externalities from ecosystem service loss

The quantification of negative externalities from ecosystem service loss is based on the estimation of impacted areas and the selection of ecosystems' services for which loss can be reasonably quantified.

The total area reserved for the project—the land planned to be acquired by CERN⁴⁷ — is 76.2 hectares, with 70.3 ha in France and 5.9 ha in Switzerland.

CERN has commissioned two specific studies to external experts to characterise the target land: a forest study finalized in September 2024 and an agricultural study. Of the reserved area, 18% was classified as forest land and 82% was classified as agricultural land, including cultivated areas and non-cultivated areas such as meadows and land used for grazing or hay production⁴⁸.

⁴⁵ E.g. L.M. Brander, R. de Groot, J.P. Schägner, V. Guisado-Goñi, V. van 't Hoff, S. Solomonides, A. McVittie, F. Eppink, M. Sposato, L. Do, A. Ghermandi, M. Sinclair, R. Thomas, Economic values for ecosystem services: A global synthesis and way forward, Ecosystem Services, Volume 66, 2024; Economic Appraisal of Investment Projects at the EIB – chapter 5: Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, 2nd edition, March 2023.

⁴⁶ No agricultural activity will be conducted by CERN on the plots acquired for the project's construction, even if no actual construction will take place on them. The agricultural space currently used for cultivation will be converted into uncultivated meadows, with no active agricultural activity

⁴⁷ The FCC project does not develop on land already owned by CERN; all land will be acquired.

⁴⁸ Constructed area is marginal and made by three houses and 0.3ha of asphalted area.

Table 23: Total area (cadastral area) reserved for the project (hectares).
Breakdown by site, location and type of land

Site	Total Area	<i>of which in France</i>	<i>of which in Switzerland</i>	<i>of which agricultural land</i>	Cultivated	<i>non cultivated</i>	<i>of which forest land</i>
PA	13.9	13.9		13.9	13.9	0	0
PB	5.9		5.9	5.9	5.9	0	0
PD	11.5	11.5		11.5	0	11.5	0
PF	8.3	8.3		8.3	0	8.3	0
PG	10.8	10.8		8.4	4.3	4.1	2.4
PH	11.3	11.3		0.8	0	0.8	10.5
PJ	8.9	8.9		8.9	8.9	0	0
PL	5.6	5.6		4.9	4.9	0	0.7
Total	76.2	70.3	5.9	62.6	37.9	24.7	13.6

Source: Authors

The FCC-related project activities which will be conducted in the reserved area⁴⁹ are the following:

- Construction of buildings.
- Construction of roads
- Creation of green buffers around the buildings (tree planting and meadows)
- Re-naturalization areas (wetlands improvement).

Buildings, roads and green buffers will be fenced, while re-naturalization areas will remain on the reserved area but unfenced. The fenced area covered by project interventions is 53.2 ha in the baseline scenario and 47.8 ha in the optimized one. The optimized scenario, currently under investigation, envisions a reduced fenced surface, less soil sealing and more green buffers. In both the baseline and optimized scenarios, 7.8 hectares of naturalization areas are included. The total area impacted by the project's interventions is thus 61.0 hectares (55.6 hectares optimized). The difference between the reserved area and the project's intervention area is made by the sum of portions of cadastral plots reserved for the project but not covered by interventions as well as access plots and access roads.

⁴⁹ Compensation measures also include interventions outside the reserved area, such as agricultural land restoration and reforestation activities designated by local authorities in other locations out of the project's perimeter.

Table 24: Project's planned interventions by type (hectares). Baseline and optimized scenario

Site	Fenced surface Baseline scenario –			Fenced surface Optimized scenario –			Non fenced surface
	Total fenced area	<i>of which buildings and roads</i>	<i>of which green buffers</i>	Total fenced area	<i>of which buildings and roads</i>	<i>of which green buffers</i>	Re-naturalization areas
PA	8.9	5.3	3.6	8.9	2.9	6.0	5
PB	5.3	3.2	2.1	4.9	2.2	2.7	0
PD	4.9	6.0	-1.150	4.5	3.7	0.8	0
PF	4.1	3.1	1.0	4.8	2.0	2.8	2.8
PG	10.1	5.7	4.4	10.1	4.1	6.0	0
PH	8.2	6.6	1.6	4.4	4.4	0.0	0
PJ	6.1	5.8	0.3	5.3	3.8	1.4	0
PL	5.6	4.2	1.4	4.9	2.6	2.3	0
Total	53.2	39.9	13.3	47.8	25.9	22.0	7.8

Source: Authors

As a consequence of the project's planned interventions, changes in land use will occur on the majority of the cadastral area reserved. The changes are reported in the Table 25 below.

Table 25: Areas (cadastral) affected by land use/destination change (hectares)

	Baseline scenario	Optimized scenario
Forest land → Constructed area	8.2	5.1
Agricultural land → Constructed area	31.7	20.8
Agricultural land cultivated → Meadow	5.1	10.1
Agricultural land → Tree plantation	7.7	15.2
Agricultural land → Wetland	7.8	7.8

Source: Authors

Any change in land use can potentially result in a variation in the value of the ecosystem services provided. The adopted approach focuses on the most significant impact in terms of hectares affected or the expected degree of variation of the ecosystem's service value.

Table 26: Quantified ecosystem's services loss by main type of ecosystem's services and land changes

	Provisioning services	Regulating and habitat services
Forest land → Constructed area	✓	✓
Agricultural land → Constructed area	✓	✓
Agricultural land cultivated → Meadow	✓	-
Agricultural land → Tree plantation	✓	(benefit)*
Agricultural land → Wetland	✓	(benefit)*

Source: Authors; Note: *see Section 5.5

➤ STEP 2 – Monetisation

The monetisation approach was differentiated for provisioning and regulating/habitat services. However, in both cases, reference values for ecosystem services were expressed in EUR2024/ha/year.

Two distinct valuation methods were applied because provisioning services and regulating/habitat services differ significantly in nature, data availability, and how they are typically valued.

Provisioning services involve tangible goods like food, fresh water, fuel, etc., which are traded in markets and have observable prices. Therefore, a market-based approach was appropriate, relying on direct data collected from field studies and economic assessments of actual production losses or harvesting potential, based on site-specific studies conducted within the project area.

In contrast, regulating and habitat services—such as climate regulation, carbon sequestration, and air quality—do not have a direct market price and are harder to quantify with local data. For these, a value transfer method was used, applying monetary values from similar ecosystems and geographical contexts found in existing literature. Specifically, the ESVD (Ecosystem Services Valuation Database) was used as the main source, as it compiles thousands of peer-reviewed ecosystem service valuations globally.

Using these two approaches ensures that each type of ecosystem service is valued in the most suitable and feasible way, based on its characteristics and the availability of reliable data.

Monetization of provisioning services

The value of ecosystem provisioning services reflects the value of products obtained from ecosystems, including food, fresh water, fuel, fibre, biochemicals, and genetic resources. A **market-based approach** has been followed to value provisioning services in the context of the FCC study, specifically:

- For **forest land provisioning services**, a baseline value of 294 EUR/ha/year was adopted. This is the average technical value determined based on the forest study⁵¹ conducted on the reserved project's area by external experts through sampling and field visits (the values range from a minimum of 11 EUR/ha/year and a maximum value of 632 EUR/ha/year in the analysed surface). This value accounts for the soil and the actualized harvesting potential, including the value of trees that have not yet reached maturity for use⁵².

⁵¹ The yearly metric was derived dividing the estimated average EUR/ha value found in the study by 30, assuming this is the lifespan needed for a full regeneration of forest.

⁵² Land acquisition costs (both for forest and agricultural land) are also included in CAPEX, thus generating a double counting issue. Still, we considered this double counting tolerable in the context of a conservative approach.

- For **agricultural land provisioning services**, a baseline value of 3,649 EUR/ha/year was adopted (the values range from a minimum of 1,515 EUR/ha/year and a maximum value of 9,082 EUR/ha/year in the analysed surface). This is the average value of agricultural loss estimated in the agricultural study, which was based on a direct investigation of the farming activities present in the area reserved for the project. This value accounts for the direct and indirect (supply chain) loss of agricultural production, including cereal production and other cultivations, forage, etc.

Monetization of regulating and habitat services

A **value transfer approach** was adopted for valuing habitat services by applying the monetary value of the ecosystem service estimated in another context to the FCC context. Despite being aware of all the limitations inherent to this approach, given the complexity of ecosystem services functioning and their subsequent valorisations, it was chosen for its feasibility among those indicated by international guidelines for ecosystem service valuation⁵³. Still, the monetization of services should be interpreted with prudence as demonstrated by the high variabilities of metrics from literature and case studies.

When performing benefit transfer, use can be made of repositories of existing valuations and studies as sources for the values to be transferred to the policy site(s). The source adopted to retrieve the necessary data to implement the value transfer approach was the ESVD database⁵⁴, which collects around ten thousand evaluations worldwide and across ecosystems based on a wide range of methodologies. This database is used by the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) for developing guidance on ecosystem service valuation, by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) in agricultural and environmental assessments, by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) for biodiversity assessments and by the European Commission to formulate environmental policies and regulations. To the best of our knowledge, this database is the most up-to-date and comprehensive sources of estimates of ecosystem service values, it is available on a downloadable Excel spreadsheet, and it is easily accessed and searched. The database provides values, expressed in a standard metric (int\$/ha/year), for each biome and ecosystem service. In practice, the pertinent biome (temperate forest, intensive land use/cropland, wetlands) and geographical area (Europe) were selected, and the values of relevant regulating and habitat services for which sufficient data was available (with a minimum threshold of at least 10 observations) were retrieved. Descriptive statistics included mean, median, min and max values. Median values were chosen as a reference⁵⁵.

- Regulating and supporting services of forest ecosystem (inc. Air quality regulation, climate regulation, and C-sequestration): 533 EUR/ha/year (min 20 EUR/ha/year, max 6,625 EUR/ha/year).
- Regulating and supporting services of agricultural land (inc. Air quality regulation, climate regulation, and C-sequestration): 574 EUR/ha/year (min 8 EUR/ha/year, max 4,854 EUR/ha/year).

⁵³ See for example Markandya, A. (2016) and USAID (2018). International guidelines suggest also other valorisation methods including primary study, modelling platform, and value transfer functions which we discarded because of their complexity and/or lack of data.

⁵⁴ This database (<https://www.esvd.net>) was initially developed for the TEEB - The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity in 2010.

⁵⁵ The values retrieved were expressed in int\$/year 2020. They were converted into EUR using PPP conversion factors (source: World Bank) and transformed in 2024 values by using GDP deflator (source: IMF).

Results

Table 27 below presents the total externality from ecosystem services loss due to the FCC project implementation. It was calculated by applying the estimated per hectare ecosystem provisioning and regulating/habitat services' loss to the impacted land area starting from the year the land-use change occurred (assumed to be one year ahead of the project's construction) and continuing until the end of the period. In the best-case scenario and worst-case scenario, the lower bound and higher bound values retrieved for monetization were respectively adopted.

Table 27: Total estimation - under different scenarios (CHF)

Scenario	Total discounted	Total undiscounted
Baseline	4,144,449	7,638,426
Best-case scenario	1,509,507	2,733,810
Worst case scenario	13,486,313	25,691,824

Source: Authors

3.2.6. Traffic-related externalities

Introduction

For the construction of the tunnel, approximately 8 million m³ of excavated material will need to be extracted and disposed of. While some of this material will be reused on-site, a portion will require transportation by truck to sorting facilities, quarries, and other destinations. The objective of this chapter is to estimate the externalities associated with pollution, GHG emissions, and congestion from the trucks used to transport the material.

Estimation

➤ STEP 1 – Quantifying the traffic-related externalities

The FCC study management provided⁵⁶ traffic estimates for trucks transporting excavated material. The document included an initial estimation of the quantity of excavated material and the different types of trucks used. Quantities were then adjusted to reflect the updated data used for the quantification of excavated materials management costs.

CERN outlined four transport alternatives:

- 4-axle trucks with a maximum cargo weight of 18 tonnes and a capacity of 12 m³.
- 5-axle trucks with a maximum cargo weight of 24 tonnes and a capacity of 17 m³.
- (3+2) axle trucks with a maximum cargo weight of 24 tonnes and a capacity of 24 m³.
- (2+3) axle trucks with a maximum cargo weight of 25 tonnes and a capacity of 24 m³.

Considering a weight of 2 tonnes per m³ of excavated soil, the maximum capacity for each type of truck can be calculated. This is necessary to determine the number of trucks needed to transport the material. According to the type of terrain (polluted, non-polluted, depolluted) and the country of destination, a specific distance is assigned.

⁵⁶ On December 5th, 2024.

The three scenarios have been constructed as follows:

- Worst-case scenario: In this scenario, French-polluted material is depolluted on-site, and trucks travel 65 km (round trip) to transport the material to quarries, while French-polluted material travels 35 km to quarries for disposal. Swiss material travels 70 km for type B material, 15 km for type E material, and 15 km for depolluted material.⁵⁷ 4-axle trucks are considered.
- Best-case scenario: French depolluted and non-polluted material travels 25 km to the nearest quarries. Swiss material is treated the same way as in the worst-case scenario.⁵⁸ (2+3)-axle trucks are considered.
- Baseline scenario: Similar to what is done for the management of excavation material cost, the baseline is an average of scenarios B and C. 5-axle trucks are considered.

Table 28: Km travelled by truck (one way) in the reference scenarios

Scenario	Material type	France	Switzerland
Worse case (i.e. Scenario B in the quantification of excavated materials management costs)	Polluted material	-	70 (type B ⁵⁹)
	Non-polluted material	35	15 (type E)
	Depolluted material	65	15 (type A)
Best-case (i.e. scenario C in the quantification of excavated materials management costs)	Polluted material	-	-
	Non-polluted material	25	70 (type B)
	Depolluted material	25	15 (type E)
			15 (type A)
			-

Source: CERN

An assessment of the congestion-related externalities was also attempted. Using CERN's data on daily traffic near the extraction points and assuming a road capacity of 15,000 vehicles per day (the capacity of a road with one lane in each direction), it is possible to roughly determine whether the additional trucks on the road result in an increase in the volume-to-capacity (v/c) ratio. The v/c ratio is a measure of road congestion, representing the ratio of the actual traffic volume to the maximum capacity of the road. Based on European Commission (2020a), four levels of congestion can be identified:

- A v/c ratio below 0.8 indicates no congestion
- A v/c ratio between 0.8 and 1 indicates a near-capacity road
- A v/c ratio between 1 and 1.2 indicates congestion
- A v/c ratio above 1.2 indicates overcapacity

Table 29 below shows the incremental number of vehicles caused by the transport of excavated material (using a passenger car equivalent of 2) compared to current traffic levels to identify changes in the v/c ratio. Examining the roads around the nine extraction sites (the eight sites and the injector), the additional trucks, in all scenarios,

⁵⁷ The material quantities and distances for this scenario equals those considered for scenario B in the quantification of excavated materials management costs (see box 2).

⁵⁸ The material quantities and distances for this scenario equals those considered for scenario C in the quantification of excavated materials management costs (see box 2).

⁵⁹ Categories A, B and E correspond to the type of landfill that can accept the material, with each category indicating the level of contamination, starting from A (the least polluted). For further details, refer to the Ordinance on the Avoidance and the Disposal of Waste, 4th December 2015 (Swiss Federal Office).

do not cause a significant increase in the v/c ratio that would change the traffic condition from one category to another. Therefore, based on the data available, no congestion effects are identified.

Table 29: Congestion state of roads around the extraction sites before and during construction

Scenario	PA	PB	PD	PF	PG	PH	PJ	PL	INJ.
Daily traffic before construction	7,803	5,918	20,475	11,331	13,681	1,709	13,954	3,380	7,803
v/c ratio before construction	0.52	0.39	1.37	0.76	0.91	0.11	0.93	0.23	0.52
Daily traffic during construction	8,342	5,976	20,973	11,396	14,215	1,831	14,458	3,474	7,851
v/c ratio during construction	0.56	0.40	1.40	0.76	0.95	0.12	0.96	0.23	0.52

Source: Authors

➤ STEP 2 – Monetisation

After determining the km*veh in each scenario and knowing the total weight of cargo per truck, the total cost of air pollution can be estimated using values from European Commission (2020a), expressed in €-cent per tkm, for each truck category.

The km*veh estimate also allows for the calculation of GHG emissions associated with the transport of excavated material. The emission values, expressed in €-cent per tkm, were also taken from European Commission (2020a) and followed the same assumptions used for air pollution.

Values are converted to CHF (2024) and discounted, given that they are distributed evenly for 8 years starting 2033, the beginning of construction.

Table 30: Unit cost of traffic pollution and GHG emissions (€-cent per t*km, 2016)

Scenario	Pollution	GHG emissions
4 axle truck	0.18	1.27
5 axle truck	0.09	0.75
3 + 2 axle	0.08	0.74
2 + 3 axle	0.08	0.7

Source: Authors based on European Commission (2020a)

A tonne-kilometre corresponds to the transport of one tonne of cargo over one kilometre. By multiplying the total kilometres travelled by trucks and the weight of cargo, the resulting tkm value allows for the monetisation of these traffic-related externalities.

Results

Table 31 below presents the results of the traffic-related externalities.

Table 31: Total estimation – Baseline Scenario (CHF, 2024)

	Total undiscounted	Total discounted
	<i>Baseline scenario</i>	
Pollution	1,175,942	834,336
GHG emissions	9,799,518	6,952,801
Total	10,975,461	7,787,137
	<i>Worst-case scenario</i>	
Pollution	2,778,669	1,971,478
GHG emissions	19,605,051	13,909,870
Total	22,383,720	15,881,348
	<i>Best-case scenario</i>	
Pollution	855,600	607,052
GHG emissions	7,914,301	5,615,231
Total	8,769,901	6,222,283

Source: Authors

3.3. TOTAL COSTS

The total project costs in the baseline scenario are illustrated the Table 32 below. The cost breakdown shows that investment costs and personnel costs represent the largest shares, amounting to 43% and 44% of the total costs, respectively. Other relevant cost categories include goods and services (5.7% of total costs), electricity (4.7% of total costs), and environmental costs (1.7%).

Table 32: Breakdown of FCC-ee total cost (Million, CHF)

	Not discounted	Discounted
Total investment costs (CAPEX)	16,215	10,171
Personnel	16,802	7,544
Electricity	1,812	764
Maintenance and repair	293	126
Good and services	2,189	940
Other operating expenditure	116	50
Decommissioning Costs	228	72
Environmental costs	653	354
Total costs	38,308	20,020

Source: Authors

Figure 17: Breakdown of FCC-ee total costs - Baseline Scenario.

Note: The breakdown is estimated by considering the total undiscounted costs by category over the entire FCC-ee time horizon. Other operating expenditure includes: Communication, meetings, events; Cryogenes and Water. Environmental costs include: GHG emissions, Radioactive emissions, Noise emissions, Productivity and ecosystem service loss, Traffic air pollution and Traffic GHG externalities.

Source: Authors

Figure 18: Time profile of FCC-ee total costs - Baseline Scenario (Million CHF, not discounted)

Source: Authors

4. MAIN SOCIO-ECONOMIC BENEFITS

4.1. THE VALUE OF SCIENTIFIC PRODUCTION

Definition of the benefit

This impact pathway explores what is probably the most immediate benefit that the FCC-ee project will deliver: scientific products. It follows the traditional idea of “knowledge push” where **research infrastructures generate scientific publications and similar products either directly or via their users. These are cited and eventually become part of a new body of knowledge** (see Catalano G. 2024, Griniece et al. 2020, Florio and Sirtori 2016). That body of knowledge later finds conscious or unconscious recognition within a broader research community and society. Final recipients of the knowledge generated may further translate it into economic benefits or apply it to societal problem-solving efforts.

While the objective of FCC-ee is advancing knowledge about the fundamentals of the Universe, this impact pathway does not measure the overall social value of the *knowledge* produced in terms of potential future practical use. As discussed in Section 2.1, estimating the full value of knowledge creation relating to fundamental scientific research ex-ante is not possible, since societal applications and the times when such knowledge applications occur cannot be foreseen. Discoveries can by definition not be programmed and by which ways and by-ways they affect society cannot be forecasted.

Instead, in the context of this study, the estimation focused on the first stages of the “knowledge push” impacts, i.e., the value of the *scientific products* produced by scientists for further use in research based on actual observations of this process in past and ongoing fundamental science projects. This impact pathway views scientists, engineers and researchers as “producers” and “consumers” of scientific products that the FCC-ee research programme is likely to generate. While acknowledging that this proxy is imperfect, the approach is largely consolidated in the literature (Martin, 1996; JASPERS, 2015; Carrazza et al., 2016; Florio 2019, Florio and Sirtori, 2016; Florio et al., 2016).

Approach

Scientometrics (Leydesdorff, 2001) is the main tool for carrying out statistical analysis of scientific products. Scientometric techniques offer a way to directly measure scientific activity and knowledge creation through the analysis and estimate of scientific production and propagation.

The approach to estimating the benefits of the scientific products of the FCC-ee relies on the analysis of patterns observed for comparable past research programs in particle and high-energy physics, including Tevatron, LEP and LHC. This approach also builds upon the model developed for the 2013 social cost-benefit analysis of the LHC, ensuring continuity in the analysis, while introducing major improvements. The steps of the approach and the key assumptions and parameters used are outlined in Table 33. They are detailed in the next section.

We considered as scientific products **any kind of citable product directly produced by the FCC-ee scientific community and cited by the research community.**

Scientific products considered in the analysis are therefore not limited to articles published in peer-reviewed journals, but they include a diversity of outputs, such as:

- Articles in peer-reviewed scientific journals,
- Working papers, non-peer-reviewed articles (e.g. made available on the CERN Document Server, Zenodo, ArXiv and dedicated open access libraries),
- Preprints (e.g. published on ArXiv and Zenodo),
- Conference proceedings,
- Conference and workshop presentations and posters,

- Scientific and technical books,
- Chapters in edited scientific and technical books.

For long-running research programmes, such as the FCC-ee, it is important to understand at which step of the research activity the scientific products are generated. We consider three distinct tiers for the analysis:

- Tier 0 scientific products (P0): they are produced by scientists, engineers and other researchers who actively participate in the research programme. They serve as “corpus” for the creation of further knowledge and science products. These products capture the knowledge acquired during the design, construction and operation phases of the FCC-ee.
- Tier 1 science products (P1): they cite P0 products.
- Tier 2 science products (P2): they cite P1 products.

In principle, further tiers of science products could be identified and considered. For this analysis, we included only the first two streams of citations (P1 and P2), since the value decreases because of dilution in the overall past knowledge from one tier to the next and therefore further tiers are only minor contributions to the total value.

Following existing literature (Florio and Sirtori, 2016; European Commission, 2014) and in line with the approach applied in the socio-economic analysis of the LHC and HL-LHC (Florio et al., 2016; Bastianin and Florio, 2018), the preferred option for the quantitative estimation of the value of scientific products is based on their so-called "marginal production cost". This approach relies on the economic concepts of "opportunity cost" and "value of time".

The decision of a scientist to spend time writing an article, downloading, reading and citing someone else's production requires the use of his/her time in this activity and represents a "lost opportunity" to use that time for the next best professional activity, such as for instance carrying out further scientific research or teaching. **The value of a scientific product can be proxied by multiplying the estimated time spent by the persons involved in the production by their average hourly salaries.** This approach is necessary due to the lack of undistorted market prices for scientific products. The subscription fees of journals and the price paid by researchers for making available an article in Open Access form do not provide a suitable indication of the underlying socio-economic value of scientific products, since they involve market mechanisms and revenue-generating activities that are not related to the scientific product and knowledge generation.

For each considered publication tier (P0, P1, P2), the value of knowledge is made of two components: the social value of producing new information *per se* plus a social value attributed to the degree of influence of that piece of knowledge on the scientific community. The social value is captured by the number of scientific productions and valued through the marginal production cost for each tier (P0, P1, P2). The influence is reflected by the number of people that consume the scientific product reflected by the number of citations, as illustrated in Figure 19. Using citations as a measure of the significance of a scientific product is an imperfect but widely accepted approach to capture the social recognition and esteem that the scientific community acknowledges to the paper (Hagström, 1965; de Solla Price, 1970). It is, therefore, reasonable to attribute a higher social value to a product that is cited more often compared to another product in the same field.

Figure 19: Illustration of the scientific products in three tiers (P0, P1, P2) and their citations (Q0, Q1, Q2) considered in the analysis based on a multi-level citation analysis.

Source: Authors

Table 33: Steps and main parameters to calculate the value of scientific production.

Step	Action	Data considered for the analysis
1	Retrieve historical data on scientific products	LHC-related scientific retrieved by Giffoni, F., Sirtori, E., & Colnot, L. (2024) from the INSPIRE HEP database Period: 1990-2021
2	Estimate the number of scientific productions by scientists and engineers working on the FCC-ee (P0)	Production over time estimated by considering the distribution of the LEP and tevatron-associated publications and the scale of the LHC. P0 = 38,008 (2024-2083)
3	Estimate the number of scientific products citing P0 products (P1, P2) and the number of citations (Q0, Q1)	Based on LHC historical data: P1/P0 = 1.3 P2/P0 = 3.7 Q0/P0 = 6.3 Q1/P0 = 19.1 Share of P1 citing highly influential P0: 7%
4	Estimate the value of scientific products	Average annual gross salary of authors (weighted between scientists and post-docs): 58,615 CHF Fraction of time dedicated per author to perform research and produce scientific outputs: 55% (applied to scientists only) Fraction of time dedicated per author to FCC-ee-related products: 22% (applied to scientists only) Average unit production value of each P0: 126,279 CHF Number of references in P1 and P2: 50 Average contribution given by a highly influential P0 to the production of P1: 33% Working days per year: 250 ⁶⁰ Working hours per day: 6.4 Working hours per year: 1,600 Average hourly gross salary: 37 CHF Hours for one citation: 3 Value of one citation (Q0 and Q1): 110 CHF.
5	Estimate the total benefit and application of the net present value formula	Social discount rate applied: 2.8% (see section 2.3.3).

Source: Authors

Estimation

➤ STEP 1 - Retrieve historical data on scientific products

The distribution of publications over time and citation patterns varies largely from one discipline to another (Glänzel and Schubert, 2004). For this reason, data for the estimation of the FCC-ee were based on historical data from similar high-energy physics projects and the respective experiment collaborations linked to these research programmes. Therefore, the data used to estimate the FCC-ee were derived from historical records of similar high-energy physics projects and their associated experimental collaborations. Specifically, since the FCC-ee includes four experiments, the LHC experiment was deemed the most relevant for comparison.

⁶⁰ Source: Eurostat. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cros/content/euro-area-and-eu-working-days-build-calendar-adjustment-regressor_en.

Historical data on LHC scientific products over the period 1990-2021⁶¹ were retrieved by Giffoni, F., Sirtori, E., & Colnot, L. (2024) by using the INSPIRE HEP database.⁶² The data extraction process identified 54,384 individual authors associated with the LHC, who collectively authored 434,065 unique scientific products. Of these, **8% (n = 34,558) were LHC-related scientific products**, while the remaining 92% (n = 399,507) were non-LHC-related products. These non-LHC-related products included outputs from other CERN collaborations/experiments as well as non-CERN-related scientific work. The LHC-related scientific products came from the major LHC experiments such as ALICE, ATLAS, CMS, and LHCb, but smaller experiments and collaborations were also included in the data retrieval process (see Table 34 below).

Table 34: Experiments and collaborations considered for P0 retrieval process

Collaborations	Experiments
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ALICE • ATLAS • CMS • FASER • LARP • LHCb • LHCf • MATHUSLA • milliQan • MoEDAL • RD12 • RD2 • RD23 • RD42 • RD5 • RD8 • SND@LHC • TOTEM • USCMS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AcerMC • CERN-H4IRRAD • CERN-HL-LHC • CERN-LHC • CERN-LHC-ALICE • CERN-LHC-ATLAS • CERN-LHC-CMS • CERN-LHC-FASER • CERN-LHC-FELIX • CERN-LHC-FP420 • CERN-LHC-HV-QF • CERN-LHC-LHCb • CERN-LHC-LHCf • CERN-LHC-MOEDAL • CERN-LHC-TOTEM • CERN-RD-002 • CERN-RD-005 • CERN-RD-008 • CERN-RD-012 • CERN-RD-013 • CERN-RD-018 • CERN-RD-023 • CERN-RD-027 • CERN-RD-042 • CERN-RD-049 • FNAL-E-0892 • FNAL-E-0893 • LARP • MATHUSLA • milliQan • SND@LHC

Source: Giffoni, F., Sirtori, E., & Colnot, L. (2024)

Figure 20 below shows the scientific production observed between 1990-2021 by distinguishing between LHC-related (blue line) and non-LHC-related products (red line). Scientific output steadily increased from 7,355 products in 1990 to an average of 17,168 products per year from 2008 to 2021. LHC-related production followed

⁶¹ The analysis timeframe aligns with key LHC milestones. Though construction was approved in 1993 and operations began in 2008, significant scientific output on its development started in the early 1990s, warranting its inclusion. The endpoint, 2021, reflects the latest available data from the INSPIRE API at the time of extraction (see Appendix A.2 of Giffoni, F., Sirtori, E., & Colnot, L. 2024). Six LHC-related papers from 1983–1989 were excluded.

⁶²INSPIRE HEP is the leading platform for scientific content in HEP as it aggregates content from multiple authoritative sources in this field, including ArXiv, CERN, DESY and a wide range of scientific publishers (e.g., Elsevier, Springer)See <https://help.inspirehep.net/knowledge-base/inspire-content-sources/>

the LHC’s milestones, peaking in 2012 (2,366 products) after the Higgs boson discovery and in 2016 (2,343 products) marking the start of the second operating phase.

Figure 20: Total scientific production, LHC- and non-LHC-related scientific production (1990-2021).

Source: Giffoni, F., Sirtori, E., & Colnot, L. (2024)

All types of scientific products were considered, including peer-reviewed articles, pre-prints, conference proceedings, theses, books, chapters, and reports. Articles and pre-prints make up 54.3% of the total sample but only 16.3% of LHC-related outputs. In high-energy physics, it is common to present original research through conference proceedings, explaining their high share (56.7%) among LHC-related products. Books, chapters, theses, notes, and reports represent a smaller portion in both the overall and LHC-related samples.

Figure 21: Scientific products by type (1990 – 2021)

Source: Giffoni, F., Sirtori, E., & Colnot, L. (2024)

➤ **STEP 2 - Estimating the number of FCC-ee related scientific products (P0)**

We estimated the number of FCC-ee related scientific products generated over time based on the following assumptions:

- The scale and the distribution by type (peer-reviewed paper, magazine article, conference proceeding, etc.) of P0 products was based on the LHC historical data from 1990-2021, as reported by Giffoni, F., Sirtori, E., & Colnot, L. (2024). The data show a growing trend in the number of new scientific publications. The reason is the increasingly faster, easier, and more direct process from research findings to publication.
- The shape of scientific production was based on the LEP trend or Tevatron ones, because of the similarity in the physics programmes: the FCC-ee experiments will provide more and more precise measures of phenomena that will certainly be observed. This is a substantial difference from the LHC discovery-based research programme. For FCC-ee, we can therefore expect a long period of scientific production with small peaks after the FCC-ee enters a new operation phase (W, Z, ZH, ttbar) due to the expected publications based on the newly available precision data.

Figure 22 below shows the estimated distribution of FCC-ee scientific products (P0) over time. The timeline covers the entire time horizon of FCC-ee and beyond (until 2083), since data analysis will continue for some time after the FCC-ee ends of operations. The production curve declines though quickly after the end of operation, following the trend of the previously observed pattern at the LEP. **A total number of 34,397 P0 scientific products is estimated to be generated during the period 2024-2064, and an additional 3,611 science products are expected after 2064.**

We need to emphasize that the figure above represents the total number of expected FCC-ee-related products, not the total number of publications by researchers involved in the collaborations and accelerators. These researchers will produce many other papers throughout their careers as part of other projects.

Figure 22: Expected distribution of FCC-ee P0 scientific products over time

Source: Authors

➤ **STEP 3 - Estimating the number of citations to P0 (P1) and to P1 (P2)**

We estimated the number of P1 and P2 products that can be attributed to the FCC-ee P0 products and the number of citations that P0 and P1 products receive (Q0 and Q1) by assuming the same ratios observed for the LHC. More specifically:

- The number of P1 and P2 products over time is estimated using the yearly trend of P1/P0 and P2/P0 ratios from the LHC program. On average, each P0 product generates 1.3 P1 products over the entire construction and operation period—0.6 during construction and 2.3 during operation. Similarly, each P0 product generates an average of 3.7 P2 products, with 1.5 occurring during the construction phase and 6.0 during the operation phase.
- Similarly, each P0 is expected to receive an average of 6.3 citations (Q0/P0), with a lower average of 1.3 during the construction phase and a higher average of 11.6 during the operation phase. In turn, P1 papers generated by a single P0 receive an average of 19 citations, with the highest levels occurring during the construction phase.

Table 35: Parameters for the estimation of citing papers (average values)

Ratios of products and citations	Construction 1993-2007	Operation 2008-2021	Average for the period 1993-2021
P1/P0	0.6	2.0	1.3
P2/P0	1.5	6.0	3.7
Q0/P0	1.3	11.6	6.3
Q1/P0	2.8	36.5	19.1

Note: Historical data from 1993 to 2021 were considered. **Source:** Authors

We have refined the estimation of P1 products by highlighting the share that cited highly influential P0, i.e. papers that contributed to a higher degree to the content of P1 products. To do so, we followed the approach introduced by Springer in 2015 (Valenzuela-Escarcega et al. 2015) to identify the most influential citations. This analysis is based on the citations count and on the content of the papers (e.g., locations of citations in the structure of the papers). By considering data for all considered research programmes (LHC, Tevatron and LEP), we estimated that **7% of P1 papers cited highly influential P0**.

Table 36: Total number of FCC-ee scientific products

Scientific product tiers	Total 2024-2064	Total 2024-2083
P0	34,397	38,008
P1	80,189	91,343
P2	457,978	526,782
Q0 (number of times P0 are cited by P1)	387,964	453,323
Q1 (number of times P1 are cited by P2)	2,318,087	2,03,048

Source: Authors

Figure 23: Expected distribution of FCC-ee scientific products over time – P0, P1, P2 (2024-2083)

Source: Authors

➤ **STEP 4 - Computing the unit value of P0 scientific products**

In line with existing literature (see for instance European Commission 2014 and 2021) and the approach applied in the socio-economic analysis of the LHC and HL-LHC (Florio, Forte, Sirtori 2016 and Bastianin and Florio 2018), the quantitative estimation of the value of scientific products is based on the Marginal Cost of Production (MCP). This approach is grounded in the economic concepts of "opportunity cost" and the "value of time." When a scientist chooses to dedicate time to activities such as writing an article, downloading, reading, or citing someone else's work, it involves a "lost opportunity" to allocate that time to the next best professional activity, such as conducting additional research or teaching. As a result, the (minimum) value of a scientific product can be approximated by multiplying the estimated time spent by individuals involved in its production by their average hourly salaries. This does not include the future value of utility for society of knowledge per se as embodied in a publication, because this is ex-ante unknown.

For each considered publication tier (P0, P1, P2), the value is made of two components: the social value of producing new information *per se* plus a social value attributed to the degree of influence of that piece of knowledge on the scientific community. The social value is captured by the number of scientific productions and valued through the marginal production cost for each tier (P0, P1, P2). The influence is reflected by the number of people that use the scientific product reflected by the number of citations. Using citations as a measure of the significance of a scientific product is an imperfect but widely accepted approach to capture the social recognition and esteem that the scientific community acknowledges in the paper.

For this estimation, we relied on the MCP model suggested by Giffoni, F., Sirtori, E., & Colnot, L. (2024), which considers the number of authors of each paper and the productivity of each of the contributing authors in the calculation. The formula used to calculate the unit cost of production is detailed in Box 3 below.

Box 3: The marginal cost of production model

$$MPC_{f,t} = MPC_{res_{f,t}}^c + MPC_{pub_t} = \left(\frac{w_{res_{j,f,t}} * h_{res_{j,f,t}}}{y_{res_{j,f,t}}(n_t)} \right) * n_t + MPC_{pub_t}$$

Where

$MPC_{f,t}$ is the average marginal cost of producing a generic scientific publication in the scientific field f at time t .

$MPC_{res_{f,t}}^c$ is the average marginal cost of doing research in that field.

$w_{res_{j,f,t}}$ denotes the average annual salary of the j -th author(s) doing research with $j = 1, \dots, n, \dots, N$; $h_{res_{j,f,t}}$ denotes their average share of working time dedicated to research and it ranges from 0 to 100%.

$y_{res}(j,f,t)(n_t)$ measures the author productivity in the period t , measured as the number of scientific products she produces in that period. The functional form of this parameter may vary by scientific fields, time period, and other factors, as collaboration practices differ across disciplines and evolve over time

MPC_{pub_t} reflects other publication production costs.

In this model, the author(s)' productivity is a monotonically increasing function of the (average) number of co-authors (n_t). The number of authors per paper is then used as a scaling factor for the term $MPC_{res_{f,t}}^c$ to incorporate co-authorship into the equation. The interpretation of $MPC_{res_{f,t}}^c$ is this: given the share of time allocated to research ($h_{res_{j,f,t}}$), co-authorship reduces each author's individual contribution to a paper but it increases productivity, allowing for more articles to be signed in a given period. The term in brackets $\left(\frac{w_{res_{j,f,t}} * h_{res_{j,f,t}}}{y_{res_{j,f,t}}(n_t)} \right)$ represents single-author publications and, therefore, requires adjustment for the number of co-authors. The functional form of $y_{res_{j,f,t}}(n_t)$ is unknown a priori and may vary by scientific fields, time period, and other factors, as collaboration practices differ across disciplines and evolve over time.

Source: Authors based on Giffoni, F., Sirtori, E., & Colnot, L. (2024)

The application of the formula described above required the following ingredients:

- The **average annual gross salary** of personnel expected to produce P0 Products: Based on evidence from interviews, it was assumed that mainly Scientists and Postdoctoral Researchers—working on both accelerators and infrastructures as well as experiments—contribute to authoring scientific publications. Using this assumption, we calculated a weighted average annual gross salary for these two categories of personnel only, distinguishing between those affiliated/managed by CERN and those affiliated/managed by other institutions. For scientists involved in experiments, assumptions were made regarding their salaries to account for the time they allocate to research activities and specifically to FCC-ee-related work (see details in the point below).

Table 37: Estimation of the average annual gross salary of P0 authors

Personnel working on accelerator and infrastructure and experiments	Total number	% managed by CERN	% managed other institutions	Gross annual salary CERN (100% FCC)	Gross annual salary Other institutions (FCC share of time only)	Weighted average salary (CHF, 2024, undiscounted)
Scientists	37,103	14%	86%	211,915	20,513*	58,615
Post docs	68,143	15%	85%	84,318	67,454	

Note: *The average salary for scientists managed by other institutions is estimated to be CHF 169 532. Based on the assumption that this group spends only 55% of their time on research activities and, within that, dedicates an average of 22% of their research time to FCC-ee, the yearly salary share was 12% ($0.55 \cdot 0.22$).

Source: Authors.

- Time dedicated to research and FCC-ee:** Among the categories assumed to contribute to signing papers, we considered that scientists and post-doctoral researchers working on the accelerators dedicate 100% of their time to research and to the FCC-ee project. Similarly, post-doctoral researchers working on the experiments also spend 100% of their time on research activities. For scientists working on experiments and managed by other institutions, however, evidence from interviews confirmed that they allocate only a portion of their time to a specific research project, hence to FCC-ee-related work. In line with Nature's 2016 Jobs Survey, we assumed that the average academic researcher spends approximately 55% of his/her time conducting scientific research and writing articles, while the remaining time is allocated to administrative tasks, teaching, data storage, and writing grant applications. Consistent with these findings, we assumed that 55% of the FCC-ee project's scientific personnel time is dedicated to scientific research and the development of scientific products. Additionally, it was assumed that only a portion of their research time is dedicated to FCC-ee-related products. Based on Giffoni, F., Sirtori, E., & Colnot, L. (2024), this was estimated to be an average of 22% over the considered time horizon. As a result, only a share of the salary rate was applied to this category. These assumptions ensure that the estimations of personnel costs (see Section 3.1.3) and their contributions to generating benefits are mutually consistent.
- The average marginal cost of publishing:** this parameter was set at EUR 311 PPS in line with Giffoni, F., Sirtori, E., & Colnot, L. (2024).
- The productivity function $y_{res_t}(n_t)$:** according to Giffoni, F., Sirtori, E., & Colnot, L. (2024) productivity range per author is a relatively small number of papers signed per year (often 6 or lower) for papers with few authors, but it dramatically increases over time and with the number of authors (up to 30-60) signed paper per year.
- Number of authors:** we analyzed the distribution of authors for the 34,397 LHC-related P0 products published between 1990 and 2021, excluding rare outliers such as papers with more than 3,000 authors. The analysis revealed that 91% of the papers—31,150 in total—were authored by 1 to 100 authors, while 9% - 3,247 papers - were authored by more than 100 authors. Among the latter, some papers had author counts up to 3000 and beyond. For scientific products with a very high number of co-authors, the marginal cost of production method may not always provide an accurate economic valuation. This is because author signatures do not necessarily indicate that all co-authors allocated time to the paper. The empirical approach presented here is grounded in a comprehensive analysis including interviews with CERN scientists, a review of collaboration signature policies⁶³, and an examination of publication and co-authorship data. This body of evidence led us to conclude that, in the specific case of HEP

⁶³ For instance CERN (2024) Template for writing LHCb papers; CDS submission procedures available at <https://ep-dep.web.cern.ch/content/submission-procedure>, Gambetta, S., et al (2022).

collaborations, the number of listed authors on a given paper is not usually a reliable indicator of the actual individual effort invested in its production⁶⁴. In fact, as confirmed by interviews, the number of scientists actually drafting those papers remains often limited to 20-25 as a maximum, the remaining being members of the collaboration whose contribution is different, such as control of data-taking or review activities rather than scientific output production. The magnitude and value of these (more indirect) contribution to individual scientific products can be hard to establish and would require ad hoc methodologies and empirical analysis. However, given the assumption that 100% of post-doc time is directly devoted to FCC research (which is probably an overestimation), these 'background' activities are already taken into account.

- **Valuation rule:** Given the above-mentioned uncertainty about the actual contributions of authors for 'large size' papers, a simple shortcut rule is needed:
 - For papers with 1 to 100 authors (10% in the empirical distribution) we assume that all contributors fully participated in the production of the scientific output, each contributing her/his time proportionally, based on their estimated productivity. Hence, for example, if the 100th author is a post-doc who signs 6 papers per year, his contribution to such paper is 1/6 of her/his yearly gross salary. If the author is a scientist with the same productivity, it would on average be 1/6 of 12% of her/his gross salary (with a range going from 100% to zero). The above mentioned productivity function will give the individual contribution.
 - For papers with more than 100 authors, whatever the total number of authors (usually reflecting the size of the collaborations or sub-sets of them), we cap the value to 100 actual contributing authors, with a time effort and value proportional to the corresponding productivity, as above. This is an upper bound for the number of actual contributing authors in terms of dedicated time and is a way to give the same value to the internal review process and additional activities beyond mere drafting within the collaborations.
 - At a later stage, uncertainty on the capping threshold can be dealt with Montecarlo simulations (e.g. with a cap at 25, suggested by some interviewed scientists, or using a percentage of the authors).

Based on the above parameters and applying the MCP formula suggested by Giffoni, F., Sirtori, E., & Colnot, L. (2024), we calculated an average unit production cost equal to 126,279 CHF for the period 2024-2083, with wide variance below and over the threshold of actual authors. Therefore, this average should be interpreted primarily as a summary statistic, rather than a precise figure. Of the 34,397 publications considered, 90.6% are contributed by fewer than 100 authors. More notably, 80.2% of these publications (27,597) are contributed by an even smaller group of authors – fewer than 8 authors (see Figure 24 below). The median value of the production costs associated to these publications - contributed by 1 to 8 authors - is approximately 18,700 CHF, a value consistent with many other scientific fields. This significant difference between the mean and the median reflects a strongly skewed distribution of production costs across publications. A small number of publications involving very large author teams drive up the average cost considerably. These high-cost outliers heavily influence the mean, while the median remains unaffected by extreme values and more accurately reflects the typical cost for the vast majority of publications. In this case, since over 80% of the publications are produced by small teams (fewer than 8 authors), the median value of CHF 18,700 offers a more representative benchmark for the "typical" publication, whereas the mean is inflated by a relatively small number of high-cost, large-team publications.

⁶⁴ For instance, some collaboration papers are formally authored by a single individual "on behalf of" the entire collaboration. From a purely scientometric standpoint, these papers are counted as single-author works, whereas others, which list all 2,000+ contributors, are classified as multi-author publications. However, these papers are often quite similar in the way they are produced, with the primary difference being the internal authorship policies applied in each case.

Figure 24: Number and share of publications by number of authors

Source: Authors based on Giffoni, F., Sirtori, E., & Colnot, L. (2024)

➤ **STEP 5 - Computing the unit value of P1 and P2 scientific products**

The value of P1 and P2 products differs from the value of P0. According to historical data based on LHC scientific production, **the average number of citations contained in P1 and P2 products is 50**. It means that 2% of the unit value of a scientific product (1/50) can be attributed to the P1 products. Nevertheless, some P0 products may provide a highly significant contribution to P1. For those highly influential P0, we assumed that up to one-third (such as 33%) of the value contained in the P1 product was influenced by the P0 product.

The value of P2 products was estimated in a similar way. It is the total marginal cost of P1 paper production divided by the number of references that the paper contains. Its value is lower than P1 products because the initial input given by the P0 product is diluted at each new wave of knowledge production.

Similarly to P0, also the unit production cost of P1 and P2 products change over time.

Finally, the value of a citation (Q0 and Q1) was estimated by assuming an average of 3 hours necessary to produce the citation, i.e. reading the original paper, understanding it, and deciding how to cite it in the new paper. With an average annual salary of 58,615 CHF and assuming a total of 1,600 working hours per year, the value of a citation amounts to 110 CHF.

➤ **STEP 6 - Estimating the value of scientific production**

The total value of scientific production is estimated by adding the number of P0, P1, P2 scientific products and the Q0 and Q1 citations and their respective unit values. The total undiscounted benefit of all estimated FCC-ee scientific products amounts to 6.5 CHF billion in the baseline scenario, which represents **2.8 CHF billion** after applying the social discount rate of 2.8%. As the table below shows, the largest share of the benefit (nearly 90%) is represented by the value of P0 scientific products generated by the scientists, engineers, and researchers directly involved in the FCC-ee project from its design phase until the end of operation and for some time beyond that.

The value of P1 scientific products and the streams of citations they receive (Q1) accounts for 9% of the total socio-economic value represented by scientific products. The more distant we go from the original scientific production, the lower the socio-economic value that we can causally attribute to the P0 products.

Table 38: Total estimated of FCC-ee scientific production value – Baseline Scenario (CHF).

Scientific production	Not discounted	Discounted	Share of the benefit over the total (discounted)
P0 scientific products	5,838,648,557	2,546,095,933	90.4%
P1 scientific products	289,192,546	117,505,042	4.2%
P2 scientific products	31,870,943	12,415,966	0.4%
(Q0) P1 citations	57,894,594	23,551,816	0.8%
(Q1) P2 citations	297,071,288	117,166,887	4.2%
Total	6,514,677,928	2,816,735,643	100.0%

Source: Authors

Figure 25: Time profile of FCC-ee scientific production value – Baseline scenario (CHF, not discounted)

Source: Authors

4.2. THE VALUE OF EARLY CAREER RESEARCHER TRAINING

Definition of the benefit

This impact pathway explores the benefit of human capital formation. Training new generations of scientists and engineers has in the past been identified as one of the main benefits of the LHC research programme. It accounted for around one third of the total socio-economic benefits of the LHC (Florio et al, 2016). The FCC-ee is expected to build human capital by improving the skills and career development of people working on the project that is unique and which therefore represents an opportunity for early-stage researchers and engineers that cannot be easily identified elsewhere. Past studies have shown that this impact pathway mainly works by developing new skills and increased labour productivity.

People are key for the development and operation of the research infrastructure. They perform data analysis, design and construct the experiments, develop software, produce scientific and technical publications, test and qualify equipment and develop tools and methods for this purpose, perform laboratory, identify issues, develop solution strategies and approaches, maintain and repair the scientific instruments and gradually improve its performance throughout its entire lifecycle. During their work period in the project, these people gain diverse technical skills, increase their problem-solving capacity, learn teamwork, acquire management and communication capabilities, acquire social capital thanks to the access to a wide network of contacts in the scientific community and benefit from reputational effects thanks to their direct participation in the activities of

a highly recognised research centre. These effects, in turn, lead to better job opportunities and a “premium” on their future salaries. This premium reflects the so-called **“marginal⁶⁵” salary increase, gained by an early-stage researcher or engineer who works for a limited period of time at the FCC-ee, compared to a salary which would be earned without that specific work experience.**

Several investigations provide evidence of the existence of this benefit (Bianchin et al., 2019; Catalano et al., 2018; Camporesi, 2001). For the LHC programme, the estimated **premium ranges between 5% and 12% of the average salary**, depending on the future professional sector, type of tasks carried out and skills acquired (Catalano et al., 2021; Camporesi et al., 2017).

In addition to on-the-job training, there exist other **activities fostering education and training of future researchers** at CERN. They include, for instance, the apprenticeship programmes for Swiss high-school students, the national and international teacher programmes carried⁶⁶ (11,414 teachers in 19 years, 600-900 teachers per year in all programmes, order of 50 teachers per year participate in an international two-week residential programme⁶⁷ and in 4-6 days lasting national programmes), high-school student master classes for about 13,000 high school students organised by the experiments in ten years (~ 1,300 pupils per year for 1-2 days per class)⁶⁸, offering professional development programmes for teachers to keep up-to-date with the latest development in particle physics and related areas, and other specific training activities existing today and potentially developed for FCC-ee. Moreover, as it was the case with LEP and LHC physics knowledge gain, the results of scientific research carried out at the FCC-ee could eventually feed into the syllabus and teaching materials of university and high-school education programmes and contribute to improving the understanding about the universe inner working and the origin of humankind of the future generations of students and, perhaps, scientists. All these benefits are part of the general impact pathway related to education and training, but their economic valuation requires different specific methodologies and data. None of these additional training pathways has been considered in this socio-economic impact analysis. Dedicated methodological investigations over a multi-year time frame under controlled conditions would be required to reliably elucidate their effects on the economy and the society.

This impact pathway focuses therefore on analysing the training and education effects of on-the-job training carried out during the FCC-ee lifetime for students and early-stage researchers. **Economic quantification of the benefits focused on the human capital effects for people who typically spend a work period between 1 and 5 years in the FCC-ee project**, based on observation evidence in the LHC programme. Methodologies previously developed and tested in the context of other research infrastructures were used for this analysis to assure a consistent and reliable approach.

Approach

A research infrastructure typically employs **four main groups of people** under a variety of contractual conditions:

- 1) **scientists and engineers** (including post-doctoral researchers),
- 2) **technical** personnel,
- 3) **administrative** and support personnel and
- 4) **students** at different education levels including trainees.

The **focus** of our analysis in this project was **on early-career researchers** (apprentices, trainees, technical students, doctoral students, post-doctoral researchers, associated members of personnel up to a cut-off age).

⁶⁵ In economics, the term “marginal” refers to the value change if the observed quantity is incremented by one unit.

⁶⁶ For statistics and materials see <https://indico.cern.ch/category/5886/>.

⁶⁷ <https://home.cern/news/news/knowledge-sharing/cerns-international-high-school-teacher-programme-turns-20>.

⁶⁸ International master classes, <https://physicsmasterclasses.org>.

- Six steps were followed to estimate the value of training (see Table 39). The assumptions for the calculation of the key parameters are based on previous existing studies, cross-checked and validated by the results of an online survey targeted to former and current researchers carried out by CERN between June 2020 and September 2022. Approximately 2,600 individuals were reached by the survey out of which 710 valid answers were analysed (27%)⁶⁹. This new survey analysed three types of information after anonymisation:
- **Personal information and education background:** Nationality and residence, gender, date of birth, marital status, type and level of formal education, type and number of courses beyond formal education, for PhDs only the name of university and department.
- **Current job:** Current occupational status, number of years in the labour market, type or organisation, sector, size of the firm, number of weekly working hours, yearly gross salary, type of contract, extra benefits, other income generating activity beyond primary occupation.
- **Experience at CERN and impact on career:** Start and (expected) end date at CERN, domain of activity, considerations on the importance of applying for a period at CERN, share of working time at CERN spent on different activities, skills improvement, publications.

Table 39: Steps and main parameters to calculate the value of training impact.

Step	Description	Key Parameter
1	Estimate the number of people per year who will benefit from the salary premium as a percentage of the total number of people involved in the FCC-ee programme	Share of people with salary premium based on: Younger than 30 years when leaving the project Staying in the project between 1 and 5 years, on average 3.78 years.
2	Determine the professional sector in which people will likely work after the project experience.	The following distribution is used: Academia and research (36%) Industry and finance (45%) Public administration, incl. Non-profit (19%)
3	Estimate the duration of the total active working life.	Average total active life is assumed to be 37.5 years, with the following probability distribution: 37 years (46%) 38 years (21%) 39 years (21%) 40 years (11%)
4	Define the lifetime salary evolution for each different professional sector	Logarithmic salary evolution functions depending on the year of experience in the labour market (X): Academia and research: $Y=34920+27133*\ln(X)$; Industry and finance: $Y=33335+34542*\ln(X)$; Public administration and non-profit: $Y=33099+37739*\ln(X)$
5	Estimate the average salary premium	Average salary premium per year: 3% (minimum 2% to a maximum of 4%); Average salary premium for the average period of 3.78 years in the project: 6% (minimum of 2%, maximum of 10%)
6	Estimate the total benefit and application of the net present value formula	Social discount rate applied is 2.8% (see section 2.3.3).

Source: Authors

⁶⁹ The dissemination strategy included direct emails, posting of 14 notices on Facebook Group Young@CERN, with 16100 users in October 2022, and 7 posts on Alumni CERN, with 8363 users in October 2022. To compute the response rate, only the direct mailing activity has been considered.

Estimation

➤ STEP 1 - Estimating the number of beneficiaries

The first step consisted in estimating the number of people per year who are likely to benefit from the salary premium until the end of the FCC-ee operation phase. This number is a fraction of the number of people reported in Section 3.1. For this study, we considered that **only students and early-career researchers, including post-doctoral employees, are beneficiaries of a salary premium, since so far, no particular studies for other professional groups have been carried out.** It is understood that this leads to an underestimate of the impact. Two criteria were considered to determine the fraction of people who benefit from a lifetime salary premium:

- **People younger than 30 years.** The economic literature on human capital accumulation (Psacharopoulos and Patrinos, 2018; Lemieux, 2006; Mincer, 1974) suggests that formal education, generally acquired during a young age, is a key determinant for future career paths, including the level of salary.
- **People who spend at least one full year on the project and no longer than five years.** Activities in a high-tech research project turned out to be a human and social capital incubator. People acquire knowledge, skills and competencies that are highly valued in the labour market. Based on previous studies,⁷⁰ the level of skill acquisition is a function of the duration of stay at the research project. This cut-off condition excludes the share of staff who remain at CERN for longer time periods.

Historical human resources data covering the 1990-2023 period were analysed to estimate the number of beneficiaries. The following categories of contracts were not considered in the analysis:

- Personnel with an indefinite staff contract, who stay at CERN for a long time;
- Corresponding associates and trainees (participating in an internship or other bilateral training programmes established with Member States), who typically stay for less than 1 year at CERN;
- Guest professors, who are typically older than 30 years old.

⁷⁰ Catalano et al. (2021); Camporesi et al. (2017); Camporesi (2001).

Table 40: Share of personnel under 30 years old and duration of stay at CERN, by contract.

CERN registration type acronym	Description	Share under 30 years old (average 1990-2019)	Average duration of stay at CERN (years 1990-2023)
STAFF (LD)	Employee with limited term contract	1.87%	5
FELL	Fellow at msc. Or phd. Level	54.00%	2.3
USER	User	28.52%	3.9
COAS	Cooperation associate	31.34%	1.4
PJAS	Project associate	34.65%	1.9
SASS	Scientific associate	2.29%	1
VISC	Visiting scientist	10.13%	1
DOCT	Doctoral student	80.81%	2.8
TECH	Technical student	88.37%	1
ADMI	Administrative student	83.30%	1
APPR	Apprentice	100.00%	3.44
Total		28.84%	3.79

Note: For staff with a limited term contract, the average duration of stay is from 1 to 5 years, but it can be extended up to 8 years. For the analysis, the share of staff remaining up to 5 years has been accounted for in the analysis. **Source:** Authors' elaboration based on CERN historical HR data.

Nearly 30% of personnel in the selected contract positions is younger than 30 years, with an average duration of stay at CERN of nearly 4 years. The latter parameter was confirmed by a survey - CERN between June 2020 and September 2022 - which found an average duration of the experience at CERN was 3.7 years.

When applying these parameters to the estimated number of FCC-ee project participants (Section 3.1.3), it is found that roughly **30% of project participants would enjoy a training benefit**. Consequently, 4,096 early career researchers were considered to benefit from a salary premium.

Table 41: Number of personnel under 30 and stay at the FCC-ee at CERN from 1 to 5 years, by contract.

Person description	Total number of participants (only considering new arrivals)	Cumulated number of participants over time
Estimated total number of people	14,202	258,107
Accelerator and infrastructure	780	27,594
Experiment 1	4,737	81,463
Experiment 2	4,737	81,463
Experiments 3 + 4	3,948	67,588
Estimated number of people under 30 years old and between 1 and 5 years of service	4,096	74,448

Note: The cumulated number of participants accounts for the total number of people who would be active on the project each year (the same individual can remain for more than one year). **Source:** Authors

➤ **STEP 2 - Determining the sector of work after leaving FCC**

The second step is to determine the sector in which students and early-career researchers will be likely to work after the experience in the project. Based on discussions held with the FCC study management, we assumed the following distribution⁷¹:

- 36% remain in the academia and research sector.
- 45% move to the industry and finance sectors.
- 19% move to the public administration sector and non-profit organisations.

This is the distribution of where people engaged in CERN projects move when they leave CERN and is based on CERN Alumni Survey carried out in 2014⁷².

➤ **STEP 3 - Estimating the duration of the working life**

The third step was to estimate the duration of the active working period of people after their project experience. It corresponds to the time people benefit from the salary premium, under the assumption that the premium will persist over the entire professional career.

Based on *ad-hoc* analysis implemented by Bianchini et al. (2019) and the collection of data on the duration of working life and retirement age in EU Member States and some extra-EU countries, we assume that the average active working life of people leaving the project follows a probability distribution shown in Figure 26. Its mean value is **37.5 years**. This means that two third of the students and early researchers entering the labour market in 2030 are expected to receive the salary premium until 2069. For those entering the labour market in 2050 the salary premium applies until 2089. More details are presented in Annex 8.4.

Figure 26: Probability distribution of the total active working life

Source: Authors

➤ **STEP 5 - Defining the salary functions**

The fourth step is about the definition of the lifetime salary evolution functions for each sector where CERN early-career researchers are expected to find a job. The literature on human capital accumulation considers the salary evolution predominantly as a function of the active working years (Psacharopoulos and Patrinos, 2018; Lemieux, 2006; Mincer, 1974). We adopted the same approach.

⁷¹ A different distribution is suggested by Bianchini et al., (2019) and Florio et al. (2016): 53% remain in the academia and research sector, 32% move to the industry and finance sectors, 15% move to the public administration sector and non-profit organisations.

⁷² They relied on a survey of 2,692 current and past members of the LHC and other experiments at CERN.

In 2020, data were collected from Glassdoor⁷³, a web service used by current and former employees from different countries worldwide to anonymously review companies and report their salaries. Data were obtained on the minimum, maximum and average yearly salaries of nearly 800,000 people from 16 countries⁷⁴ and 11 different job titles⁷⁵. 1,004 records with micro-level information on the salary, the number of years of work experience, the sector of employment (public, private, university, no-profit, hospital), and any additional monetary bonus or premiums was also collected. These data were processed to first attribute the different job categories in Glassdoor to the three professional sectors (academia and research, industry and finance, public administration and non-profit), second to convert all salary figures into CHF (2021) and third to empirically estimate the distributions of salaries by sector and year of experience.

The salary functions were determined using a logarithmic function, which fits the analysed salary data well (see Table 37 and Figure 27 below). The slope and intercept of the salary functions taken into consideration have been updated in the new study by means of GDP deflator to reflect 2024 prices. Annex 8.5 reports all the details about how the salary functions were determined.

Figure 27: Lifetime salary of early-career researchers by sector of employment (CHF)

Source: Authors' elaboration based on Glassdoor data

➤ **STEP 6 - Estimating the salary premium**

Camporesi et al. (2017) and Catalano et al. (2021) explored the contribution of spending a period of research and/or work at the Large Hadron Collider of CERN to the expected future lifelong salary of early-career researchers. They used data from a survey of CERN Alumni, another survey targeted to so-called "team leaders" at CERN. A team leader represents the academic institution that contributes to a high energy physics experiment at CERN and keeps track of the persons dispatched by that institute to CERN. They estimated a salary premium between 5% and 12% based on experience, but not reliable post-CERN employment contract data.

⁷³ <https://www.glassdoor.it/aziende/?source=gdemployermenu>.

⁷⁴ Italy, Germany, USA, France, UK, Spain, India, Brasil, Canada, Netherlands, China, Portugal, Belgium, Poland, Switzerland, Greece.

⁷⁵ Software Engineer, Analyst, Manager, Consultant, Professor, Statistician, Director, Manufacturing Engineer, Executive, Technician, Educator, Instructor, Researcher.

Therefore, a dedicated survey was implemented between 2020-2022 to estimate the salary premium using gross salary data actually reported by persons who have left CERN. The survey results confirmed the **positive correlation between the salary of people after their experience at CERN and the number of years they spent at CERN** (Figure 28).

Figure 28: Relationship between the salary and number of months of service at CERN

Note: Annual gross salary information and the number of years spent at CERN from 201 respondents. The correlation between the two variables is 0.26, statistically significant at 1% level (p -value < 0.01). Variables are measured in natural logarithms (ln). **Source:** Authors based on survey results.

Using survey data, we estimated the salary premium using a Mincerian salary function (see Box 4), the standard tool used in education economics to analyse the determinants of salary. **We found that the salary premium expressed as a percentage of the average yearly salary is a decreasing function of the number of years of service at CERN** (Figure 29). More specifically:

- An average salary premium of 3% (ranging from a minimum of 2% to a maximum of 4%) is gained for one year of work in a project at CERN;
- An average salary premium of 6% (ranging from a minimum of 2% to a maximum of 10%) is gained for the average number of years an early-career researcher works in a project at CERN (as from Table 39, 3.78 years, i.e. about 45 months).

Box 4: Estimation of a Mincerian salary function augmented with CERN relevant variables

The equation is: $Salary_i = \beta_o + \gamma CERN + \beta_1 EDU_i + \beta_2 EXP_i + \beta_3 EXP_i^2 + \beta_4 \bar{Z}_i + \varepsilon_i$

where:

- i is the i -th individual;
- Salary is the gross annual salary (often measured in log hours);
- CERN is the number of months of service at CERN (in log);
- EDU is the number of years in formal education (in log);
- EXP is the number of years of labour market experience (active working life) after leaving CERN (in log);
- Z is a vector that contains all the other socio-economic characteristics of individuals (gender, age, type of contract, size of firm, sector of employment, acquired skills, domain of activity, country).

In the equation above, the parameter of interest is γ , which captures the contribution of CERN on salary once the influence of all the other factors entering the equation is isolated. The parameter γ is expected to be positive and statistically different from zero.

Source: Authors based on Psacharopoulos and Patrinos, 2018; Lemieux, 2006; Mincer, 1974.

Figure 29: Salary premium as a function of the time spent at CERN

Source: Authors' estimation based on survey results

The survey confirmed that an experience-based learning process is instrumental in developing skills that are demanded by the labour market (Figure 30). The acquisition of hard skills, such as technical, problem-solving capacity, and scientific skills are likely to drive the initial career development of CERN early-career researchers, including their salary. Other skills, such as language skills, independent thinking, cultural and social skills also play an important role.

Figure 30: Determinants of the salary premium: skills acquired at CERN

Thanks to my experience at CERN, I have improved my:

My experience at CERN helped me...:

Note: Number of respondents to the relevant questions in the survey: 347. **Source:** Authors based on survey results.

➤ **STEP 7 - Estimating the training benefit**

We estimated the total value of training benefit using the parameters and data presented in steps 1 to 5. The estimated salary premium is applied to the salary functions by professional sector and then multiplied by the estimated number of people students and early career researchers that would leave the FCC-ee project every year. Figure 31 shows the time trend of the training benefit for early-career researchers who find a job either in the academic and research sector or in industry and finance, or in public administration and non-profit.

In the baseline scenario with a salary premium of 6% (on average, 3.78 years), **the total undiscounted benefit amounts to 20.7 billion CHF and 4.9 CHF when considering discounted value.** 47% of this benefit is enjoyed by people who are likely to find a job in the industry, 32% in academia, and 21% in the public administration sector.

The training benefit extends significantly beyond the time horizon of the project. This is due to the fact that the benefit persists for the entire duration of the working life of people, including for those who leave the project in the very last years of the operation phase. Because a significant portion of benefits occurs in the distant future, the discounting formula, which is used to express the benefits in present terms (as explained in Section 2.3.3), has a significant influence on the total benefit value benefit (Table 38).

Figure 31: Time profile of training benefits by professional sector – Baseline Scenario (CHF, not discounted)

Note: Annual salary benefits generated for the three employment sectors considered (academia & research, industry & finance, public administration and non-profit). The x-axis shows the year in which the benefit is generated. The y-axis indicates the undiscounted amount of CHF generated in that year. **Source:** Authors

Figure 32: Total training benefits by professional sector – baseline scenario (CHF and %, not discounted).

Source: Authors

Different scenarios are derived by applying different salary premiums, ranging from a minimum of 2% (worst scenario) to a maximum of 10% (best scenario). The table below summarises the benefit (CHF, discounted value) obtained for each scenario and for each sector of employment. The Figure below shows the time profile of the total value calculated in the three scenarios

Figure 33: Time profile of training benefits in the baseline, optimistic and pessimistic scenario (CHF, not discounted)

Note: Annual salary benefits generated for the three employment sectors considered (academia & research, industry & finance, public administration and non-profit). The x-axis shows the year in which the benefit is generated. The y-axis indicates the undiscounted amount of CHF generated in that year. **Source:** Authors

Table 42: Total estimated FCC-ee training benefit under different scenarios (CHF, discounted).

Training benefits	Worst-case scenario	Baseline scenario	Best-case scenario
Academia and research	534,698,336	1,604,095,007	2,673,491,678
Industry and finance	777,849,774	2,333,549,322	3,889,248,871
Public administration and non-profit	349,611,763	1,048,835,290	1,748,058,816
Total	1,662,159,873	4,986,479,619	8,310,799,365

Note: salary premium equal to 10% is considered in the best-case scenario, 6% in the baseline scenario, 2% in the worst-case scenario. **Source:** Authors

4.3. INDUSTRY BENEFITS FOR SUPPLIERS

Definition of the benefit

This impact pathway explores effects that the project is expected to generate on companies. A wealth of literature and empirical evidence exists documenting the channels through which big science and research infrastructure investments generate industrial spillovers (Sirtori et al., 2019; Florio et al., 2018; Griniece et al. 2020; Autio et al., 2004). Different effects that generate the impacts exist.

First, when companies work closely with the research infrastructure to develop technologically intensive products and deliver high-tech services, they exchange ideas and knowledge, feeding the creation of new processes, products and services that the companies can also exploit in other markets (see Castelnovo et al. 2018, Florio et al. 2018. and Sirtori et al. 2019). This benefit is related to the idea of the **FCC-ee as a platform of “Open Science & Innovation”**: the project can be used by companies as a platform to bring their technologies to higher maturity or quality levels, to test out new developments, to find solutions to costly or time-intense issues in an environment with low and controlled investment risks, which can eventually bring them additional market opportunities. Previous work on the LHC and the HL-LHC projects found that the socio-economic benefits generated through procurement activities for the construction and operation of the research infrastructure, defined as **procurement profit/sales multiplier** (or economic utility/sales ratio), accounts for over one-third of all the project benefits (Florio et al. 2016). Castelnovo et al. (2018) empirically proved that CERN suppliers of highly innovative technologies for LHC benefited from a higher profitability after their first contract with CERN. Bastianin et al. (2021) demonstrated that **becoming a supplier of CERN is associated with a statistically significant increase in the number of patent applications by firms**, even if this effect is observed in a relatively long-time range of five to eight years.

Second, persons who have actively participated in the research programmes can develop solutions that can find applications in society outside their initially targeted domain. This happens typically through technological development that stimulates the **establishment of spin-off companies** aimed at commercialising the new technology. Florio and Sirtori (2016) and the European Commission geode (2014) showed that the societal benefit from this technology transfer to society is reflected in the cumulative profit made by the new companies during their entire lifecycle.

Third, some studies found that **industry benefits propagate beyond the direct suppliers** and affect the entire supply chain (Nordberg et al., 2003; Autio et al., 2004). Recently, Florio et al. (2018) conducted an on-line survey addressed to CERN suppliers to explore the type of relationship established between suppliers and CERN, the variety of learning and performance benefits enjoyed, and the benefits to second-tier suppliers. Based on 669 valid responses, they found that both CERN suppliers and their subcontractors achieve a better economic performance, when they are directly involved in structured and collaborative relationships with CERN. These relationships facilitate the acquisition of technical know-how, provide access to resources, and reduce the

uncertainty and risks associated with complex projects, thus enabling suppliers to enhance their development activities.

Fourth, **the involvement of companies in the development and operation of the research infrastructure project can lead to territorial effects**, also called **local multiplier effects**. This is the additional economic benefit accrued to an area from the money being spent in the local economy. Several researchers have found strong evidence for the presence of the local multiplier effect of public or private investments, measured in terms of employment creation (e.g. Moretti, 2010). However, to the best of our knowledge, contrary to the work carried out in this study, there are no previous quantitative studies trying to estimate the local multiplier effect associated with research infrastructures.

Fifth, **changes in the economic activities of firms working with a research infrastructure and their business supply chain can generate increases in wages, profits and tax expenditures**. These, in turn, lead to changes in final demands: higher wages lead to higher consumption; changes in profits give rise to changes in additional household consumption; changes in profits also give rise to changes in capital⁷⁶ owners' income as well as investment in the case of retained profits or re-investment to offset the capital "used" in the production process as depreciation, also feeding into consumption. Rising tax receipts can lead to increased public spending at a constant budget deficit or reduce budget deficits at constant public spending. All these are referred to as **induced effects**: by working via value added, **they amplify the initial direct and indirect effects**.

In the context of this analysis, we have quantified the incremental long-term benefits associated with the direct supplier firms (procurement profit/sales multiplier). This is the first industry benefit accounted for in the analysis, which builds on consolidated empirical experience in the field of big science projects. Exploratory studies have been carried out in the past to estimate the benefit associated with ICT spin offs and the local multiplier effect of procurement on the local economy in which supplier firms operate (see Section 5 on Additional Benefits). The analysis of local effects of procurement is based on one case study that is relevant for the FCC-ee, the production of a large amount of superconducting radiofrequency cavities for the European XFEL project. The results of this analysis are detailed in Crescenzi and Piazza (2023) and are briefly summarised in Section 5.9. A dedicated study has been carried out to estimate the induced effects on value-added and employment using an Input/Output simulation model. Results are discussed in Streicher (2023) and summarised in Section 5.10. Local household spending and job creation effects have been estimated by Gutleber and Alix (2023) and are briefly outlined in Section 5.11.

Estimation

Following previous literature focusing on LEP (Schmied, 1977; Bianchi-Streit et al., 1984), this benefit is calculated through a procurement profit/sales multiplier. A multiplier for procurement activities relating to the CERN LHC programme was specifically estimated in 2020. The **multiplier is defined as the ratio between a supplier's profit that can be attributed to a CERN procurement activity (sales net of costs) and the volume of CERN contracts**.

Considering that the procurement multiplier derived for LHC procurement activities is very similar to the multiplier previously estimated for LEP, it is assumed that this multiplier does not significantly change over time and, thus, the same multiplier value has been applied during the analysis for the FCC-ee project.

The steps and parameters used to estimate the industry benefits are summarised in Table 43 and more extensively discussed in the following section.

⁷⁶ Notice that in this context, "capital" refers to the stock of *real* capital (mainly machinery, vehicles, buildings, but also licenses and software), not "financial capital" as funds of money.

Table 43: Steps and main parameters to calculate the value of industry benefits.

Step	Description	Key Parameter
1	Estimate the technological intensity level of FCC-ee investment	Value of investment cost with high or very high technological intensity level (scale 4 or 5): 2,550.3 million CHF Value of investment costs with a moderate or low technological intensity level (scale 2 or 3): 1,022 million CHF.
2	Estimate the procurement-related profit/sales multiplier	Profit/sales multiplier: 3.06 for procurement with high or very high technological intensity level 1.96 for procurement with low or moderate technological intensity level.
3	Estimate the total benefit and application of the net present value formula	Time lag between the contract start and the measurable occurrence of the benefit for the supplier: 5 years Social discount rate applied is 2% (see section 2.3.3).

Source: Authors

➤ STEP 1 - Estimate the technological intensity level of FCC-ee investments

Taking into account the specific content and characteristics of the different FCC-ee systems, the FCC study management assigned two parameters to each investment cost item:

- A **fraction of the system concerned**, which is the share of investment costs that can be considered leading to new or enhanced products and services, ranging from 0 to 1;
- A **technological intensity scale**, indicating the degree of design work and knowledge creation intensity on a scale from 1 (low) to 5 (high). We defined this scale following previous work by Castelnovo et al. (2018), who classified a sample of 300 LHC orders according to the following five-point scale:
 - 1) very likely to be off-the-shelf products⁷⁷ with low technological intensity.
 - 2) off-the-shelf products with an average technological intensity.
 - 3) mostly off-the-shelf products, requiring limited design and engineering work according to detailed specifications.
 - 4) products requiring project-related customisation and adaptation with a moderate to high design and engineering activity.
 - 5) products requiring scratch developments and CERN/supplier co-developments or significant adaptation of an existing product or service for the project.

The specific attributions are presented in Table 44.

⁷⁷ Note that the term “product” also includes material treatments, consultancies, constructions, installations and other services.

Table 44: FCC-ee technological intensity levels and fractions of concerned project segments and subsystems

System	Domain	Fraction of the system concerned [0-1]	Technological intensity scale [1-5]	Technological intensity origins
Pre-investment studies	All	0.05	3	Pre-investment studies
Collider magnets	Accelerator	0.5	5	Collider magnets
Collider radiofrequency	Accelerator	0.5	5	Collider radiofrequency
Collider vacuum chambers	Accelerator	0.5	5	Collider vacuum chambers
Power converters	Accelerator	0.3	3	Power converters
Power converters for ttbar	Accelerator	0.3	3	Power converters for ttbar
Element support and alignment	Accelerator	0.2	3	Element support and alignment
Beam transfer elements	Accelerator	0.5	4	Beam transfer elements
Beam intercepting devices	Accelerator	0.2	2	Beam intercepting devices
Beam intercepting devices for ttbar	Accelerator	0.2	2	Beam intercepting devices for ttbar
Beam instrumentation and diagnostics	Accelerator	0.8	5	Beam instrumentation and diagnostics
Protection and interlock systems	Accelerator	0.5	4	Protection and interlock systems
Controls	Accelerator	0.3	3	Controls
Machine-Detector Interface	Accelerator	0.2	3	Machine-Detector Interface
Machine-Detector Interface, 2 additional interaction points	Accelerator	0.2	3	Machine-Detector Interface, 2 additional interaction points
Polarisation and energy calibration	Accelerator	0.2	3	Polarisation and energy calibration
ttbar main and top-up ring RF + cryo + technical infrastructure	Accelerator	0.5	5	ttbar main and top-up ring RF + cryo + technical infrastructure
Linear accelerator	Injector	0.5	5	Linear accelerator
Positron production	Injector	0.5	5	Positron production
Damping ring and beam lines	Injector	0.5	5	Damping ring and beam lines
Technical infrastructures	Injector	0.3	3	Technical infrastructures
Transfer lines	Injector	0.5	4	Transfer lines
Cryogenics	Infrastructure	0.4	3	Cryogenics
Cryogenics, additional 2 interaction points	Infrastructure	0.4	3	Cryogenics, additional 2 interaction points
Electricity infrastructure and energy management	Infrastructure	0.5	3	Electricity infrastructure and energy management
Electricity infrastructure, 2 additional interaction points	Infrastructure	0.5	3	Electricity infrastructure, 2 additional interaction points
Cooling and Ventilation	Infrastructure	0.3	4	Cooling and Ventilation
Transport and logistics	Infrastructure	0.2	2	Transport and logistics
Transport and logistics, 2 additional interaction points	Infrastructure	0.2	2	Transport and logistics, 2 additional interaction points
Computing, data services, fibres	Infrastructure	0.3	3	

Geodesy and survey	Infrastructure	0.2	3	
Access, safety, radiation & environment monitoring	Infrastructure	0.5	3	
Subsurface civil engineering	Civil Engineering	0.4	3	
Subsurface structures, 2 additional interaction points	Civil Engineering	0.3	3	
Surface structures	Civil Engineering	0.4	3	
Excavated materials management	Civil Engineering	0.3	5	
CE planning, management, architecture, landscaping	Civil Engineering	0.4	3	
400 kV connection to grid in France	Territorial development	0	1	
20 kV connections	Territorial development	0	1	
Land plot, agriculture and environment-related costs	Territorial development	0.1	4	
Access related costs	Territorial development	0	1	
Water transport-related costs	Territorial development	0	1	
Administrative processes	Territorial development	0.5	4	
Experiment 1	Experiment	0.7	4	
Experiment 2	Experiment	0.7	4	
Experiment 3	Experiment	0.7	4	
Experiment 4	Experiment	0.7	4	

Source: Authors

Multiplying the technological intensity capacity percentage by the assumed cost for each item (see Section 3.1.2), we obtain a distribution of investment costs by technological intensity level. Table 45 presents this distribution in the baseline scenario. The total value of investment items considered to have some technological intensity capacity amounts to 6.8 billion CHF, corresponding to 43% of the assumed total investment costs (16 billion CHF). Of these investments, 45% have a moderate level of technological intensity, 20% have a high level, and 34% have a very high level of technological intensity.

Table 45: Value of FCC-ee investment costs with some technological intensity capacity

Technological intensity capacity, relevant for industrial benefit generation	Million CHF (baseline scenario, undiscounted)	Share over total investment costs
2 – low (off-the-shelf products with an average technological and technological intensity)	67.2	1%
3 - moderate (mostly off-the-shelf products, usually high-tech and requiring detailed specifications)	3,136	45%
4 - high (high-tech and highly innovative products with a moderate to high specification activity intensity to customise a product for LHC)	1,342	20%
5 - very high (products at the frontier of technology with an intensive customisation work and co-design involving CERN staff)	2,350	34%
Total value of FCC-ee investment items with technological capacity	6,895	100%

Source: Authors

➤ **STEP 2 - Estimate the procurement profit/sales multiplier**

As a starting point for the estimation of the multiplier, we built on previous results published by Castelnovo et al. (2018), which analysed a sample of LHC procurement contracts and estimated the net effect on revenues and profitability for CERN suppliers after their first contract with CERN. The sample was obtained by extracting contracts from the CERN procurement database over the 1995-2008 period. 1,269 industrial suppliers from 34 countries that received at least one order above 10,000 CHF for the LHC construction⁷⁸ were considered. For these firms, financial data on their revenues and profitability (EBIT = revenues net of losses, depreciation and amortisation but gross of interests and taxes) were collected from the ORBIS (by Bureau van Dijk⁷⁹) global database of companies. The final sample included 351 supplier companies for which long time series of financial data were available both before and after the year of the first contract with CERN (up to 15 or 20 years, depending on the company and the financial performance variable).

Table 46: Sample of LHC supplier companies used to determine the profit/sales multiplier.

From the CERN procurement database	➔	Sample considered
1,269 suppliers from 34 countries	Financial data are available for a long period of time before and after becoming CERN supplier (source: ORBIS database)	351 (28%) suppliers from 18 countries
Period 1995-2008		Period: 1995 - 2008
13,804 orders (> 10,000 CHF)		Period of analysis (incl. financial data): 1991 - 2014
		2,329 (17%) orders (> 10,000 CHF)

Source: Authors based on Castelnovo et al. (2018)

⁷⁸ Only orders above ten thousand CHF were considered so as not to include the smaller off-the-shelf contracts to which no industrial spill overs is generally associated.

⁷⁹ https://www.bvdinfo.com/en-gb/our-products/data/international/orbis?gelid=CjwKCAjw2K6lBhBXEiwA5RjtCbNwfR-MJX8DtCKzThCFru6_KT9yysud-H0ioL18hcZFY6e6fLrW8hoCaGUQAvD_BwE.

This sample included mainly large firms, based in France, UK, Spain, Germany, and Italy. Most of them (58%) supplied goods that have a higher technological intensity and level of innovation. Technology intense orders of the LHC concern mainly magnets, building work (incl. civil engineering), cryogenic technologies and low-temperature materials (e.g. superconducting materials, magnets and radiofrequency systems).

Using multivariate regression analysis, an econometric technique that estimates one outcome variable on the basis of the value taken by one or more predictor variables, Castelnovo et al. (2018) were able to “isolate” the CERN effect on suppliers’ performance from other factors. They found that:

- **Becoming a LHC supplier is associated with an average net increase in revenues of 45.6 million Euro (71 MCHF)⁸⁰ and a net increase in average profitability of 6 million Euro (9.3 MCHF)⁸¹ for each firm.** This is the average net effect after correction of any other factors that could impact on revenues, such as company size, inflation dynamics, GDP cycle, pure time effects and geographic-country effects.

The procurement effect on revenues and profitability is higher for suppliers of more high-tech and innovative products: if only the sub-sample (n = 222) of high-tech suppliers is considered,⁸² the net impact on revenues is 56.7 million Euro and on profitability (EBIT) is 8.8 million Euro (13.7 MCHF) per firm on average as shown in column 3 of Table 47.

Table 47: Impact of LHC procurement on suppliers’ revenues and EBIT.

	Entire sample (n=351)		Only high-tech sample (n=222)	
	Yearly variation operating revenues	Yearly variation EBIT	Yearly variation operating revenues	Yearly variation EBIT
	(th EUR)	(th EUR)	(th EUR)	(th EUR)
Factors influencing suppliers’ revenues/EBIT	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
LHC procurement effect	45,596.1***	5,999.5***	56,770.6***	8,863.1**
Supplier Size				
Very large	8,655.2***	295.0	11,833.7**	824.8
Large	-867.1	1,440.6	-4,178.2	1,924.0
Medium	-1,022.1	77.91	-2,333.4	213.1
Small	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Macro-economic factors:				
Annual variation of Inflation	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Annual variation of country GDP	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Time factors (year-fixed effects)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Years*country	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Constant	-30,830.7***	-2,531.8***	-18,338.2***	-2,605.3***

⁸⁰ The standard deviation of the normal distribution is equal to 18.4 million Euro.

⁸¹ The standard deviation of the normal distribution is equal to 2.3 million Euro.

⁸² Firms that have more than 50% of their orders labelled as high-tech.

R-squared	0.085	0.114	0.132	0.147
Number of observations	5799	5812	3703	3706

Note: Panel fixed-effects regression; Period 1991 – 2014. *p < 0.10, ** p < 0.05, ***p < 0.01

Source: Authors based on Castelnovo et al. (2018)

We used these results to calculate the procurement profit/sales multiplier. In line with the concept of economic utility/sales ratio previously used in the literature, which is defined in terms of incremental revenues minus potential losses or costs (Schmied, 1977; Bianchi-Streit et al., 1984), we used "profit" as the proxy of the economic "surplus" enjoyed by supplier firms. We divided the net economic effect of CERN procurement on profit (after subtracting the share of profit margin attributed to the CERN contracts, i.e. 5% according to Castelnovo et al. 2018) by the value of the procurement contracts (Table 48). This calculation provides a value for the procurement impact multiplier for LHC.

The analysis revealed that:

- **1 CHF spent on a procurement contract with a high level of technological intensity generates on average 3.06 CHF of additional profits for the supplier.**
- **1 CHF spent on all procurement for the LHC generated on average 1.96 CHF of additional profits for the supplier.**

We assumed that 1 CHF spent on a procurement contract with no or little technological intensity (e.g. purely off-the-shelf products) generates no additional profit/sales (multiplier = 0). The steps taken to estimate these multipliers are presented in the following table.

Table 48: Workflow to determine LHC procurement profit/sales multiplier.

Reference suppliers: CERN LHC suppliers between 1995-2008 Period of analysis (incl. financial data): 1991 - 2014			
Item	Value	Formula/Source	
CERN LHC procurement effect on supplier's EBIT (1 supplier)	EUR 5,999,500	Castelnovo et al (2018), Table 5	(A)
CERN LHC hi-tech procurement effect on supplier's EBIT (1 supplier)	EUR 8,863,100	Castelnovo et al (2018), Table 6	(B)
CERN LHC procurement effect on suppliers' EBIT (all sample, n=351)	EUR 2,105,824,500	(A)*351	(C)
CERN LHC procurement effect on suppliers' EBIT (hi-tech sub-sample, n=222)	EUR 1,967,608,200	(B)*222	(D)
Value of CERN LHC procurement contracts (all sample, n=351)	EUR 1,045,640,979	CERN LHC procurement database	(E)
Value of CERN LHC hi-tech procurement contracts (hi-tech sub-sample, n=222)	EUR 616,195,793	CERN LHC procurement database	(F)
Average EBIT margin (EBIT/Operating revenues)	5%	Castelnovo et al (2018), Table 1	(G)
Profitability (EBIT) MULTIPLIER	1.96	(C)-[(E)*(G)]/(E)	(H)
Profitability (EBIT) MULTIPLIER (hi-tech)	3.06	(D)-[(F)*(G)]/(F)	(I)

Source: Authors based on Castelnovo et al. (2018)

The profit/sales multiplier obtained for the LHC (3.06 for high-tech procurement) confirms the previous estimates for the LEP programme (average value = 3). For the estimation of the industrial spillover benefits of FCC-ee, **we assume that the LHC procurement impact multiplier also applies to FCC-ee procurement.**

➤ **STEP 3 - Estimate the benefit for FCC-ee suppliers**

We quantified the industrial benefit of procurement as follows:

- We only considered the share of FCC-ee construction costs that are likely to be subject to a minimum level of technological intensity only;⁸³
- For investments with a technological intensity level of 4 and 5 (high and very high), a profit/sales multiplier of 3.06 was applied;
- For investments with a technological intensity level of 2 and 3 (low or moderate), a multiplier value of 1.96 was used.

We assumed that a 5-year time lag occurs between the contract start and the time when the first effects for the supplier materialise.

Since the industrial spillovers were calculated by applying the multiplier to the capital expenditure, the benefits for suppliers correlate linearly with the contract volumes.

In the baseline scenario (i.e. assuming the average investment costs presented in Section 3.1.2), the benefit for industry suppliers amounts to 17.6 billion CHF (not discounted) and 9.5 billion CHF (discounted).

Table 49: Total estimated industrial benefit for suppliers – Baseline Scenario (Million, CHF)

	Not discounted	Discounted
Total investment costs	16,215	10,171
Investment costs with high and very high innovation level	6,896	4,246
Industrial benefit for suppliers	17,577	9,569

Source: Authors

⁸³ We are implicitly assuming that all this investment share will be outsourced through procurement. This is a realistic assumption for the accelerator and infrastructures. Civil engineering is the major part to be outsourced, followed by hardware and infrastructures.

Figure 34: Time profile of FCC-ee industry benefits for suppliers, compared with the high-tech investment costs – Baseline Scenario (CHF, not discounted).

Source: Authors

4.4. THE VALUE OF ICT INNOVATIVE SOFTWARE

4.4.1. Definition of the benefit

The development of ICT tools and the generation of widely available data not limited to scientific results (e.g. engineering test data, operation monitoring, system tests, etc.) are essential outputs of research infrastructures. Collectively, the LHC experiments produce about 16 petabytes of raw scientific data each year that is analysed using a worldwide distributed data processing environment, the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG). In 2017, the permanently stored data exceeded 200 petabytes and in 2023 it exceeds 300 petabytes. This corresponds to all the data stored in Facebook's "Hive" data store. The WLCG distributes today more than 1.3 exabytes of data from CERN to 11 major computing centres in Europe, North America and Asia. From there, it is sent to 170 centres in 42 countries. While raw, pre-processed and annotated data is first made available to the members of the scientific collaborations of the LHC experiments, a subset of the annotated data and simplified data suitable for self-programmed analysis software is also made available with a delay to researchers who are not members of the collaborations, schools and interested people via open access data infrastructures.

Putting in place a global data sharing- and processing infrastructure has led to the creation of numerous, openly accessible software packages, platforms and on-line services, which are also used in environments outside high-energy physics. They range from scalable data storage and distribution middleware over data analysis and visualisation to data management and workflow systems. Also, openly accessible software has been developed with value that extends beyond the scientific collaborations. Examples include innovative Cloud computing services (e.g. Helix Nebula Science Cloud⁸⁴ serving five scientific research domains), meeting and event management software (e.g. Indico) and information access software (e.g. Zenodo).

The socio-economic impact of ICT technologies and open data generated by research infrastructures remains an understudied topic in existing literature. A few previous studies have examined the socio-economic benefits of software packages such as Root and Geant4, which originated from the LHC programme but are now widely used beyond the high-energy physics community (Florio, Forte, Sirtori, 2016; Catalano et al., 2019). Similarly, in 2020, exploratory estimates were conducted to quantify the benefits of ICT developments related to open information platforms (e.g., Zenodo) and collaborative web services (e.g., Indico). The results of these estimates are presented in Section 5.7.

⁸⁴ https://www.hnscicloud.eu/sites/default/files/files/HNSC_BookletA5_November2018_21081123_web.pdf

Given the fast-paced evolution of ICT and the difficulty in fully capturing all potential developments induced by the FCC-ee, a conservative methodology has been adopted for the analysis of this impact pathway. This approach specifically considers software originally developed by CERN and its partners that are likely to be significantly upgraded or replaced to meet the needs of the FCC-ee.

Evidence gathered so far suggests that constructing a new circular collider, such as the FCC-ee, will necessitate substantial innovation in detector simulation software. This could involve either replacing or significantly enhancing Geant4.

4.4.2. Estimation

Geant4 is a tool to create simulations of the passage of particles or radiation through matter using the Monte Carlo simulation method. It is the reference simulation engine for the LHC experiments at CERN and other high-energy physics labs worldwide. The Geant4 software is the successor of the Geant series of software toolkits developed starting from 1994 (Amako, 2004). The source code is available under an open-source license, but it is also possible to use Geant4 indirectly through a program designed as a customised tool for an application domain, or to create a fully independent stand-alone application for a specific setup or detector. Application areas that are covered range from High Energy and Nuclear Physics, medical physics, assessment of material effects in accelerator beamline design, to the evaluation of the effects of space radiation on satellites and planetary bodies.

Like Geant4, any new simulation software – which will be required by FCC-ee science - can find use in the non-HEP community, thereby generating a spillover benefit for society. A number of further innovations can be related to the usage of artificial intelligence in this area or the introduction of quantum sensing and computing. Some of these developments are unpredictable, but the collaborations around the FCC-ee experiments will most likely be able to make significant contributions to simulation software development.

To estimate the value of this socio-economic benefit, the approach previously followed by Florio et al. (2016), when estimating the value of Geant4, is adopted.

Table 50: Steps and main parameters to estimate the value of a new detector simulation software

Step	Description	Key parameters
1	Estimation of the user community outside CERN	Number of institutes and companies (not individual users) using the software: 95 contributors + 30 external users (non-contributors).
2	Estimation of the development cost of the new software and the avoided costs for external users	Total development and maintenance cost: 44.2 MCHF (the same as for Geant4). Share of cost born by external contributors (non-CERN): 50%. Period of development: 2031-2057. Development cost born by each external contributor (non-CERN): 232 thousand CHF. Avoided cost for each contributing institute: 43.96 MCHF. Avoided costs for each other non-contributing institute: 44.2 MCHF.
3	Estimate the total benefit and application of the net present value formula	Social discount rate applied: 2.8% (see Section 2.3.3).

Source: Authors

➤ STEP 1 – Identifying user institutions

For Geant4, Florio et al. (2016) identified around 50 research centres, space agencies and firms using it. They included 38 institutions who contributed in some form to the development of the code, excluding CERN (e.g. Fermi National Accelerator Laboratory, SLAC National Accelerator Laboratory, Centre for Medical Radiation Physics, European Space Agency, etc.). 12 other laboratories, institutes and companies used the Geant4 licence

without having contributed to its development (e.g. NASA, General Electrics, Philips, Siemens, Varian, Boeing, General Motors). This figure is based on CERN data and reflects the user community in 2006 (<http://Geant4.web.cern.ch/Geant4/license/>). CERN does not keep track of the number of users and installations. More updated data (<https://Geant4.web.cern.ch/collaboration/members>) indicate a **user community of around 95 contributing institutes in 2023**, excluding CERN, either members of the Geant4 collaboration or external contributors. Keeping the 2006 proportion of 3:1 between contributing institutes and other non-contributing institutions constant, we can assume a **total number of 30 non-contributing users**. In the absence of more solid data to build our estimates on, this figure is considered sufficiently plausible and conservative.

➤ **STEP 2 – Calculating avoided costs**

The benefit is estimated as the avoided cost for the external users and it is based on the production cost of a new software. It was estimated that the production cost of Geant4 was about 44.2 million CHF up to 2013⁸⁵, i.e. in the first 20 years of its development, which started in 1994. This figure was based on the estimated effort involved in the development of the 2 million lines of C++ code base and an average annual salary of the persons involved of about 56,000 USD per year. Florio et al. (2016) assumed that CERN contributed 50% of this cost (22 million CHF). Hence, the remainder was covered by other external contributors. If we keep the same cost figures for the FCC-ee new software and assume the same share of contribution by CERN, the average contribution to the production cost for each lab would be 232,591 CHF (50% of 44.2 million CHF divided by 95). **The avoided cost for each contributing lab is the total estimated production cost net of their specific contribution. The avoided cost for other non-contributing users is the full production cost.** Table 51 shows that the benefit difference between a contributor and a non-contributor is insignificant and that the benefit for a contributor with respect to its engagement is huge. This is, unsurprisingly, the motivation for collaborative, open software development.

Table 51: Production cost of a Geant4-like detector design and/or simulation software

Description of cost element	Total production cost of Geant4 between 1994 and 2013 (CHF)	Average yearly production cost of Geant4 (CHF)
A - Total cost (including markup and code) for the software development	44,192,341	2,209,617
B - Production cost born by CERN (A*50%)	22,096,171	1,104,809
C - Production cost born by other contributing institutes (A-B)	22,096,171	1,104,809
	Total development cost of the new FCC-ee simulation software in the first 20 years (CHF)	Average yearly production cost of the new FCC-ee simulation software
D - Total cost (including markup and code) for the new software development (D=A)	44,192,341	2,209,617
E – Development cost born by each external contributor (non-CERN) (C/95)	232,591	11,630
F - Avoided cost for each contributing institute (F=D-E)	43,959,750	2,197,988
G - Avoided costs for each other non-contributing institute (G=D)	44,192,341	2,209,617

⁸⁵ Expressed in 2021 CHF terms.

Note: All figures are expressed in 2024 terms. **Source:** Authors

We assume that the new software would be developed starting from 2031, but further developments will continue even during the FCC-ee operation. For comparison, the first version of Geant4 available to external users was released in 1999, after 5 years of development, but its update continued in the following years. Version 11 was released in December 2022. The production cost paid by the contributing labs is assumed to distribute uniformly starting from 2031 to 2064 (the year of the last infrastructure upgrade).

A caveat to note: we do not account for the possibility of a joint initiative being established outside CERN by other research communities, as there is no evidence to support such a scenario—though it cannot be entirely ruled out.

➤ **STEP 3 Estimating the total benefit**

The total cumulated avoided cost representing the total undiscounted benefit is estimated to be 7,428 million CHF. The discounted benefit is 4,375 million CHF at the 2.8% social discount rate. This benefit, in fact, would stand for a range of potential software developments that cannot be explored in detail at this stage.

Table 52: Total estimated benefit of a detector modelling and simulation software – Baseline Scenario (Million, CHF).

Benefit description	Not discounted	Discounted
Simulation software development - contributing labs	5,638	3,321
Simulation software development - non-contributing labs	1,790	1,054
Simulation software development	7,428	4,375

Source: Authors

4.5. CULTURAL BENEFITS

Creating an interest in science among all citizens is part of the mission of any research infrastructure. To this end, organisations participating in the FCC-ee project have already launched and will continue to develop activities to attract lay people, for instance through exhibitions, open days and guided tours. Social media, news and press articles and websites are also used to disseminate news and facts about the research. The Science Gateway⁸⁶, a new visitor centre at CERN inaugurated in 2023, confirms the aim to increase the engagement of citizens.

To estimate the impacts of those "cultural benefits", we distinguish between benefits for onsite visitors and benefits for on-line ("virtual") visitors. They are discussed separately because the evaluation approaches are different. For on site visitors the well-established travel cost method is used to estimate the value. For virtual visitors, the socio-economic benefits can be estimated by valuing the estimated time spent on the social media and other on-line communication channels interact and consume the information.

Box 5: The value of cultural benefits of LHC and HL-LHC projects: overview of previous results

A first attempt of estimating the monetary value of the cultural impacts of the LHC programme was carried out by Florio, Forte and Sirtori (2016). The following groups of beneficiaries were considered: (a) onsite CERN visitors; (b) visitors to CERN travelling exhibitions; (c) people reached by media reporting LHC-related news; (d) visitors to CERN and experiment collaborations websites; (e) users of LHC-related social media (YouTube; Twitter; Facebook; Google+); (f) participants in two volunteer computing programs. It was found that the

⁸⁶ <https://sciencegateway.cern/home>

generated benefits amount to around 2.1 billion Euro (undiscounted, 2013 prices), thus contributing to around 12% of the total benefits.

An update of the estimations was carried out by Bastianin and Florio in 2018 in the framework of the cost-benefit analysis of the High Luminosity upgrade of the Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC), assessing its economic costs and benefits up to 2038. It was found that benefits stemming from outreach activities represent 13% of total benefits mostly coming from onsite visitors (57%).

An investigation carried out by Crespo Garrido and Catalano (2018) has confirmed the value of cultural benefits to the public provided by Florio et al (2016) and Bastianin and Florio (2018). More recently, Crespo Garrido (2020) focused on virtual visitors of CERN outreach activities, such as YouTube, social media (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and LinkedIn) and websites. Also, she reports results of a survey carried out to reveal the direct economic effects of onsite visitors. This work resulted in the creation of a spending distribution for onsite visitors. Details can be found at <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2711506>.

Source: Authors

4.5.1. Onsite visitors

To estimate the socio-economic cultural impacts for onsite visitors, first, the number of visitors that are expected to visit CERN and the FCC has to be estimated. Based on these figures, the socio-economic value can be estimated.

➤ **STEP 1 - Estimating the number of visitors**

We distinguish between three types of visitors: **(i) CERN total visitors, (ii) visitors to experiments and (iii) open day visitors.**

- **CERN conventional visitors:** This category refers to persons that visit any or a combination of the CERN visit points, such as e.g. microcosm exhibition, the proton-synchrotron, the LEIR accelerator, the Antimatter Factory, the Synchrocyclotron, the Globe of Science and Innovation, the Science Gateway, the large magnet assembly facilities, SCool lab and several other highlights.
- **Visitors to experiments:** these are part of a private group that visits the experiment only⁸⁷.
- **Open-day visitors:** these additional visitors are expected during open days which were assumed to occur every 5 to 7 years.

Overall, CERN currently welcomes almost 400,000 visitors per year. According to estimates based on current data provided by the FCC study management, a total of 19 million visitors are expected to be welcomed in a scenario with FCC-ee over the period 2024–2064 (see Table 53 below for details). The expected trend of these visitors is illustrated in Figure 35 below.

⁸⁷ According to information provided by CERN (as of January 15th, 2025), these visitors are not included in the total visitor count, as they participate in private guided tours.

Figure 35: Number of visitors forecasted in the FCC-ee project scenario

Source: Authors

To accurately estimate this benefit, it is essential to consider only the proportion of visitors who will come to CERN specifically because of the FCC-ee. For this purpose, we relied on a recent survey conducted by CERN started in June 2023 (hereafter referred to as the "CERN Visitor Survey"). While the survey is still ongoing, CERN extracted preliminary data on December 16, 2024, for this analysis. The dataset includes 3,547 responses collected since June 2023. According to the survey, 24% of visitors come as part of a group, while 76% visit individually. Additionally, 55% of visitors are classified as "CERN-motivated," meaning their primary reason for traveling was to visit CERN, whereas 45% are categorized as "Region-motivated" visitors who travelled to the area for other reasons and took the opportunity to visit CERN (see Table 53 below).

Table 53: Number of respondents by visitor type and rationale of visits

Motivation	Individual visitors	GROUP
CERN motivated	1,164	540
Region motivated	1,173	209
Total	2,337	749

Source: Authors' elaboration based on CERN Visitor Survey (2024)

Based on survey results and in agreement with the FCC study management, the following assumptions were applied:

- Conventional CERN visits: an increasing share of these visitors is attributed to FCC-ee, starting at 0% in 2024 and gradually rising to 50% by 2064.
- Visitors to the FCC-ee construction sites and the four experimental sites: these visitors are fully attributed to FCC-ee, as they would not have been accounted for in a scenario without FCC-ee.
- Visits to the decommissioned LHC tunnel: adhering to a conservative approach, these are not attributed to FCC-ee since they would be justified even in the absence of the FCC-ee.
- Open-day visitors: these are attributed to FCC-ee only for the additional capacity created by the new accelerator; all other visitors are excluded from the count.

Based on these assumptions, it is estimated that out of 19 million visitors, 5.5 million will be attracted by FCC-ee, while the remaining will be motivated more by the overall CERN activity and longstanding reputation of world scientific excellence. Details of these estimations, broken down by visitor type and the expected trend over the period, are provided in the table and figure below.

Table 54: Number of expected CERN visitors, 2024-2064

Site	Visitor type	Total N of visitors	N of visitors attributable to FCC-ee
Open Day Visits	Individual	680,000	230,000
	Group	0	0
Conventional CERN visits (it includes the Science Gateway)	Individual	10,475,000	1,149,750
	Group	3,874,500	425,250
Construction site visits to 6 sites: PA, PD, PF, PG, PJ, PL (no individual visits are possible)	Individual	0	0
	Group	960,000	960,000
No longer operated LHC and LHC Experiment sites (no individual visits are possible)	Individual	0	0
	Group	672,000	0
FCC-ee experiments and visitor centres	Individual	1,272,000	1,272,000
	Group	1,536,000	1,536,000
Sub-Total	Individual	11,977,500	2,651,750
	Group	7,042,500	2,921,250
Total		19,020,000	5,573,000

Source: Authors

Figure 36: Number of on-site visitors attracted by FCC-ee over the period 2024-2064

Source: Authors

➤ **STEP 4 - Estimating the benefit generated by onsite visitors**

Previous studies have valued the cultural benefits for onsite visitors by estimating the willingness-to-pay (WTP) for a visit⁸⁸. The most common way to estimate the WTP is through the travel cost method (see Box 6 below)⁸⁹, which reflects the socio-economic value to reach and visit CERN/FCC-ee.

Box 6: The travel cost method

The travel cost method (TCM) was suggested by Hotelling (1947) and developed by Clawson and Knetsch (1966) to assess the value of environmental resources and recreational sites⁹⁰. The TCM has also gained popularity in cultural economics, particularly regarding cultural heritage⁹¹. The method attempts to place a value on a non-market good by drawing inferences from expenditures incurred to ‘consume’ it, including the cost of the trip (e.g., fuel, train, or airplane ticket), the opportunity cost of time spent travelling, entry fees, onsite expenditures, and accommodation costs.

Two types of TCMs exist: the "individual demand approach" and the more common "zone of origin approach" (Anex, 1995). The latter is the simplest and least expensive approach and is applied by collecting information on the number of visits to the site from different distances. This information is used to construct the demand function and to estimate the economic benefits for the recreational services of the site. Instead, the individual demand approach uses survey data from individual visitors in the statistical analysis rather than data from each zone.

Although widely adopted, the TCM is affected by a major limitation that need to be addressed. The limitation relates to the apportionment issue arising whenever it is reasonable to assume that a trip is made for different reasons (a multi-purpose trip). Disentangling the willingness to pay of visitors for a given infrastructure when more than one attraction is located in the same site or in the same area could be arduous.

Source: Authors

According to this approach, the socio-economic value per visitor is estimated as the sum between:

- the cost incurred by visitors to travel to CERN and the FCC;
- the value of time spent travelling;
- expenditures incurred onsite and connected to their visit.

As to the first component of the travel cost method formula, the travel cost depends on the distance, i.e. the country of origin of the visitor and the transport mode used (plane, train, bus/car). On the basis of information on the origin country of visitors provided by the CERN survey of tourists, it was possible to calculate the share of visitors by distance and type of visitors (individuals or in group), and, for each combination (type of visitor and distance), the share of visitors by transport mode, being it either a car/bus, train or plane (see Table 55 below). The larger share of visitors originates from a distance ranging from 500km to 1500km, while the second most popular group is comprised of local visitors. As for the means of transport, plane is the only viable choice for long-distance trips, while the composition remains much more heterogeneous for short distances. Cars are the most popular means (81% for groups and 66% for individuals) for the 50-500km range category.

⁸⁸ See, for instance, Clawson and Knetsch (1966); Caulkins et al. (1986); Cuccia and Signorello (2000); and Bedate et al. (2004).

⁸⁹ See for instance, Pearce (1993); Loomis and Walsh (1997); and Mendes and Proença (2005).

⁹⁰ For a review, see, for instance, Garrod and Willis (1991); Hanley and Barbier (2009); and Tietenberg and Lewis (2008).

⁹¹ See, for instance, Alberini and Longo (2005); Bedate et al. (2004).

Table 55: Share of visitors by distance and transport mode.

	Share of visitors	Distance (midpoint km)	Roundtrip (km)	Car/bus/Tram	Train	Plane	Total
Group visitors							
Less than 50 km	30%	40	80	56%	39%	5%	100%
50 - 500 km	8%	300	600	81%	8%	11%	100%
501 - 1500 km	45%	1,000	2,000	40%	3%	57%	100%
> 1500 km	16%	2,000	4,000	0%	1%	99%	100%
Total	100%						
Individual visitors							
Less than 50 km	30%	40	80	65%	30%	5%	100%
50 - 500 km	9%	300	600	66%	13%	21%	100%
501 - 1500 km	36%	1,000	2,000	43%	12%	45%	100%
> 1500 km	26%	2,000	4,000	0%	0%	99%	100%
Total	100%						

Source: Authors' elaboration based on CERN Visitor Survey (2024)

The average travel cost by distance, transport mode and type of visitors was then estimated (see Table below). It is generally higher for individuals because, according to the survey responses, they typically prefer travelling by plane, while group visitors, which include many school trips, tend to come from closer locations, e.g. Switzerland, France).

Table 56: Average travel cost by distance and type of visitor (CHF 2024)

Distance	CERN motivated group visitor	Region motivated group visitor	Of which attributable to FCC-ee	CERN motivated individual visitor	Region motivated individual visitor	Of which attributable to FCC-ee
less than 50 km	102.56	174.64	81.30	106.76	195.59	83.70
50 - 500 km	155.19	215.70		234.24	272.92	
501 - 1500 km	324.82	303.12		246.53	307.93	
> 1500 km	468.95	505.74		535.53	527.36	
TOTAL	264.04	325.21		289.62	334.81	

Source: Authors processing of CERN's survey to visitors

As to the second component of the travel cost method formula, the value of travel time reflects the opportunity cost of time measured by the amount of hourly salary that the visitor forgoes while travelling. It directly depends on the distance and the transport mode. The following assumptions were applied:

- The number of hours needed for a roundtrip for each mode of transport was estimated as a weighted average between the hours travelled and the share of visitors by specific transport mode;
- For travel by car/bus, it is taken a speed of 70 km/h on average;
- For travels by train, it is taken an average speed of 70 km/h;

For travels by plane, the time to reach the airport and the time before boarding is considered, in addition to the average duration of a flight roundtrip.

The value of travel time per hour was calculated based on a literature review on the value of time for leisure activities (see Annex 8.6). Estimates are made for a baseline scenario, as well as for a more optimistic and pessimistic scenario, where higher or lower value of travel are assumed, respectively. The value of travel estimates applies to any type of visitor, both individuals and group visitors.

Table 57: Value of travel time per hour (CHF/hour).

Scenario	CHF/hour, 2024	Probability distribution
Pessimistic scenario	8	35%
Baseline scenario	15.4	50%
Optimistic scenario	20.4	15%

Source: Authors

By multiplying the share of visitors by distance (Table 55), the number of hours travelled (Table 58), and the value of travel time by distance (Table 57), we obtained the average value of travel time by distance for both individual and group visitors, in the three baseline, optimistic and pessimistic scenarios. The values are higher for groups due to the combination of transport modes that groups use compared to individuals: as shown in Table 55, groups tend to prefer travelling by bus on longer distances, while individuals prefer the plane; hence the longer travel time for visitors in groups.

Table 58: Average travel time (roundtrip) by distance and transport mode – Hours

Distance	Mid -Point (Km)	Roundtrip (Km)	Car/Bus (Hours)	Train (Hours)	Plane (Hours)	Total Time (Hours) - Weighted Avg
CERN visitors in group (N= 540)						
less than 50 km	40	80	1.1	1.1	2	1.19
50 - 500 km	300	600	8.6	8.6	3	7.98
501 - 1500 km	1,000	2,000	28.6	28.6	4	13.55
> 1500 km	2,000	4,000	57.1	57.1	8	8.72
Region visitors in group (N= 209)						
less than 50 km	40	80	1.1	1.1	2	1.17
50 - 500 km	300	600	8.6	8.6	3	7.53
501 - 1500 km	1,000	2,000	28.6	28.6	4	17.49
> 1500 km	2,000	4,000	57.1	57.1	8	8.00
CERN Individual visitors (N= 1,164)						
less than 50 km	40	80	1.1	1.1	2	1.17
50 - 500 km	300	600	8.6	8.6	3	7.36
501 - 1500 km	1,000	2,000	28.6	28.6	4	19.83
> 1500 km	2,000	4,000	57.1	57.1	8	8.21
Region Individual visitors (N= 1,173)						
less than 50 km	40	80	1.1	1.1	2	1.19
50 - 500 km	300	600	8.6	8.6	3	7.31
501 - 1500 km	1,000	2,000	28.6	28.6	4	17.60
> 1500 km	2,000	4,000	57.1	57.1	8	8.43

Source: Authors

For the third component of the travel cost method, we considered onsite expenditures, including accommodation costs, food and drink expenses, and souvenirs.

In order to properly account for FCC-ee attribution, a distinct willingness to pay was calculated for CERN-motivated and region-motivated visitors. According to CERN visitors survey, CERN-motivated visitors stay in the area for three days, while region-motivated visitors tend to stay longer, around four days, to visit other attractions in the region. For the purpose of WTP estimation, the following assumptions were made:

- For CERN-motivated visitors, the willingness to pay corresponds to 100% of the value of travel time, travel costs, and local expenses.
- For region-motivated visitors the willingness to pay is calculated on the assumption that they spend 1 day at CERN. For this reason, only 25% of the value of travel time and travel costs is attributed to FCC-ee, while local expenses are considered for just one day.

Detailed figures of onsite expenditure by item, distinguishing between CERN-motivated and region-motivated visitors (individual versus group), are provided in the Table 59. The daily average local expenditure of visitors incurred for a visit in the region is between 180 CHF for visitors in groups to 228 CHF for individual visitors. For CERN-motivated visitors, that figure is multiplied by the duration of the visit (3 days on average). Therefore, the total local expenditure amounts to 539 CHF for groups and to 684 CHF for individuals.

Table 59: Average expenditure for each visitor by item by stay (CHF, baseline scenario).

	CERN visitors in group (N= 540)	REGION visitors in group (N= 209)	CERN individual visitors (N= 1,164)	REGION individual visitors (N= 1,173)
Accommodation	236	79	328	109
Food and drinks	160	53	197	66
Souvenirs	94	31	91	30
Visits to other sites (museums, exhibitions), excl. CERN	49	16	68	23
Subtotal local expenditure	<i>(49%) 539</i>	<i>(52%) 180</i>	<i>(54%) 684</i>	<i>(62%) 228</i>
Travel cost	<i>(24%) 264</i>	<i>(23%) 81</i>	<i>(23%) 290</i>	<i>(23%) 84</i>
Value of time	<i>(27%) 297</i>	<i>(86%) 86</i>	<i>(23%) 299</i>	<i>(15%) 53</i>
TOTAL	<i>(100%) 1,100</i>	<i>(100%) 347</i>	<i>(100%) 1,272</i>	<i>(100%) 365</i>

Source: Authors based on CERN visitors survey

When considering the full travel cost, i.e. the sum of local expenditure, travel cost and the value of travel time, the total expenditure is between 347 and 1,272 CHF per stay. The average expenditure for each day depends on the motivation and the average is around 395 CHF per CERN-motivated visitor and 356 per region motivated visitor.

Figure 37: Share of expenditure for onsite CERN-motivated visitors in groups and individuals (2023-2024)

Source: Authors based on CERN visitors survey

As shown in the table below, CERN-motivated individuals and groups have a higher WTP compared to Region-motivated visitors.

Table 60: WTP of CERN visitors in the baseline scenario, CHF 2024

MOTIVATION		INDIVIDUAL VISITORS		GROUP	
		Total WTP per person	Of which local expenses	Total WTP per person	Of which local expenses
(CERN motivated)	Total	1,272	684	1,100	539
	Daily*	/	228	/	180
Region motivated	Total	365	228	347	180
	Daily*	/	228	/	180

Note: *the value of time and the travel cost do not change according to the number of days. **Source:** Authors based on CERN visitors survey.

To estimate the total cultural benefit for onsite visitors, the number of visitors attributable to the FCC-ee – distinguishing between individuals and groups - is multiplied by their respective WTP. The discounted benefit generated by onsite visitors is estimated to be approximately 2.2 billion CHF in the baseline scenario (see table below). Using the minimum and maximum values of time presented above, the worst-case and best-case scenarios are also calculated. The time profile of this benefit is shown in the Figure 38 below.

Figure 38: Time profile of FCC-ee cultural benefit related to onsite visitors (CHF, not discounted)

Source: Authors

Table 61: Total estimation under different scenarios (CHF, 2024)

	Not Discounted	Discounted
Worst case scenario	4,226,965,845	1,969,014,120
Baseline scenario	4,807,412,832	2,241,679,405
Best case scenario	5,195,290,143	2,423,884,981

Source: Authors

4.5.2. Virtual visitors

➤ STEP 1 - Definition and overall approach

Virtual visitors constitute an important impact pathway, given the ubiquity of the Internet to access information and entertainment. Virtual visits linked to the FCC encapsulate a large spectrum of different activities, ranging from the consultation of textual information to videos and social media. Direct engagement in the form of "virtual visits" appeared during the COVID-19 period and become ever more important, in particular for distant visitors around the globe.

Currently social networks may not exist in the future and may well be replaced by new products and services. However, it is assumed that the types of activities and services they propose will be retained in the next years. As a consequence, the data we used on existing social media for the benefit estimation (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn and Youtube), can be considered representative of more abstract types of media (i.e., personal network, photos network, short text/information network, professional network, and video network) and can be used in the estimates even if the specific products and services are expected to evolve or be replaced

We estimated the impacts from the following on-line channels:

- **Visits to social media accounts managed by CERN**, including two types of activities: **impressions** (number of times a piece of content is seen) **and engagements** (number of actions, such as likes or shares, taken on a piece of content).
- The following types of social networks are considered in the analysis:
 - Personal network (e.g. Facebook)
 - Photos network (e.g. Instagram)
 - Text/short information network (e.g. Twitter)
 - Professional network (e.g. LinkedIn)
 - Video network (e.g. Youtube).
- Visits to the CERN managed websites
 - CERN main website
 - Websites of the LHC experiment collaborations.

Due to data availability constraints, the analysis focuses on virtual visits to the content directly managed by the CERN. For this reason, the figures presented must be considered as a lower-bound estimate of on-line cultural benefits today. In particular, the estimation does not include:

- On-line visits to social media content produced by the collaborations (i.e., through their own accounts and pages);
- Participants in the virtual tours that CERN started organising during the COVID-19 period;
- Cultural benefits from exposure to CERN or FCC-related content produced by any other media (e.g. newspapers, websites, fora, blogs, other social media pages not managed by CERN). This "on-line echo" from FCC activities cannot be entirely attributed to the project, but it is more of an indirect benefit. For this reason, it is not accounted here. However, it is discussed in Section 5 with reference to the perception of society for CERN and the FCC project.

Empirical studies show that when consumers are accustomed to receiving an on-line service or content for free, their willingness to pay for it is very low or nil (see, for instance, Chyi, 2005). Considering that most web and social media resources are free of charge, the overall approach to estimating benefits from this outreach activity is therefore based on the "opportunity cost of time" spent engaging with the different digital activities. The "opportunity cost of time" is the value of the time that the information consumer could use to do the next best thing instead of consuming the on-line contents. This may be a leisure activity or a professional activity. This approach can be seen as a direct extension of the travel cost method (used to evaluate the benefit for on-site visitors) and builds upon extensive literature on the value of leisure time (see, for instance, Boardman et al., 2011).

The benefit estimate is carried out in two sequential steps: the estimation of the volume of on-line visits expected to be directly caused by the FCC project and the economic valuation of the time spent during these visits.

➤ **STEP 2 - Estimating the volume of on-line visits**

The volume of on-line visits related to the FCC-ee is estimated on a yearly basis. It relies on historical data collected from CERN's communication group on visits to the main CERN website and social media accounts. Hence, these data are not specific to particular research projects. For our analysis, assumptions were made regarding the number of visits specifically attributable to the FCC-ee. This estimate has been revised to reflect updates to the project timeline and to ensure consistency with onsite visitor estimates, particularly concerning the share of visits attributed to the FCC-ee. It is now assumed that the maximum attributable share of visits is approximately 50%, aligning with the assumption used for total CERN visitors (as discussed in the previous section). In the scenario without the FCC, it is assumed that the number of on-line visits to websites and social media will follow the same patterns as the on-site visitors. This conservative assumption implies stability of the activity for most of the forecasting period, with a drop in 2041-2043, corresponding to the end of the LHC activity.

In the scenario with the FCC, it is assumed that the volume of on-line visits caused by the FCC mirrors the trend of growth of the scientific publications due to the FCC-ee. The share of online visits attributable to the FCC-ee starts as a marginal share of the total CERN on-line visits. The main jump in on-line visits is expected to occur in 2048, with the start of operations. Then, this share is expected to grow further during the operative phase. The number of on-line visitors is expected to reach its maximum between 2051 and 2064. In these years, the share of the total CERN on-line visits associated with the FCC reaches about 50% in 2051 and remains constant after that. This share is in line with the historical data of LHC, with reference to the period of its construction and operation (Florio, Forte and Sirtori 2016).

Figure 39: Share of total CERN on-line visits associated with the FCC-ee

Source: Authors

To estimate the number of visits linked to CERN social media, we used historical data of impressions and engagements for the 2019-2022 period provided by the CERN communications group.⁹² Future growth patterns are assumed to be the same for all types of social media and for both engagements and impressions.

These revised growth patterns have been applied to historical data on CERN's online traffic, as provided by the CERN communications group. Future growth trends are assumed to be consistent across all types of social media, as well as for both engagements and impressions. Due to the adjustments made in this analysis— affecting both on-site visitors and publications—the estimated number of attributable impressions, engagements, and online visitors has been revised accordingly. Specifically, for the FCC-ee over the 2024–2064 period, impressions are estimated at 1.7 billion, engagements at 83 million, and CERN website visits at 183 million. Under these assumptions, impressions and engagements related to CERN social media are estimated as displayed in the following figures.

Figure 40: Estimates of impressions related to FCC-ee on CERN-managed social media

Note: the chart displays the number of visits in the incremental scenario, hence net of the number of visits that would occur even in the without-the-project scenario. **Source:** Authors

⁹² Historical data for 2019-2022 had some missing months. We calculated the yearly values using simple proportionality (e.g., if two months were missing, the values for the ten months were summed and multiplied by 12/10 to obtain a yearly estimate).

Figure 41: Estimates of engagements related to FCC-ee on CERN-managed social media (incremental scenario).

Note: the chart displays the number of visits in the incremental scenario, hence net of the number of visits that would occur even in the without-the-project scenario. **Source:** Authors.

At its full regime from 2048 onwards, the FCC-ee is expected to generate 135 to 162 million impressions and 6 to 7 million engagements each year. This is about 1.5/2 times the level of visits of CERN social media in the latest historical data.

For the CERN websites, historical data were extracted from the analytics solution of the CERN ECO group which refer to the main CERN website. The data covers the period from December 2018 to March 2023. However, due to a change in the Cookie policy in March 2021, the number of visitors is severely underestimated from this month onwards. As the number of visits was fairly stable over the period 2018-2020, the data used for the estimating consists of the historical data from 2020. In line with these patterns, and as a conservative approach, the number of visits is considered stable up to 2022, at the level of the 2020 year.

For the experiment collaboration websites, we rely on data from 2017 from Crespo Garrido (2020). In this study, it was estimated that the total number of visits (including the experiments' websites) was 16.5% higher than those of the main CERN website only. This ratio is used for the 2020-2022 period to correct our estimates of the total visits.

FCC-related visits to the CERN websites can thus be estimated using the previously mentioned assumptions (Figure 42). The **number of website visits generated by the FCC-ee is assumed to reach about 16 to 17 million per year in the 2050s.** This is about 1.5 times the total CERN websites' activity at the beginning of the period.

Figure 42: Estimates of visits to the CERN websites

Source: Authors

➤ **STEP 3 - Estimating the benefit for virtual visitors**

To estimate the socio-economic value of virtual visits, we need an estimation of the average time spent for each visitor, and the marginal social value of their time.

Previous research has highlighted methodological difficulties in estimating time spent on on-line activities. Extensive literature has been developed on this matter, in particular in the context of psychology and medical research on the linkages between depression and social media use (see Parry et al., 2021 for a methodological review⁹³). A key insight is that self-reported estimates of time spent tend to be unreliable.

As a result, estimates used in this report for social media are based on existing evidence from multiple sources, especially from the social media companies themselves. Indeed, these companies have granular information on time spent for specific interactions (e.g., minimum time to count a view for an Instagram post). For the time spent on engagement (e.g., shares, likes, etc.), it is arbitrarily assumed to take 1 second in each situation. Engagements and impressions are cumulative, i.e., an impression may lead to an engagement, and if this is the case, the time spent for both actions are added. The estimates are summarised in Table 62.

⁹³ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9167894/>

Table 62: Average time spent by social media and type of visit.

Social media	Time spent on an impression	Time spent on an engagement
Personal network	4 seconds ⁹⁴	1 second
Photos network	3 seconds ⁹⁵	1 second
Text/short information sharing	4 seconds ⁹⁶	1 second
Professional network	4 seconds ⁹⁷	1 second
Video network	246 seconds ⁹⁸	1 second

Sources: Authors' estimates based on Facebook, Instagram, Business Insider, Statista, Databox, Hootsuite.

As to the websites, the estimate of the time spent for each website visit is based on statistics from the CERN analytics platform. Based on statistical analysis, a visit is assumed to last on average 203.49 seconds (a bit more than 3 minutes).

Combining the volume of visits generated by the FCC-ee and the estimates of time per visit, it is possible to derive the total time spent during the period under evaluation. The formula is a simple multiplication:

$$Time\ spent_{i,j} = volume\ of\ visits_{i,j} \times time\ per\ visit_j,$$

where i is the year (ranging from 2021 to 2057), j is the activity (ranging from 1 to 3: impressions & engagements on social media, visits on the websites).

Overall, **time spent by virtual visitors on CERN social media is estimated to amount to about 17 billion seconds, or 203,000 days during the 2024–2064 period due to the FCC-ee.** Time spent on impressions is much higher than for engagements, as impressions represent 99.5% of the total. Videos contribute the largest share, with approximately 11 billion seconds (or around 130,000 days) spent watching video content. This is due to the longer duration of this type of content compared to the others. Personal networks (e.g., Facebook) and text/short information networks (e.g., Twitter) are the other important contributors to time spent, accounting for 13% and 12% of the total, respectively.

Time spent on virtual visits to the CERN websites is much higher than the total time spent on social media. Indeed, these visits represent around 37 billion seconds or around 430,000 days during the observation period.

We assume that the average time per visit remains constant over the entire observation period. Hence, the yearly patterns of time spent follow the evolution of the volume of visits only.

The value of the time spent is calculated with the "opportunity cost" method, which implies that the time spent on social media and websites is reflected by the missed opportunity to spend time on other, potentially profitable activities. Since not all virtual visitors are likely to be economically active workers, we cannot use wages to estimate the opportunity cost of time. Instead, we used the per capita GDP, differentiated by the geographical profile of the virtual visitors. Historical demographic data from CERN social media are considered to estimate the geographical breakdown of virtual visitors for both the CERN social media and the websites. In particular, data from Youtube is used, given that it is the most granular information available in terms of number of countries. The composition of visitors is described in Figure 43.

⁹⁴ Estimate derived from <https://blog.hootsuite.com/ideal-social-media-post-length/> suggesting that the best time is similar to a tweet. Note that FB research on time spent by piece of content in feed (NB: video only) is different at 2 sec:

<https://www.facebook.com/business/news/insights/capturing-attention-feed-video-creative>

⁹⁵ Estimate derived from IG counting of views: <https://help.instagram.com/1562166204102854>

⁹⁶ Estimate derived from <https://www.businessinsider.com/it-would-take-10-years-to-read-one-days-tweets-2011-2?r=US&IR=T> ; reduced to account the fact that this is ideal not actual time

⁹⁷ Estimate derived from <https://blog.hootsuite.com/ideal-social-media-post-length/> suggesting that the best time is similar to a tweet.

⁹⁸ Estimate based on Statista average duration of Youtube videos - 11.7 min (<https://www.statista.com/statistics/1026923/youtube-video-category-average-length/>) and databox estimate of typical retention rate (35%) (<https://databox.com/audience-retention-youtube>)

Figure 43: Assumed composition of virtual visitors by country of origin

Note: Other developed countries include Canada, Italy, Switzerland, Spain, Australia, the Netherlands, Poland, Greece, Japan, Belgium, Sweden, Romania, South Korea and Austria. Other emerging countries include Brazil, Russia, Mexico, Turkey, the Philippines, Indonesia, Ukraine and South Africa. **Source:** Authors’ assumptions based on Youtube data (provided by CERN).

On-line visitors come mainly from the USA (44%) and from other highly developed countries, but also from some emerging economies, such as India (8%). Thanks to this demographic data, it is possible to weigh the GDP per capita of different countries to obtain an average GDP per capita of virtual visitors. The geographical breakdown is assumed to remain constant over the time period. GDP per capita of individual countries is assumed to grow as indicated by the International Monetary Fund (World Economic Outlook Database 2020).⁹⁹

Considering that the annual per capita GDP corresponds to the output produced for 365.25 days, each one composed of 24 hours of 3,600 seconds, it is possible to derive the value of a second of time for a visitor by dividing the yearly GDP per capita by 31.5 million seconds in a year. Given that we have estimates for the time spent for each on-line interaction, we can multiply them by the value of a second to obtain monetary estimates of these actions for the visitors. The obtained values for each type of interaction in 2024 are displayed in the table below¹⁰⁰.

Table 63: Monetary valuation by type of visits in 2024 (CHF)

Social media	Monetary value of each impression or visit in 2024	Monetary value of each engagement in 2024
Personal network	0.0074	0.0018
Photos network	0.0055	0.0018
Text/short information sharing	0.0074	0.0018
Professional network	0.0074	0.0018
Video network	0.4545	0.0018
CERN websites	0.3764	Not applicable

Source: Authors

⁹⁹ IMF data does not provide GDP growth rates for some countries. Hence, their growth rates were extrapolated by CSIL based on countries with similar levels of development. India, Brazil, Mexico, Philippines, Indonesia and South Africa were predicted to have the same growth pattern as Turkey; Canada, Australia were predicted to have the same growth pattern as USA; South Korea was predicted to have the same growth pattern as Japan.

¹⁰⁰ These figures change over time based on the weighted GDP per capita developed above.

Multiplying the monetary values with the volume of on-line visits over time leads to the estimate of the undiscounted annual benefit generated by the FCC-ee. They are summarised in Figure 44.

Figure 44: Time profile of FCC-ee cultural benefits for on-line visitors (CHF, not discounted).

Source: Authors

Visits to the CERN social media account account 32% of the benefits over the entire period, compared to 68% for the visits to the websites.

The total undiscounted cultural benefit for on-line visitors is estimated to be approximately 229 million CHF (Table 64) and the discounted benefit amounts to about 102 million CHF.

Table 64: Total estimated cultural benefit for online visitors – Baseline Scenario (CHF)

Cultural benefits	Not discounted	Discounted
Social media	73,569,596	32,797,160
Websites	155,623,008	69,376,386
Total	229,192,604	102,173,545

Source: Authors

4.5.3. Total cultural benefits

Summing up the cultural benefits enjoyed by onsite and online visitors, **the total undiscounted benefit accounts for 4.8 billion CHF, 95% associated to onsite visitors.**

Table 65: Total estimated cultural benefit for onsite visitors – Baseline Scenario (CHF)

Cultural benefits	Undiscounted	Discounted
For onsite visitors	4,807,412,832	2,241,679,405
For online visitors	229,192,604	102,173,545
Total	5,036,605,436	2,343,852,951

Source: Authors

4.6. TOTAL QUANTIFIED BENEFITS AND BENEFIT-COST RATIO

The estimated value of all the benefits that we measured and monetised with the socio-economic impact studies is summarised in Table 66. Both discounted and undiscounted values are presented, but **comparisons across different benefits and the calculation of the total amount of benefits are only possible using discounted values**, which allow comparability of benefits accruing in different time periods (as explained in Section 2.3.3.22.3.3.2 on the Social Discount Rate).

The total present value of quantified benefits amounts to 24 billion CHF in the baseline scenario. The largest benefit, among those that have been quantified, is related to the industrial spillovers for suppliers, accounting for nearly 40% of total estimated benefits. The second largest benefit is for early career researchers, particularly in terms of the skills they develop and the reputational advantages gained from their time at CERN, both of which significantly enhance their professional careers.

By comparison, the total costs estimated for the entire duration of the FCC-ee project – including investments costs, operational costs and environmental costs - amount to 20 billion CHF (discounted). **The net present value (NPV) of the FCC-ee project in the baseline scenario, i.e. the discounted value of all estimated benefits net of costs, is positive and amounts to 4,071 million CHF. The benefit/cost ratio is estimated at 1.20**, meaning that the quantified socio-economic benefits so far exceed costs by 20%. A positive NPV and a benefit/cost ratio higher than one indicate a clear positive net contribution of the FCC-ee project to societal well-being in the baseline scenario.

The probability distribution of obtaining a positive net present value from the implementation of this project will be estimated in a subsequent iteration of the analysis. All the main uncertain variables will be singled out, more pessimistic or optimistic values will be attributed according to specific distribution functions, and a Monte Carlo simulation will be run to determine the NPV estimate in probabilistic terms.

Table 66: Total estimated benefits and costs of the FCC-ee project - Baseline Scenario (Million, CHF)

	Share of the total	Not discounted	Discounted
TOTAL COSTS	100%	38,308	20,020
CAPEX	50.8%	16,215	10,171
OPEX	47.1%	21,212	9,423
OPEX PERSONNEL		16,802	7,544
OTHER OPERATIONAL COSTS		4,410	1,879
NEGATIVE EXTERNALITIES	1.7%	653	354
SHADOW COST OF CARBON*		633	341
SOCIAL COST OF IONISING RADIATION		1.3	0.6
SOCIAL COST OF PROJECT-RELATED INDUCED NOISE		0.02	0.02
LOSS OF AGRICULTURAL INCOME, BIODIVERSITY & HABITAT		8	4
SOCIAL COST OF PROJECT-RELATED TRAFFIC-INDUCED AIR POLLUTION		1	1
SOCIAL COST OF PROJECT-RELATED TRAFFIC-INDUCED GHG EXTERNALITIES		10	7
DECOMMISSIONING COSTS**	0.4%	228	72
TOTAL CORE BENEFITS	100%	57,244	24,092
SCIENTIFIC PRODUCTION	11.7%	6,515	2,817
EARLY CAREER RESEARCHER TRAINING	20.7%	20,687	4,986
INDUSTRIAL BENEFITS FOR SUPPLIERS	39.7%	17,577	9,569
OPEN SOFTWARE (EXPERIMENTS AND DETECTORS)	18.2%	7,428	4,375
CULTURAL BENEFITS	9.7%	5,037	2,344
... FOR ONSITE VISITORS		4,807	2,242
... FOR ONLINE VISITORS		229	102
NET PRESENT VALUE			4,071
BENEFIT / COST RATIO			1.20

Note: Discounted values at 0.028 Social Discount Rate. *Limited to the construction and operation phases without the GHG emissions associated with the construction of the accelerator. **Approximated using the

dismantling costs estimated at CERN, being aware that decommissioning costs are generally higher than dismantling costs. **Source:** Authors.

Figure 45 shows the overview of the quantified core benefits.

Figure 45: Overview of quantified benefits – Baseline Scenario (Million CHF, discounted)

Source: Authors

5. ADDITIONAL BENEFITS

Additional benefit pathways have been explored and assessed. Due to the uncertainties associated with these benefits at this stage, they have not been included in the estimates presented in the previous chapters. They are discussed separately in the following sections to offer a more comprehensive perspective on their potential impact and significance.

5.1. RESIDUAL VALUE

FCC-ee is conceived as both a stand-alone project and as the enabler for the second-phase programme a hadron collider in the order of 100 TeV c.m. collision energy (FCC Conceptual Design Report). The building of assets for FCC-ee that can be made available for the subsequent FCC-hh project is a pillar of the sustainability concept for an integrated research programme that can last until the end of the 21st century.

From the perspective of the socio-economic impact study, some of the fixed assets developed for the FCC-ee research infrastructure will not be used for FCC-ee only (see their costs in Section 3.1.2) but will remain available as a “gift” for the subsequent project. This benefit is commonly referred to as the “residual value of the project” (European Commission 2014; StR-ESFRI 2019). The residual value reflects the capacity of the remaining service potential of fixed assets whose economic life is not yet completely exhausted.

According to Article 18 (Residual value of the investment) of Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 480/2014 the valuation of the residual value can be made in the case of non-revenue generating projects by computing the value of all assets and liabilities based on a standard accounting depreciation formula or considering the residual market value of the fixed asset as if it were to be sold at the end of the time horizon.

We have estimated the residual value at the end of the FCC-ee phase in three steps using a simplified and conservative approach.

- *First*, CERN identified the assets that are expected to retain some residual value at the end of the FCC-ee phase. They are assumed to be the RF systems for the Z and ttbar operation modes the electricity infrastructure the ventilation and cooling systems and all subsurface and surface civil structures. Additional systems may also retain some value at the end of the FCC-ee project time horizon, but they are not considered for the sake of prudence.
- *Second*, CERN defined the share of the initial investment cost that will retain a value for FCC-hh also thanks of the maintenance and repair actions are conducted over the FCC-ee life time (whose costs have been accounted for in the operating costs see Section 3.2). These estimates are based on discussions with managers of the FCC international collaboration involved in the systems’ design and development.
- *Third* we have multiplied the residual share by the initial investment costs to determine the retained value for each asset.
- *Fourth* we have applied the Social Discount Rate to report a final discounted residual asset value.

The residual value of the assets built up during the FCC-ee phase is estimated to be in 2066 at approximately 7.9 billion MCHF (undiscounted), which corresponds to 55% of the total FCC-ee investment costs. The discounted value is 2.5 billion MCHF.

Table 67: Items with residual value beyond 2064 (CHF)

Item	Domain	Share of residual value	Total discounted	Total not discounted
Power converters for ttbar	Accelerator	20%	313,537	1,000,000
Element support and alignment	Accelerator	20%	14,422,715	46,000,000
Beam intercepting devices for ttbar	Accelerator	20%	2,006,639	6,400,000
ttbar main and top-up ring RF + Cryo + technical infrastructure	Accelerator	80%	285,695,168	911,200,000
Cryogenics	Infrastructure	50%	32,451,108	103,500,000
Cryogenics, additional 2 interaction points	Infrastructure	50%	470,306	1,500,000
Electricity infrastructure and energy management	Infrastructure	50%	101,899,616	325,000,000
Electricity infrastructure, 2 additional interaction points	Infrastructure	50%	940,612	3,000,000
Cooling and Ventilation	Infrastructure	85%	220,401,030	702,950,000
Transport and logistics	Infrastructure	100%	55,182,561	176,000,000
Transport and logistics, 2 additional interaction points	Infrastructure	100%	3,448,910	11,000,000
Computing, data services, fibres	Infrastructure	100%	26,650,669	85,000,000
Geodesy and survey	Infrastructure	100%	116,949,405	373,000,000
Access, safety, radiation & environment monitoring	Infrastructure	100%	62,707,456	200,000,000
Subsurface civil engineering	CE	100%	1,351,345,670	4,310,000,000
Subsurface structures, 2 additional interaction points	CE	100%	0	0
Surface structures	CE	100%	158,022,788	504,000,000
400 kV connection to grid in France	Territorial development	100%	9,406,118	30,000,000
20 kV connections	Territorial development	100%	9,406,118	30,000,000
Land plot, agriculture and environment-related costs	Territorial development	100%	10,973,805	35,000,000

Access related costs	Territorial development	100%	16,303,938	52,000,000
Water transport-related costs	Territorial development	100%	1,254,149	4,000,000
Total			2,480,252,318	7,910,550,000

Source: Authors

5.2. CREATION OF RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES THROUGH CONTRACTS

Introduction

CERN including the FCC-ee has an electrical energy consumption varying between 400 GWh and 2 TWh per year. New market realities resulting from geopolitical developments as well as changes in demand of member states and their citizens requiring low carbon and green solutions are accelerating the need to decarbonise energy supply whilst creating new opportunities across the power value chain. In line with the REPowerEU plan¹⁰¹ CERN strives for energy independence and energy cost planning security and aims therefore at operating the FCC as much as reasonably possible with renewable energy sources. The proposed concept contributes to "Repower Europe" and supports the transition to a carbon neutral society according to the Commission Recommendation on facilitating Power Purchase Agreements (PPA).¹⁰² The ultimate objective is to maximise the amount of renewable electricity in the portfolio while maintaining maximum supply guarantee and minimising costs. The feasibility of such endeavour and the associated investments costs have been explored in two high-level exploratory studies prepared by external consultants in 2023 (Accenture, McKinsey).

According to the results of such studies, the FCC and the CERN can be supplied with RES during operation at a stable cost thanks to the use of multiple incremental long-term power purchasing agreements (PPAs). These agreements will provide planning security for electricity suppliers that lets them invest in building up significant RES capacities in the GW range for which only a part would be used for the FCC because the particle collider is characterised by a varying operation pattern throughout the year and over its fifteen years of operation. The unused capacities can be made available for other users, thus helping to speed up the energy transition and access to RES at a competitive cost. Including in a PPA the condition to make excess energy available to the market would lead to the generation of a societal impact by supplying electricity from RES to society. This will also allow avoiding CO₂eq by producing electricity with the new power plants, instead of the current energy mix.

The above-mentioned studies advise to conclude a set of long-term off-site baseload physical PPAs (see Box 7 below). Specifically, it is estimated that concluding a set of long-term off-site baseload physical wind power PPAs would permit covering more than 60% of CERN's electricity need for the FCC period. Offshore wind has been identified as a key technology for CERN for power supply, to be procured "investment-alike" manner via PPAs that support the development of a new offshore wind park located in France, with a partner who makes the capital investment and carry the construction and operational risks. Adding a solar energy component would permit covering 80% of CERN's electricity need for the FCC period with excess capacity that can be made available to the market.

¹⁰¹ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_22_1511.

¹⁰² https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=PI_COM%3AC%282022%293219&qid=1653033569832.

Box 7: PPA types

Off-site PPA is a contract associated with a utility-scale plant connected to the transmission or distribution network of the country's electricity system to take energy from its point of origin to the consumer point. Off-site PPAs can be further distinguished depending on the delivery point (physical, virtual, sleeved) or how the energy is delivered (as produced, baseload, and consumed). Based on the first categorization, a physical PPA is a contract where the renewable developer sells the renewable energy to an end consumer either directly or through an energy retailer, which supplies the energy from the renewable asset. Missing energy is supplied from the retailer's generation portfolio. At the end of the month, the consumer receives a single bill for all its consumption, whether from the dedicated RE installation under the PPA or other resources of the developer under the PPA or at the sports market.

Based on the second categorization, the baseload PPA is a contract where the renewable developers convert the gross generation from the plant into a duration-based pre-defined volume (e.g. yearly) called baseload. The consumer agrees to buy a total volume of energy over a period spanning typically several years. Profile and volume risks are with the seller, who may be the developer or an intermediary entity. If the seller cannot meet its obligations through its plants, the agreed volume will be sourced from the spot market.

Source: Authors based on Renewable Energy Supply Feasibility Analysis

Different socio-economic benefits would be generated. At a macro-level, this investment would contribute to the European energy transition by increasing the renewable energy availability and use in Europe, reducing CO₂ equivalent emissions, and improving long-term price stability. This is in line with the EU objective of reaching an energy mix composed of 45% of renewable energy sources by 2030. Moreover, the construction and operation of the wind farm would impact on employment, with cascade effects on local consumption.

For this analysis, two specific benefits directly attributed to the FCC-ee programme are estimated:

- Socio-economic value of the residual overcapacity produced by the new renewable energy sources made available to society.
- The CO₂ eq. avoided by producing electricity with the new power plant, instead of the current energy mix.

The specific steps followed for the benefit estimation are summarised in what follows. For simplicity reasons, the text speaks about a "wind farm" or "power plant". However, in an actual situation with multiple PPAs, the build-up of renewable energy sources can be distributed over multiple locations and by several energy suppliers.

Estimation

➤ STEP 1 – Quantifying CERN energy needs

The total energy needs for CERN and FCC-ee have been estimated for the 15 years of FCC-ee operation, as shown in Table 68. In total, CERN will use 28.5 TWh of energy, 22.25 TWh of which will be used by FCC-ee only, corresponding to a share that goes from 55% (in the year when FCC-ee is shut down for upgrades) to 77% in the last years of operation at maximum energy capacity.

For the purpose of this analysis, it is assumed that, in the baseline scenario, CERN and the FCC-ee will be supplied with 80% of their electricity needed from a mix of renewable sources (specifically, 60% from offshore wind and 20% from solar PV). In the best-case scenario, this percentage would increase to 95%, while in the worst-case scenario, it would decrease to 60% (only offshore wind).

Since the particle collider is characterised by a varying operation pattern throughout the year and over its fifteen years of operation, CERN will be able to make a portion of its originally contracted offshore wind capacity from PPAs available to society. Moreover, since renewables are not available all the time, it will need to buy some additional energy from the market. The grid would still be necessary for some hours when CERN's demand is higher than the contracted renewable power production.

Table 68: Amount of energy used for CERN or FCC-ee only, either sold to the market or bought from the market (baseline scenario).

	Total energy used by CERN (TWh)	Energy fraction used by FCC-ee (%)	Total energy used for FCC-ee (TWh)	Energy bought from PPA for FCC-ee (TWh)	Energy bought from the market for FCC-ee (TWh)	Energy sold to the market by FCC-ee (TWh)
Z pole year 1	1.56	71%	1.1	0.9	0.2	0.6
Z pole year 2	1.56	71%	1.1	0.9	0.2	0.6
Z pole year 3	1.56	71%	1.1	0.9	0.2	0.6
Z pole year 4	1.56	71%	1.1	0.9	0.2	0.6
WW year 1	1.90	68%	1.3	1.0	0.3	0.7
WW year 2	1.90	68%	1.3	1.0	0.3	0.7
HZ year 1	2.00	75%	1.5	1.2	0.3	0.9
HZ year 2	2.00	75%	1.5	1.2	0.3	0.9
HZ year 3	2.00	75%	1.5	1.2	0.3	0.9
Upgrade (1y)	1.01	55%	0.55	0.4	0.1	0.3
Top year 1	2.30	77%	1.77	1.4	0.4	1.0
Top year 2	2.30	77%	1.77	1.4	0.4	1.0
Top year 3	2.30	77%	1.77	1.4	0.4	1.0
Top year 4	2.30	77%	1.77	1.4	0.4	1.0
Top year 5	2.30	77%	1.77	1.4	0.4	1.0
Sub-total	28.55	-	20.90	16.72	4.18	12.14
Other phases*	Na	-	1.80	1.40	0.35	Na
Total	Na	-	22.65	18.12	4.53	Na

Note: * Transition phase (2046 and 2047) and analysis phase (2063 and 2064). **Source:** Authors based on McKinsey study but re-scaled to match the latest data on electricity consumption made available by the FCC study management.

In the baseline scenario, the baseload of offshore wind production available to society would amount to approximately 1.4 TWh per year (see Table 69 below). The assumption is that this additional offshore wind production capacity will become available to society earlier than it would in the absence of CERN PPAs for the FCC-ee project. However, this benefit is limited to five years (from 2046 to 2050), as the energy mix is anyway expected to evolve by 2050 to meet the climate neutrality objective.

Table 69: Baseload for CERN or FCC-ee and for the society - Baseline scenario

	Unit	Value
Baseload for CERN per year	%	60%
Baseload for the society per year	%	40%
Baseload for CERN per year	TWh	2.1
Baseload for the society per year	TWh	1.4

Source: Authors based on material received from the FCC study management

In the worst-case scenario, the baseload values remain the same as in the baseline because the expected shares of offshore wind used by CERN and made available to society do not change. In the best-case scenario, the share of offshore wind used by CERN increases (from 60% to 75%), reducing the baseload available to society.

The fact that society will have access to excess offshore wind capacity from CERN will also help avoid CO₂eq emissions by producing electricity with the new power plants rather than relying on the current energy mix. To quantify the emissions saved, the following GHG intensity factors were used:

 Table 70: CO₂eq intensity factors

	Value (G CO ₂ EQ/KWH)	Source
GHG intensity of electricity generation (EU27)	203	European Environment Agency
GHG intensity of electricity generation (France)	58.0	Ademe Base Carbone (and annual decrease of 4% used for the calculation of CO ₂)
GHG emissions estimates for offshore wind power (France)	15.6	Ademe Base Carbone

Source: Authors based on cited sources

➤ STEP 2 – Monetisation

The socio-economic value of the energy produced and made available to society can be valued using the **Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE)**, which is a commonly used metric that calculates the average cost of generating one unit of electricity over the lifetime of a generation asset, accounting for capital, operation, maintenance, and fuel costs.¹⁰³ It is expressed in terms of cost per unit of energy produced (e.g., EUR/MWh). Although LCOE is a well-developed and standard technique in evaluating energy sector economics, authors (see Box 8 on different sources for LCOE) approach model formulation in various ways, leading to significant variations in the reported figures.

¹⁰³ The LCOE does not take into account the specific territorial conditions of electricity production: in particular the significant French state subsidies to offshore wind farms. The result of the benefit is therefore overestimated.

Box 8: LCOE sources

There are many organisations that estimate LCOE values on an annual basis; a few of them are:

- BNEF analyses LCOE for the different power generation technologies
- Lazard determines the LCOE of all technologies in the power sector of the USA
- IRENA estimates the renewable power generation costs across the world on a periodic basis.
- IEA, as part of its annual flagship report, World Energy Outlook (WEO), has long-term projections of LCOE up to 2050 for the different power generation technologies.

Furthermore, various government organisations have developed LCOE models customised for their respective countries, such as the US LCOE model by the Department of Energy (DOE)¹⁰⁴ and the UK Government’s electricity costs model developed by the Department of Energy and Climate Change (DECC), amongst many others.

In France, RTE¹⁰⁵ recently studied the evolution of average costs for future renewable energy installations in the country.

Source: Authors

For the purpose of this study, the LCOE values from the RTE study¹⁰⁶ were primarily considered and supplemented with values from the International Energy Agency (IEA) and a European Commission study¹⁰⁷. The following table summarises the values.

Table 71: LCOE values

Technology	Share in the total French energy production	LCOE (EUR/MWH)
Offshore wind	0.5%	40*
Onshore wind	9.8%	40*
Solar photovoltaic	4.4%	30*
Nuclear	64.8%	65*
Thermique fossile	6.6%	100
Thermique renouvelable et déchets	6.6%	100
Hydraulique	11.9%	100
France electricity mix		68

Source: Authors. **Note:** * Average values from RTE (2022) Futurs énergétiques 2050.

For the CO₂ savings, the most recent estimate of the socio-economic value of one unit CO₂eq is provided by the European Commission (2021) Vademecum for the economic appraisal¹⁰⁸. One ton of CO₂eq has a value of 148 EUR in 2024 (expressed in 2016 prices), equivalent to 144 CHF, increasing over time to reflect the increasing marginal cost for society from the production of an additional emission unit. By 2050, it is estimated

¹⁰⁴ NREL (<https://www.nrel.gov/>) is a national laboratory of the U.S. Department of Energy. Among other things, it provides an online Levelized Cost of Energy Calculator: <https://www.nrel.gov/analysis/tech-lcoe.html>.

¹⁰⁵ See RTE (2022)

¹⁰⁶ Ibidem.

¹⁰⁷ See Trinomics 2020

¹⁰⁸ The French value (available in the 2020 *Complément opérationnel D* of the *Guide de l'évaluation socioéconomique des investissements publics* by France Stratégie) was also considered. However, we opted to use the more recent estimates from the EIB. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that the two sets of estimates are similar. For reference on the French values estimated in 2019 by the commission chaired by Alain Quinet, see France Stratégie (2019).

at 800 EUR/ton (expressed in 2016 prices), equivalent to 777 CHF/ton. This value is then assumed to remain constant until the end of the time horizon.

By adjusting the 2016 prices with the GDP deflator, one ton of CO₂eq has a value of 192 EUR in 2024 (expressed in 2024 prices), equivalent to 183 CHF. By 2050, it is estimated at 1,037 EUR/ton (expressed in 2024 prices), equivalent to 988 CHF/ton.

Results

The first part of the benefit is calculated by multiplying the amount of electricity supplied by CERN to the market by the difference between the estimated LCOE of the French grid electricity mix and the LCOE of the electricity provided by CERN. The second part of the benefit is calculated by multiplying the value of a ton of CO₂eq by the difference between the estimated CO₂eq emissions associated with the grid electricity mix and the CO₂eq emission associated with the offshore wind baseload electricity made available by CERN to society. This benefit would span from 2046 to 2050, i.e. the 5 years of operation until 2050.

In the baseline scenario, the total undiscounted benefit for society is 227.1 million CHF. The discounted value is 117.3 million CHF. The largest portion of this benefit (85%) arises from the first component, i.e. the availability of electricity for society at a lower LCOE compared to the LCOE of the French grid electricity mix. Considering the best-case and worst-case scenarios regarding the share of RES used by FCC-ee, the benefit under consideration ranges from 227.1 to 194.5 million CHF (or from 117.3 to 100.4 million CHF in discounted values). In the worst-case scenario, the values remain the same as in the baseline because the expected shares of offshore wind used by CERN and made available to society do not change. In the best-case scenario, the share of offshore wind used by CERN increases, reducing the baseload available to society and thus shrinking the benefit.

Table 72: Total estimation - under different scenarios (CHF, 2024).

Scenario	Not discounted	Discounted
Baseline	227,136,998	117,281,244
Best-case scenario*	194,461,203	100,385,959
Worst-case scenario*	227,136,998	117,281,244

Note:* These scenarios refer to the share of offshore wind used by CERN. If it increases (as in the best-case scenario), the baseload available to society decreases, thus shrinking the benefit. **Source:** Authors.

5.3. SUPPLY OF WASTE HEAT

Introduction

A large part of the energy used to operate the particle collider and its experiments is converted into heat. The heat is dissipated via water-based cooling systems that connect to evaporation towers. A study has been conducted to prove the feasibility of recovering and re-using waste heat. The idea is that the recovered waste heat will be supplied via district heating networks to consumers in the vicinity of the FCC-ee sites. The benefit considered in this section is the avoided cost of purchasing energy for heating from conventional energy sources such as oil, wood, gas and electricity, thanks to the fact that the price of the heat supplied by the CERN sources is lower than the one produced by conventional energy sources. The environmental benefits associated with the reuse of heat are discussed in Section 5.4.

It is worth noting that the reuse of waste heat also results in slight energy and water savings compared to a scenario without such a system (see

Box 9 below). However, these savings are already factored into the quantities of energy and water considered in the analysis, as well as their associated costs. Since the counterfactual scenario in the analysis assumes the absence of an FCC altogether, the energy and water savings from the reuse of waste heat do not generate a net benefit but rather contribute to a reduced cost for energy and water.

Box 9: Energy and water savings due to waste heat re-use

In particle accelerators, cooling systems use large amounts of water to dissipate the heat generated by equipment. This water is often evaporated in cooling towers, leading to significant water consumption. However, by distributing waste heat for other uses, such as heating nearby buildings or industrial processes, less water is needed for cooling. This reduction in evaporation helps save water, which was estimated by experts at CERN to be approximately 1.6 cubic meters of water being saved per megawatt-hour (MWh) of heat distributed.

Moreover, by distributing waste heat for other uses, some cooling towers will no longer be needed or will operate at reduced capacity. This reduces the energy consumption associated with cooling, as less energy will be required to run these systems. The experts at CERN have estimated that the energy savings might be around 4,000 MWh on average per year. It is considered to be 0 for the long shutdown year.

Source: Authors

Estimation

➤ STEP 1 – Estimation of the amount of waste heat available

The table below shows the waste heat capacities per year from the various sources in the FCC-ee machine (magnets, alcores, absorbers, experiments, power convertors, RF, cryogenics, general services, and chilled water). The total anticipated heat production varies from approximately 830 GWh during the operational Z phase to about 1,600 GWh during the operational tt phase (excluding the long shutdown phase). Based on these assumptions, a significant amount of heat can be recovered, particularly at the PH site in Cercier/Marlioz, France, due to the presence of the superconducting radiofrequency particle acceleration system. In contrast, the potential is relatively lower for the PB (Presinge/Choulex) and PF (Eteaux/La Roche-sur-Foron) sites.

Table 73: Waste heat production per year and per FCC-ee operational phase (MWh).

Beam energy	45.6 GEV	80 GEV	120 GEV	182.5 GEV
Operation mode	Z	W	H	tt
Heat energy produced	MWh	MWh	MWh	MWh
Site PA	137,898	151,852	172,485	225,289
Site PB	14,890	17,726	22,788	34,419
Site PD	137,898	151,852	172,485	225,289
Site PF	14,890	17,726	22,788	34,419
Site PG	137,898	151,852	172,485	225,289
Site PH	229,602	313,584	335,949	523,762
Site PJ	137,898	151,852	172,485	225,289
Site PL	24,894	48,215	56,380	109,157
Total per year	835,868	1,004,659	1,127,845	1,602,913

Source: FCC study management, 2024

➤ **STEP 2 – Estimation of demand for waste heat**

FCC-ee can provide waste heat during the year, mainly during its operation. Potential consumers have been identified within a 5 km radius. The estimated yearly potential waste heat consumption has been distributed over the FCC-ee lifetime, assuming a different consumption potential over the different operation phases of the FCC-ee project, as detailed in the Table below.

Table 74: Waste heat quantity and potential consumption by FCC-ee phase and site (GWh/year)

Mode		Z			W			H			tt		
Baseline													
Site	Qty	Potential Consum.	%	Qty	Potential Consum.	%	Qty	Potential Consum.	%	Qty	Potential Consum.	%	
PA	137.9	137.9	100	151.9	150.0	100	172.5	169.0	98	225.3	212.0	94	
PB	14.9	14.9	100	17.7	17.7	100	22.8	22.8	100	34.4	34.0	99	
PD	137.9	45.0	32	151.9	46.0	30	172.5	46.0	26	225.3	49.0	22	
PF	14.9	14.9	100	17.7	17.0	96	22.8	21.0	92	34.4	29.0	84	
PG	137.9	40.0	29	151.9	40.0	26	172.5	40.0	23	225.3	40.0	18	
PH	229.6	6.0	3	313.6	6.0	2	335.9	6.0	2	523.8	7.0	1	
PJ	137.9	20.0	15	151.9	20.0	13	172.5	20.0	12	225.3	20.0	9	
PL	24.9	19.0	76	48.2	30.0	62	56.4	32.0	57	109.2	33.0	30	
Total	835.8	297.8	36	1004.8	326.7	32	1128	356.8	32	1603	424.0	26	
Worst-case scenario													
Site	Qty	Potential Consum.	%	Qty	Potential Consum.	%	Qty	Potential Consum.	%	Qty	Potential Consum.	%	
PA	137.9	122.0	87	151.9	130.0	86	172.5	139.0	81	225.3	161.0	71	
PB	14.9	14.9	100	17.7	17.7	100	22.8	23.0	100	34.4	34.0	99	
PD	137.9	25.0	10	151.9	26.0	11	172.5	26.0	15	225.3	26.0	12	
PF	14.9	12.0	80	17.7	13.0	73	22.8	15.0	66	34.4	19.0	55	
PG	137.9	23.0	17	151.9	24.0	16	172.5	24.0	14	225.3	24.0	11	
PH	229.6	6.0	3	313.6	6.0	2	335.9	6.0	2	523.8	7.0	1	
PJ	137.9	11.0	8	151.9	12.0	8	172.5	12.0	7	225.3	13.0	58	
PL	24.9	9.0	36	48.2	10.0	21	56.4	11.0	20	109.2	11.0	10	
Total	835.8	222.9	27	1,004.8	238.7	24	1128	256.0	23	1,603	295.0	18	
Best-case scenario													
Site	Qty	Potential Consum.	%	Qty	Potential Consum.	%	Qty	Potential Consum.	%	Qty	Potential Consum.	%	
PA	137.9	162.8	122	151.9	200.1	131	172.5	228.8	132	225.3	334.4	148	
PB	14.9	152.8	1025	17.7	169.6	958	22.8	195.3	856	34.4	259.7	755	
PD	137.9	-	-	151.9	-	-	172.5	-	-	225.3	-	-	
PF	14.9	15.0	100	17.7	17.0	100	22.8	21.07	92	34.4	29.0	84	
PG	137.9	40.0	29	151.9	40.0	26	172.5	40.0	23	225.3	40.0	18	
PH	229.6	-	-	313.6	-	?	335.9	-	-	523.8	-	-	
PJ	137.9	20.0	15	151.9	20.0	13	172.5	20.0	12	225.3	20.0	9	
PL	24.9	-	-	48.2	-	-	56.4	-	-	109.2	-	-	

Total	835.8	390.6	47	1004.8	446.6	44	1128	505.1	45	1603	683.2	43
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Source: CERN communication and Ginger-Burgeap, 2024

➤ STEP 3 - Estimation of the avoided cost

The cost for the supply of waste heat in a district for heating and air conditioning (cooling) purposes (C) is given by the cost for the service (S) and the cost of energy (E): $C = S + E$. These components depend on the mix of sources used to obtain heat (gas, electricity, etc.). More specifically:

- S includes transport and distribution costs, management costs (investment and operation costs), marketing costs and the supplier's earnings margin.
- E is the cost of energy.

The table below shows the cost of waste heat considering the heating (and cooling) cost per year of an apartment between 50 and 100 m² in the region around CERN. The typical heating consumption for a 50 m² apartment is 6 MWh per year, so the working hypothesis is a consumption per year of 10 MWh per year per apartment/household. It compares the costs in three cases:

- Heat is distributed via a network fuelled by gas.
- Heat is distributed via a network fuelled by electricity.
- Heat is distributed via a network using the FCC-ee waste heat.

Table 75: Cost for the supply of waste heat and avoided cost (EUR/MWh and CHF/MWh).

	Cost of the service (S)	Cost of energy (E)	Total cost (EUR/MWH)	Note
Gas	26	103	129	
Electricity	129*	219	219	*It is assumed that the cost of the service does not apply since every household typically has a general electricity supply contract, even if the electricity is not used for heating purposes.
FCC-ee waste heat	108	2*	110	*As regards the cost of energy, CERN only receives 2 EUR/MWh from the heat network operator to compensate for the creation of the infrastructure to supply heat within CERN premises.
Avoided costs		EUR/MWH	CHF/MWH	Note
FCC waste heat vs. gas		19	18	
FCC waste heat vs. electricity		109	104	
FCC waste heat vs. a mix of gas and electricity		64	61	A simple average between the gas and electricity prices is considered.

Source: CERN communication and Ginger-Burgeap, 2024.

Costs can vary according to conventional energy prices and network investment and operating costs.

Results

When multiplying the avoided cost from using the CERN waste heat as compared to the mix of gas and electricity with the yearly demand in the baseline scenario, a total of 312.6 million CHF of benefit is estimated

over the project time horizon, corresponding to 131.9 million CHF in discounted terms. In the worst-case scenario, the discounted value decreases to 95.4 million CHF, while in the best-case scenario, it increases to 264.0 million CHF.

Table 76: Total estimation – under different scenarios (CHF, 2024).

Scenario	Not discounted	Discounted
Baseline	312,578,794	131,944,519
Worst-case scenario	225,392,886	95,445,971
Best-case scenario	456,574,149	190,831,249

Source: Authors

5.4. SAVINGS OF GHG EMISSIONS DUE TO HEAT RECOVERY

Introduction

A large part of the energy used to operate the particle collider and its experiments is converted into heat. Traditionally, the heat is dissipated via water-based cooling systems that connect to evaporation towers. A study has been conducted to prove the feasibility of recovering and re-using waste heat. The idea is that the recovered waste heat will be supplied via district heating networks to consumers in the vicinity of the FCC-ee sites. The environmental benefit stems from the fact that the energy used by the FCC research infrastructure is re-used and supplied for heating and cooling purposes, avoiding the use of alternative, mainly non-renewable, sources with higher carbon intensity such as gas, wood, oil and conventional electricity mix. Accordingly, the benefit is calculated as the difference between the value of GHG emissions produced by the mix of energy used for heating and cooling purposes in the CERN region and the (lower) GHG emissions in the scenario of the CERN waste heat.

Estimation

➤ STEP 1 – Quantifying the volumes of CO₂eq savings using FCC waste heat

The table below shows the carbon intensity of the current energy mix used to produce heat in the region around CERN. It is, on average, 186.7 gCO₂e/KWh. A 4% annual reduction in the carbon intensity of the energy mix is envisaged starting in 2025, in line with France's objective of achieving carbon neutrality by 2050. As a result, the grid's carbon intensity is projected to reach approximately 70 gCO₂e/KWh by 2048 and around 40 gCO₂e/KWh by 2062, the period during which the waste heat is expected to be recovered. The expected carbon intensity of the energy mix for heat production with the FCC is approximately 18 gCO₂e/kWh in the baseline scenario, 17 gCO₂e/kWh in the best-case scenario, and 22 gCO₂e/kWh in the worst-case scenario. The hypotheses on the electricity mix used by FCC are explained in Section 3.2.1.

Table 77: CO₂(eq) intensity for alternative heating systems.

Heating system	gCO ₂ eq/KWH	Weight in the energy mix	Weighted CO ₂ eq per year gCO ₂ eq/KWH
Electrical heating	147	0.36	52.9
Gas heating	227	0.34	77.2
Oil heating	324	0.16	51.8
Wood (renewable)	30	0.11	3.3
Heat pump	49	0.03	1.5
Total		1.00	186.7

Note: Calculation based on ADEME, Carbone 4 and Pays de Gex Agglomeration. **Source:** Authors

The waste heat supplied as a result of the FCC operation sourced from sustainable energy sources is presented in Section 5.3. Specifically, the estimated yearly potential waste heat consumption in the vicinity of the FCC-ee sites over the FCC-ee lifetime, assuming a different consumption potential over the different operation phases of the FCC-ee project, is detailed in Table 13.

The table below shows the CO₂eq savings from using the FCC waste heat to produce energy as compared to using the current energy mix used to produce heat in the region around CERN. The reduced carbon footprint is calculated for the FCC-ee operational phase only.

 Table 78: Volumes of CO₂eq savings using FCC waste heat over the operational phase (tons CO₂eq).

Scenario related heat to supply	Scenario related to electricity production		
	Baseline	Best-case	Worst-case
Baseline	173,563	178,318	156,194
Best-case	247,875	254,804	222,525
Worst-case	126,058	129,490	113,529

Source: Authors

➤ STEP 2 – Monetisation

The most recent estimate of the socio-economic value of one unit CO₂eq is provided by the European Commission (2021) Vademecum for the economic appraisal¹⁰⁹. One ton of CO₂eq has a value of 148 EUR in 2024 (expressed in 2016 prices), equivalent to 144 CHF, increasing over time to reflect the increasing marginal cost for society from the production of an additional emission unit. By 2050, it is estimated at 800 EUR/ton (expressed in 2016 prices), equivalent to 777 CHF/ton. This value is then assumed to remain constant until the end of the time horizon.

¹⁰⁹ The French value (available in the 2020 *Complément opérationnel D* of the *Guide de l'évaluation socioéconomique des investissements publics* by France Stratégie) was also considered. However, we opted to use the more recent estimates from the EIB. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that the two sets of estimates are similar. For reference on the French values estimated in 2019 by the commission chaired by Alain Quinet, see France Stratégie (2019).

By adjusting the 2016 prices with the GDP deflator, one ton of CO₂eq has a value of 192 EUR in 2024 (expressed in 2024 prices), equivalent to 183 CHF. By 2050, it is estimated at 1,037 EUR/ton (expressed in 2024 prices), equivalent to 988 CHF/ton.

Results

The environmental benefit of waste heat reuse is derived from the avoided GHG emissions in the project scenario, where CERN supplies waste heat—produced using a cleaner electricity mix—to district heating networks serving consumers near the FCC-ee sites. This is compared to the emissions from alternative heating and cooling methods typically used in the CERN region. Consistently with the negative externality of GHG emissions, the French energy mix is considered in the baseline scenario. **The total benefit is estimated at 169.9 million CHF (undiscounted), corresponding to 74.1 million CHF after discounting.** In the worst-case scenario, the discounted value decreases to 53.9 million CHF, while in the best-case scenario, it remains about 104.9 million CHF.

Table 79: Total estimation - under different scenarios (CHF, 2024).

Scenario	Not discounted	Discounted
Baseline	169,958,795	74,056,432
Worst-case	123,405,629	53,931,023
Best-case	242,909,285	104,866,449

Source: Authors

5.5. BENEFITS REWILDING (HABITATS AND BIODIVERSITY)

Introduction

Along with the construction of necessary infrastructure (buildings, roads) for the FCC, CERN also foresees the implementation of mitigation actions. These action aims to generate positive externalities to compensate for the negative ones associated with the construction of the FCC-ee (presented in Section 3.2.5). The planned **mitigation actions** (to date) include:

- Creation of green buffers next to the project site with tree planting (15.2 hectares) and meadow creation (6.8 hectares). Data refers to the optimized scenario described in Table 24.
- Improvement and preservation of wetlands within the project's reserved area (7.8 hectares).
- Re-creation of agricultural areas to other locations out of the project's reserved area, in sites to be indicated by host state notified bodies.

The list of mitigation actions is not fully defined, as the implementation of the Avoid-Reduce-Compensate (ERC) approach that requires a goal of ecological equivalence (=biodiversity gains at least equal to the biodiversity losses caused by the project) is still ongoing, and it might require additionally environmentally positive measures to be implemented.

Estimation

➤ STEP 1 – Quantification

The analysis focuses on the most significant expected change in ecosystem services caused by the project's interventions, setting aside the mitigating interventions where the impacted land is relatively small or where the

marginal increase in the value of ecosystem services is negligible or difficult to determine¹¹⁰. Therefore, the focus is placed on the 7.8 ha of re-naturalization area designated for targeted wetland improvement actions.

➤ STEP 2 – Monetisation

The monetisation of ecosystem services gains was conducted by taking the difference of the value of regulating and ecosystem service retrieved from the ESVD database¹¹¹ for wetlands compared to intensive use land/cropland. Regulating and supporting services considered for wetlands include air quality regulation, climate regulation/C-sequestration and moderation of extreme events.

The total regulating & habitat service gain from re-naturalization activities was estimated at 1,582 EUR/ha/year.

Table 80: Regulating & habitat services gain of wetland improvement (EUR/ha/year)

Ecosystem	Unit of measure	Value
Inland Wetlands	EUR/ha/year	2,156
Intensive use land/cropland	EUR/ha/year	574
Difference	EUR/ha/year	1,582

Source: Authors based on ESVD data

As mentioned in the case of ecosystem services loss (see Section 3.2.5), the monetization of these services should be interpreted with prudence, as demonstrated by the high variabilities of metrics from literature and case studies.

Results

The total benefits from ecosystem services gained thanks to re-naturalization activities is estimated at 388,002 CHF undiscounted, equalling **206,971 CHF discounted**, obtained by multiplying the EUR 1,582 ecosystem services gain to the total hectares impacted by re-naturalization activities starting from the year 2032, assuming that these activities are conducted in parallel with construction works.

Table 81: Total estimation - Baseline Scenario (CHF).

Scenario	Not discounted	Discounted
Baseline	388,002	206,971

Source: Authors

5.6. VALUE OF CONTRIBUTION TO REGIONAL EMERGENCY SERVICES

Introduction

A larger accelerator like the FCC requires a new emergency preparedness and intervention framework supported by infrastructure at both underground and surface levels. As part of this safety concept, the transition of emergency and fire brigade services from CERN to a financial and training support scheme with regional services is planned. The plan foresees a small core team of leading firefighting experts at CERN that cooperate

¹¹⁰ E.g. The tree planted area was discarded as the average metrics available from the ESVD database for temperate forest are hardly applicable to newly planted tree area, assuming that its biodiversity services content will not be the same, especially until trees are not grown

¹¹¹ See Chapter 5 for additional details on ESVD database

with a number of firefighting and emergency services in the vicinity of some major FCC surface sites. The FCC project would co-fund these services through local employment of highly skilled professional firefighters, organisation and funding of continuous training and exercises, support of materials and central intervention coordination.

The core team of officers and leading experts at CERN would comprise up to 10 emergency intervention and firefighting experts. Up to 5 emergency and firefighting service stations in the vicinity of FCC surface sites would be co-funded by FCC with up to a total of 50 firefighters and emergency intervention experts and with annual investments in materials in France. These costs are already included in the FCC operation expenditure estimates. These co-funded personnel would strengthen the existing number of firefighting and emergency service personnel in the Ain and Haute Savoie personnel. Due to the very limited number of necessary interventions at FCC sites, these personnel would for the majority of the time generate benefits for the emergency and firefighting capacity of the region.

In response to local department requests, these activities are expected to involve a total commitment of 1,925 person-years from 2029 until the end of decommissioning in 2069.

Estimation

The economic value of firefighters in the region is estimated by multiplying the number of personnel by the yearly value of one firefighter, calculated using the hourly rate of voluntary work (€35.61 in 2021 prices) and the average annual intervention hours (91). This results in an approximate total of €7 million (undiscounted). Additionally, the cost of materials—including vehicles, heavy transport, equipment, and training—is estimated at €32 million (undiscounted) over the same period.

After converting and discounting these values to reflect current prices, the final figures are expressed in CHF (see table below).

Table 82: Total estimation – Baseline Scenario (CHF).

Scenario	Not discounted	Discounted
Baseline	30,132,367	15,777,497

Source: Authors

5.7. OTHER ICT BENEFITS

Exploratory estimates were carried out between 2022 and 2024 to quantify the benefits of ICT developments related to open information platforms and collaborative web services. Existing platforms, specifically Zenodo and Indico (see Box 10 below), were used as illustrative examples for this estimation. We discuss below if and to what extent FCC-ee might be instrumental in such developments.

Box 10: Examples of existing ICT platforms

Zenodo is a general-purpose open repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. It enables researchers to deposit research papers, datasets, research software, reports, and any other research-related digital artefacts. For each submission, a persistent digital object identifier (DOI) is minted, ensuring that the stored items are easily citable. Launched on 8 May 2013, Zenodo succeeded the OpenAIRE Orphan Records Repository, providing researchers in any subject area with a platform to comply with open science deposit requirements, particularly in the absence of an institutional repository. It is run with Invenio (a free software framework for large-scale digital repositories), developed by CERN for building digital repositories and content management systems. Zenodo platform has been fully integrated into the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) portal, serving as a unified European access point to research data, tools, and services for researchers and businesses across Europe. For CERN's internal purposes, a separate service called the "CERN Document Server" (CDS) is deployed and operated, based on Invenio technology. The CDS serves as a digital repository for CERN's research outputs, providing easy access to documents, publications, and other scholarly content created by CERN's researchers.

Indico is a collaborative Web service to manage events of all kinds and sizes. This includes personal meetings (such as working group meetings, workshops and conferences) as well as training events and visits. The system includes planning, agenda, invitations, registrations, payments, document archive (presentations and materials), minutes, integration with video conferencing tools and in-room video conferencing systems, attendant feedback and an ever-growing portfolio of additional functions that are added on an as-needed basis. The system has been developed and one service is operated by CERN for a worldwide user community of more than 15,000 people. This tool is used by other organisations such as the United Nations headquarter and research institutions worldwide. It serves as a typical example of a tool that global collaborations require.

Source: Authors

Both platforms are developed by different organizations, including CERN, with various collaborators involved. Competitors in the market (e.g., Whova and EventBrite for Indico, or Figshare and Dryad for Zenodo) have different architectures and are usually available for a fee. Comparisons are not easy and it seems challenging to specifically attribute to FCC-ee the development of similar software in the next two decades. Additionally, the rapid evolution of ICT warrants caution in their inclusion in the quantitative estimates presented in Chapter 4. Despite this, an attempt to guess their benefits is discussed in the following section, should further in-depth analysis be necessary.

5.7.1. Benefits from the development of a new digital open information platform

According to information collected through interviews at the CERN IT department and Library service in 2020, there is strong interest by users and need to reinforce the existing open information platform, such as Zenodo (see Box 10 above).

An econometric model has been developed by Crespo Garrido et al. (2023) to estimate the socio-economic impact of a new centralized virtual repository, which will serve the data storage and usage needs of FCC-ee in the future. The value of this repository is estimated as the sum of the present value of measurable benefits it generates, net of the present value of its development and maintenance costs

Three types of benefits were identified and evaluated:

- **Data storage:** An open Access virtual repository allows researchers to deposit any document in digital format, from articles to software, data and metadata free of charge, in principle without size limitations.
- **Online usage:** The impact of using the open-access repository via its web interface is reflected by the time spent by unique visitors on the platform for finding, accessing and reading information.
- **Downloads:** It reflects the impact of accessing information hosted in the repository through the downloads of documents and associated data. This benefit adds to the value for online usage: in addition to searching and exploring data in the online platform, users can decide to download them. Downloads are positively correlated with the probability of reusing the scientific material. Such a service is not

obvious, as for instance the widely popular US National Library of Medicine MEDLINE system shows, where access is limited to abstracts and materials behind paywalls (e.g established by journal publishers to protect copyright).

Historical data related to Zenodo were taken as a reference for the estimation of future benefits associated with the development of a new digital open information platform. In addition, a survey was launched in 2022 to elucidate the “common value” of the Zenodo virtual repository. The survey results were used to verify and refine the model of the value of open science repositories as a common good for society.

The steps and key data used to estimate the benefit are summarised in Table 83. Values have been updated in the framework of revisions carried out in 2025.

Table 83: Steps and main parameters to estimate the value of a new digital open information platform.

Step	Description	Key parameters
1	Cost estimation of the new platform	4% annual growth rate of costs from 2024 to 2064.
2	Estimation of the benefit of data storage	10% annual increase in the number of files of less than 50 GB from 2028 to 2040; 3% annual increase for files larger than 50 GB. Value of each document below 50 GB: 106.4 CHF. Value of each document larger than 50 GB 150.8 CHF.
3	Estimation of the benefit of online usage	10% annual increase in the number of unique web users from 2022 to 2040; 0% growth rate after 2040. Average time spent by a unique user on the platform: 4 minutes. Value of time spent on the platform: 0.29 CHF/minute.
4	Estimation of the benefit of downloads	Number of downloads assumed of each stored document: 1. Value of each download: 6.67 CHF.
5	Estimate the total benefit and application of the net present value formula	Social discount rate applied: 2.8% (see Section 2.3.3).

Source: Authors

➤ STEP 1 - Development and maintenance cost

The estimation of the cost of developing the new platform is based on the historical costs related to the development and maintenance of Zenodo. **In total, just 3.2 million CHF have been spent between 2012 and 2023 for Zenodo, with an average of 264,000 CHF per year.** The creation of a virtual repository entails an initial investment peak at the beginning of its development, and then the annual expenditure stabilises and only the salary of people involved in its maintenance and further improvements has an influence on costs. For the sake of simplicity, a 4% linear annual growth has been assumed for the future years. **A total additional cost of 25 million CHF** (13 million CHF in discounted terms) is estimated **for the period 2028-2064.**

The software product used for the Zenodo deployment, called Invenio has also been used by at least 39 additional institutions and nations worldwide, beyond CERN (e.g. Inspire).¹¹² Institutions using Invenio as a basis for developing their own data repositories enjoyed a benefit consisting of the avoided cost of development. Without the fully integrated library system provided by Invenio, these other repositories would not exist in the present form, and they would not be integrated worldwide. Since its integration in the EOSC-Hub¹¹³ catalogue of services in 2020, a single portal for European researchers and innovators to discover, access, use and reuse a broad spectrum of resources for data-driven research, access to Zenodo services is expected to further increase. Since there is no way to foresee whether the code developed for a potentially new FCC-related virtual repository

¹¹² <https://inveniosoftware.org/showcase>.

¹¹³ <https://www.eosc-hub.eu/>

will have a similar use outside CERN, **the avoided costs of today roughly 840 million CHF (40 installations times 21 million CHF) by other institutions due to the development of Invenio are not accounted as a benefit for the FCC-ee project.**

➤ **STEP 2 - The value of data storage**

The benefit of data storage reflects the socio-economic value of all files stored in the free virtual repository. Unlike typical free virtual repositories, such as Arxiv¹¹⁴ or IEEE Xplore¹¹⁵, which store documents in text format, Zenodo also stores datasets, software, videos, images, and files in arbitrary formats. **The measurement is based on the market price of Dryad¹¹⁶**, an international open-access non-profit repository of research data, funded by members and data submitters (Beagrie et al. 2010). It is especially used to store data underlying scientific and medical publications (mainly evolutionary biology, genetics, and ecology). Dryad has a price list for data storage, which we used as a reference to establish a monetary value for the new virtual repository. The prices for uploading files to its repository are as follows:

- For less than 50 GB the price is 111.72 EUR (i.e. 106.42 CHF) per document.
- For more than 50 GB it charges 46.55 EUR (i.e. 44.34 CHF) for each additional 10 GB.

The number of files archived was estimated by distinguishing between those lower and higher than 50 GB, by considering the historical data stored in Zenodo between 2014 and 2021.¹¹⁷ It was assumed a 10% annual increase in the number of files of less than 50 GB from 2028 to 2040 and a 3% annual increase for files larger than 50 GB. The total benefit for data storage is estimated by applying the unit costs applied by Dryad to the estimated number of files archived starting from 2028 to 2064 (end of the FCC-ee time horizon). More precisely, each document smaller than 50 GB 106.4 CHF and larger than 50 GB 150.77 CHF (i.e. 106.42 + 44.34 CHF) were valued.

The undiscounted benefit amounts to about 2.4 billion CHF. The discounted benefit is about 1.3 billion CHF.

➤ **STEP 3 - The value of online usage**

The second benefit consists of the online usage of the repository. It is measured as the monetary value of the time spent by unique visitors of the web interface. **The value of web usage is based on Piwik¹¹⁸ statistics.** Piwik is a free and open-source web analytics application used by Zenodo for its metrics. As shown in Table 84 in 2021 over 11.5 million individual web visitors of Zenodo were recorded, each one spending an average of 2 minutes exploring the repository.

¹¹⁴ <https://arxiv.org>

¹¹⁵ <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org>

¹¹⁶ <https://datadryad.org>

¹¹⁷ Precise statistics about Zenodo community sizes do not exist. We have assumed sizes to be up to 50 GB.

¹¹⁸ <https://www.piwik.pro>

Table 84: Number of users and time spent on Zenodo (2013-2021).

Year	Number of unique website visitors	Time spent by all visitors (minutes)	Time spent per visitor (minutes)
2013	4,107	12,528	3
2014	58,548	252,909	4
2015	123,266	514,733	4
2016	251,088	964,550	4
2017	526,591	1,816,950	3
2018	1,296,918	3,524,495	3
2019	2,240,481	6,181,306	3
2020	14,035,544	24,292,827	2
2021	11,560,541	21,197,854	2

Source: Authors data based on Piwik analytics.

For FCC-ee related platform development, it was assumed the same number of web users as for Zenodo in 2021, applying a 10% annual growth rate until 2040 and a stable volume from this point on. The growth rate is based on the growth of users of the IEEE Xplore and Arxiv reported growth rates.

The estimated value of time spent on the platform is 0.29 CHF/minute. It has been derived on the basis of the 2021 average salaries per minute for researchers (professionals and technicians of scientific activities) in all EU countries provided by the Eurostat database. The reliability of these salary data was ensured by cross-checking them with data reported in a recent paper by Morretta et al. (2022) on the value of publications in the field of Earth Observation.

The total undiscounted benefit calculated is about 2.57 billion CHF, considering an average of 4 minutes per visit (which includes the time to search for a document and for the next page to open), an annual increase of 10% until 2040, and a time value of 0.29 CHF/min. The discounted benefit amounts to 1.4 billion CHF.

➤ STEP 4 - The value of downloads

The socio-economic value of downloads reflects the impact of accessing information hosted in the repository through the off-line use of documents and other types of data. Zenodo does neither record the number of downloads per document, nor tracks if a document has been downloaded several times by the same person. For this reason, it was assumed that **each document stored in the repository is downloaded at least once** in its lifetime.

Even if Zenodo, and any future new repository, are free of charge, it was necessary to set a reference monetary value for the downloads of data. The IEEE Xplore digital library and the journal Nature - for which individual subscription fees are publicly available - were taken as examples. IEEE is a non-profit organisation. The purchase price of a research article through an individual subscription is 6.22 EUR in IEEE Xplore and 7.70 EUR in Nature. The average price for these two on-line sources is 6.96 EUR per article. A monetary value of 7 EUR (i.e. 6.67 CHF) was set for each downloaded Zenodo article or dataset.

These values were compared with the results of a survey on the hypothetical willingness to pay of Zenodo users and non-users (see Box 11 below). The survey returned a higher willingness to pay for the possibility of downloading documents from Zenodo. Therefore, the 6.67 CHF previously calculated provides a conservative estimate of the socio-economic value associated with this benefit.

Box 11: Contingent valuation on open science repositories: case study on Zenodo

A contingent valuation of the value of Zenodo as a common good was carried out between January and July 2022. An online survey was launched, which collected answers from 182 respondents from different countries worldwide. Around half of the respondents stated a zero willingness to pay for unlimited data storage on Zenodo or for unlimited access to Zenodo scientific information. These responses were predominantly from CERN employees stating as a reason that Zenodo should not be a paid service. When considering the respondents who are willing to pay at least some money for Zenodo services, it was found:

- An average WTP for data storage of 8.87 EUR per person;
- An average WTP for downloads of 17.34 EUR per person.

An econometric analysis was carried out to analyse the positive responses and investigate the factors that explain the hypothetical willingness to pay (WTP) for Zenodo. It was found that the WTP is not influenced by the type of education, age or other socio-economic characteristics of the respondents, but only by the knowledge of the Zenodo platform: people who know already the Zenodo services are more willing to pay for them.

More details on the survey and its results are presented in Crespo Garrido et al. (2023).

The total annual value of the benefit from downloads was obtained by multiplying the unit value per download and the number of documents stored annually. **The total undiscounted benefit for the period 2028 - 2064 is 147.8 million CHF**, i.e. a discounted value of 78.4 million CHF.

➤ **STEP 5 - Total benefit simulation**

The following table shows the total benefit potentially associated with the development of a new open information platform that would be used by users outside CERN during the FCC programme. It is simulated as the sum of benefits net of costs.

Table 85: Total estimated benefit of a new digital open information platform – Baseline (CHF)

Item	Undiscounted	Discounted
Data Storage benefit	2,359,595,320	1,251,512,710
Online usage benefit	2,571,254,527	1,363,721,816
Downloads benefit	147,807,024	78,394,900
Total benefits	5,078,656,870	2,693,629,426
Cost	25,412,154	12,796,461
Net benefit (total benefit minus cost)	5,053,244,717	2,680,832,966

Source: Authors

5.7.2. Benefits from the development of a new web collaborative service

A new, or significantly upgraded meeting, workshop and conference management tool might be developed to serve the needs of the worldwide collaboration involved in the FCC-ee project.

Differently from the estimation of the benefit of the digital open information platform, the cost of developing and maintaining this new tool was not considered. This cost was considered to be negligible compared to the expected benefits, as also shown for the Zenodo-like software.

A survey was conducted to estimate the hypothetical willingness to pay (WTP) of private users in relation to a synthetic Indico-like product. The steps and main parameters considered for the estimation of the benefit are listed in the Table 86 below.

Table 86: Steps and main parameters to estimate the value of a new web collaborative service

Step	Description	Key parameters
1	Calculation of the number of events organised with the collaboration / management software	Yearly growth rate in the number of events: 20% between 2023-2040; 5% between 2041-2064 Total number of events organised (2028-2064): 13,813,415
2	Estimation of the WTP	Average willingness to pay for each event: 544 CHF
3	Estimate the total benefit and application of the net present value formula	Social discount rate applied: 2.8% (see Section 2.3.3).

Source: Authors

➤ STEP 1 - Number of events

14 organisations (excluding CERN) using Indico were identified in 2022, including the European Space Agency, the EGI foundation, the Square Kilometre Array Observatory (SKAO), the United Nations and others. Historical data on the number of events organised yearly by these organisations through Indico are available. They increased from about 4,100 in 2015 to nearly 10,000 in 2022. These figures were taken as a reference basis to project the number of events expected to be organised in relation to the FCC-ee project. The average annual growth rate in the number of events was 16% in the 2015-2022 period.¹¹⁹ The events organised by CERN and related high-energy physics institutes were not accounted for: the focus was only on the benefit accruing to external institutions who are active in other domains.

For the future, **it was assumed a 20% annual growth rate until 2040, and a 5% growth rate afterwards.** These rates assume a constantly growing number of events organised using collaborative / management software, and a growing number of organisations using this software. **A total of 13.8 million events are expected during the 2028-2064 FCC-ee reference period.** Only events occurring after 2028 are attributed to the new software developed for the FCC-ee project.

➤ STEP 2 - Willingness to pay

A survey was run in 2022 to investigate the willingness to pay for the services offered by the Indico-like tool. Responses were obtained from 2,100 individual adult persons working in private sector companies with more than 50 computers who are users of the conference, workshop, and meeting management software. The countries where the survey was launched were Spain, Italy, France, Germany, the United States, and the United Kingdom. Most respondents use the software in their working life either daily or weekly.

The survey was designed to elicit consumer preferences based on hypothetical markets using a choice experiment method. More details on the survey and the results obtained are presented in Crespo Garrido et al. (2023).

An average willingness to pay for each event of 571 EUR (i.e. 544 CHF) was estimated.

➤ STEP 3 - Total benefit simulation

The socio-economic benefit was estimated by multiplying the number of events recorded every year since 2028 by the average WTP value.

¹¹⁹ Interestingly, no peak of activity was recorded in the 2020-2021 years of the COVID-19 pandemic. On the contrary, the number of events organised declined, due to the slow-down of the research and professional activities. In 2022, the number of events returned to the pre-pandemic levels.

The total undiscounted socio-economic benefit is 7.5 billion CHF for a time period of 30 years (2028-2064). It amounts to an average annual value of 203 million CHF (undiscounted). **The present value of the benefit, after applying the social discount rate of 2.8%, is 3.49 billion CHF.**

A caveat on the valuation of digital platform development is needed: the benefits in terms of WTP seems so high that, in the current panorama of the industry, there would be wide room for commercial supply at competitive price or for free, if there are side profits from attracting users.

5.8. BENEFITS FROM ICT SPIN-OFFS

Every year, persons who have actively participated in the CERN research programmes establish spin-off companies thanks to the knowledge gained and the technologies developed during their work experience at CERN. This socio-economic benefit is different from the industrial spillovers enjoyed by supplier companies and quantified in Section 4.3. It refers to the establishment of new businesses, placing new or improved products and services on the market that would otherwise most likely not exist. Some illustrative examples include, but are not limited to:

- a company serving today over 100 million people and businesses with secure Internet services (e.g. mail, VPN, cloud storage).
- a 4.0 software solutions company active in industrial automation.
- a company active in cutting-edge technologies for education.
- a company providing solutions for air quality data analysis.
- a company supplying imaging solutions for the scientific and industrial market.

The steps followed and main parameters used to tentatively estimate the value of ICT spin-offs are summarised below.

Table 87: Steps and main parameters to estimate the value of ICT spin-offs

Step	Description	Key parameters
1	Estimation of the number of ICT spin-offs	Spin-offs per year from 2031 to 2064: 2 (for a total of 68 over 34 years).
2	Estimation of the market value of spin-offs	Distribution of market value as a function of time (X): Minimum $Y = 446,671 + 8,413,050 \ln(X)$ Average (baseline) $Y = 2,010,020 + 8,329,299 \ln(X)$ Maximum $Y = 4,243,375 + 9,164,574 \ln(X)$ Distribution probability of survival: declining for 10 years after the company establishment (83% after 1 year, 37% after 5 years, etc.) and then stabilising at 20%.
3	Estimate the total benefit and application of the net present value formula	Social discount rate applied: 2.8% (see Section 2.3.3).

Source: Authors

➤ STEP 1 - Number of spin-offs

First, the number of ICT spin-offs expected to be generated during the FCC-ee lifetime was estimated. Since 2015, CERN has recorded 39 spin-off companies operating in the ICT sector. This number was obtained based on a longer list of clients who pay royalties to CERN (source: CERN Knowledge Transfer department, May 2023). The list includes large and small companies, universities, and research institutes. Out of this list, we extracted small and medium companies existing for less than 30 years (larger companies and older ones have been excluded).

Consistently with these historical data, it was assumed that FCC-ee will continue generating **about 2 new spin-off companies each year starting from 2031**, during the design and preparation phase, until the end of the time horizon (2064).

➤ **STEP 2 - Market value**

Second, the socio-economic benefit attributed to the ICT spin-offs was estimated. The benefit is defined on the basis of the current market value of these companies, which is the price a company would have if it were offered for acquisition on a financial market. It is estimated as the present value of future cash streams of the company¹²⁰. The initial market value of the company in its first year of life and the incremental values recorded in the subsequent years were considered.

Such information is available from two proprietary databases: Orbis Zephyr (Bureau van Dijk¹²¹) and Dealroom¹²². The financial data of the 39 relevant companies were retrieved as possible comparators¹²³. Statistics on the annual economic performances of these companies were used to estimate the distribution of market value and the yearly incremental market value over time. Since they are estimated on the basis of a small number of observations, future research is needed for validation.

Figure 46: Distribution of the lower bound, average and upper bound market values of spin-off companies over time and the marginal (incremental) market value per spinoff (CHF)

Source: Authors

Not all spin-offs are likely to survive for a long time. In the EU, the average survival rate of companies in the ICT sector one year after their establishment is 83%; it reduces to 37% after 5 years. The survival curve of newly born enterprises in the ICT sector over a 20-year period was estimated by assuming a gradually declining survival rate approaching 20% in the long term.

¹²⁰ Alternatively, it can be calculated by computing the value of assets and liabilities held by a company. Source: <https://corporatefinanceinstitute.com/resources/valuation/market-value/>

¹²¹ https://www.bvdinfo.com/en-us/our-products/data/greenfield-investment-and-ma/zephyr?gclid=CjwKCAjw-7OIBhB8EiwAnoOEK7nZoe5XNYIzQOHRZkAITYGzeAFFe7FUQbQi0x3XTT_LZuIGx1R9qRoCa4QQAyD_BwE

¹²² <https://dealroom.co/>

¹²³ More specifically, information on the market value was available for 18 companies; information on the total assets was available for 30 companies.

Figure 47: Survival curve of newly born enterprises in the ICT sector – European Union EU 27, 2019

Source: Authors based on Eurostat data for the first 5 years, then own estimates.

The yearly incremental market value was multiplied by the probability of company survival each year to obtain an estimate of the socio-economic benefit expected to be generated by each ICT spin-off.

➤ **STEP 3 - Total benefit estimate**

The total benefit is estimated by applying the distribution of the incremental market value for a period of 20 years to the number of new ICT spin-offs per year (adjusted by the probability of survival). The benefit estimation starts in 2031. The benefit for the last two ICT spin-offs, expected to be established within the FCC-ee time horizon (i.e. in 2064), spans until 2084.

The total undiscounted benefit of the ICT spin-off expected to be generated thanks to the FCC-ee project is estimated to be 831.7 million CHF in the baseline scenario, where the average market value of companies is considered (i.e. 408.6 million CHF discounted at the 2.8% social discount rate). Considering the lower and upper bound market values, a more pessimistic and a more optimistic benefit value is obtained, as shown in the table below. These figures are not to be considered as a forecast, but as an illustrative simulation based on a conjectural scenario.

Table 88: Total estimated benefit of ICT spin-offs – under different scenarios (Million, CHF).

Scenario	Not discounted	Discounted
Pessimistic scenario	732,658,764	354,203,179
Baseline scenario	831,744,907	408,627,681
Optimistic scenario	1,180,250,058	591,045,081

Source: Authors

5.9. LOCAL BENEFITS OF PROCUREMENT: A CASE STUDY

Crescenzi and Piazza (2023) have conceived a novel framework to identify and estimate the regional economic impacts that a new particle-collider-based research infrastructure set up as a globally distributed project can create through their procurement. They validated this new approach in one case study by examining the local economic impacts of procurement activities carried out for the supply of superconducting radiofrequency cavities (SRF) for the European X-ray Free Electron Laser (XFEL) facility in Germany. One supplier firm E. Zanon (today Zanon Research & Innovation) and its surrounding area (Schio, Italy) were analysed.

To estimate the *additional* local economic impact *directly caused* by a research infrastructure procurement contract compared to how the region would have evolved in its absence, the Trajectory Balancing Method (TBM), developed by Hazlett and Xu (2018) and building on the synthetic control method, introduced initially by Abadie et al. (2015), was applied. This method allowed the authors to compare Schio with a suitable counterfactual of municipalities with similar characteristics, but that did not receive any procurement contract for XFEL. A synthetic Schio was created by selecting a weighted combination of control locations to approximate the pre-treatment trajectory of the outcome variable for the observed location (Schio). TBM estimates the effect of the treatment, in our case, the procurement contract, by comparing the evolution of the outcome variable of interest for the unit affected by the treatment to the evolution of the same outcome variable for the synthetic control. The intuition behind TBM is that if the trajectory of the outcome variable of interest is similar for both the synthetic and the treated unit before the treatment, any discrepancy we observe post-treatment can be attributed to the XFEL procurement contract.

The authors found that high-tech procurement contracts to Zanon affected manufacturing employment in the supplier's municipality well beyond the boundaries of the procurement contract with effects beyond the firm that received the contract. **Every new employee that the supplier added to its internal workforce to fulfil the contract supported 15 additional manufacturing jobs outside the firm's boundaries.** In monetary terms, **each one million Euros spent on procurement supported additional 11 manufacturing jobs in the supplier's municipality durably beyond the contract duration.** As a result of this contract, the number of manufacturing employees in Schio was 7% higher than it would have been in the absence of the SRF procurement.

The analysis suggests that the positive employment effect remained concentrated within the industrial manufacturing sector; in fact, no statistically significant positive effect is revealed for other linked sectors in the same local area. Moreover, it is found that the positive effects were geographically concentrated within the municipality of Schio, with no spillover effects on the neighbouring municipalities.

This study focused on a large and technology-intensive contract. Further research is needed to apply the proposed approach to other technology procurement cases to better understand the heterogeneity of such effects. For example, it can be used to understand how different technologies, different contract volumes and different technology intensities would impact the local economy in which the supplier is located in different ways.

5.10. MACRO-ECONOMIC MODEL FOR GLOBAL VALUE ADDED AND JOB CREATION

Streicher (2023) from WIFO used a complementary approach to estimate the value added and employment effects that are connected to the construction and operation of FCC-ee. The analysis was carried out using the ADAGIO simulation model (Kratena et al. (2013, 2017), a dynamic global Input/Output model, which covers 43 countries plus a "rest-of-the-world" data set. It builds on "supply-use" tables which describe the economy in terms of commodity flows: which sectors of the economy produce which commodities (supply) with respect to who consumes these commodities (use). In short, the model describes the flow between sectors and users, allowing to simulate ex-ante the effects of a "demand shock" in the economy. It has been used to simulate how

the new demand from the construction of FCC-ee translates into production of (and employment in) firms from various sectors and countries.

Using this model, Streicher first estimated the direct effects of project-related expenditures in the economy and the associated indirect effects that arise at the level of suppliers in the production of the intermediate or investment goods needed for the construction and operation of FCC-ee. These firms need, in turn, inputs from other firms, which again give rise to further purchases of intermediate products, creating a global value chain. Then, he estimated the induced effects that arise because of direct and indirect effects which correspond to increased spending within the business' supply chain, which generates additional consumption.

It was found that the construction and operation of FCC-ee are directly and indirectly linked to around 50 billion CHF over a 30-year period, **creating job opportunities amounting to 800,000 person-years. This corresponds to 1.7 billion CHF of annually value added and 27,000 jobs yearly.**¹²⁴

These figures must be interpreted with the following considerations: First, the "indirect jobs" are derived under a steady-state assumption – the estimates do not project major economic variables into the future (exchange rates, price levels and productivity being the most important ones). Therefore, the effects are estimated as if the FCC-ee was constructed and operated today. Second, the model focuses on immediate, short-term effects generated from the initial shock, but does not consider more long-lasting effects for the economy. Third, any type of private or public infrastructure investment project producing the same initial shock to the economy (i.e. raising the same demand for products and activating the same sectors in the economy) would generate comparable direct, indirect and induced effects. However, the areas in which a particle-collider and high-energy physics research project generates effects are different from ordinary infrastructure projects. The FCC-ee activates high-tech, engineering and energy sectors as well as emerging fields of activities. It generates a significant amount of jobs for knowledge workers and increases jobs in the high-quality tourism sector throughout all periods of the year. It is important to note that due to the FCC-ee global value chain, nations that are today not CERN member states and who do not contribute directly to the FCC project would profit from the investments (e.g. USA and China). This is an opportunity for project management to consider strategic goals such as fostering the inclusion of non-member states with economic benefit potentials as contributing nations into the project and to consider "smart specialisation" and "clusters" to assure that benefits remain within the nations who financially contribute to such a project.

5.11. LOCAL EFFECTS OF PROJECT PARTICIPANTS' HOUSEHOLD SPENDING

Gutleber and Alix (2023) used existing CERN personnel statistics since the LEP construction period to estimate the evolution of persons who would be active during the FCC-ee construction and operation periods and estimated the effects of their presence onto the local economy. This scenario is used as a reference baseline for several socio-economic impact pathways such as the generation of scientific products (Section 4.1) and the value of training (Section 4.2). Together with the historical databases of personnel and users, the scenario was used to estimate the economic effects of the LHC programme today and for the potential FCC-ee programme. The quantification of the direct, indirect and induced economic effects in the two host states was carried out using the INSEE national statistics data on household spending in France and the household income and spending statistics of the canton of Geneva. The results have been cross-checked against the Input/Output model established by Streicher (2023) from WIFO, and the results turned out to be consistent. This offered the opportunity to provide more detailed estimates for the local economic effects of FCC-ee on the job market.

¹²⁴ These figures refer to the sum of direct, indirect and induced effects.

The analysis revealed that, without including the LHC construction phase, the LHC and HL-LHC generate during their 30-years long scientific research programme about 8.9 billion EUR of household spending in the French-Swiss border region.

The entire FCC-ee programme is also assumed to last 30 years, but it is split into about 15 years of design and construction and 15 years of operation. Since during the design and construction phase less scientific researchers are assumed to be active in the programme, the total overall local economic impact relating to household spendings of people active at CERN is anticipated to be lower, in the order of 4.4 billion EUR. The major share of these spendings, 3.4 billion EUR can be attributed to the FCC-ee programme alone. While today the spendings are distributed about 60% in France and 30% in Switzerland, a modest shift of the activity focus to the Haute-Savoie department would result in a split of about 70% of the effects in France and 30% in Switzerland. Figure 48 below shows the total effects and the estimated distribution between the two host countries.

A key finding of this analysis is that without the FCC-ee project the region would experience substantially less economic effects, equivalent to the benefits that the residents during the FCC-ee project period would generate. France and Switzerland would observe a slowing of the local economic development, most notably in the tourism, the industrial and personal services sectors.

Figure 48: Consumption-related spendings of residents in France and in Switzerland over a 30-years long FCC-ee period.

Source: Gutleber and Alix (2023)

The following aspects are worth being highlighted:

- Today almost 9,000 people out of the more than 17,000 CERN registered persons are considered resident for at least one year in the region. These figures are assumed to remain during the FCC-ee operation period. A minor reduction during the FCC-ee period would most likely be compensated by the presence of construction workers. The FCC-ee does not lead to further, significantly increasing

amounts of persons in the region, but rather a minor shift of the activity from the Pays de Gex in the department of Ain to the Haute-Savoie region.

- Today most persons active on CERN's research programmes are not CERN employees. We assume that the number share of non-CERN employees remains at least as high as today, although locally employed project participants are likely to grow and generate more to the regional wealth creation. The FCC-ee is envisaged to be an international programme that builds even more on collaborations than the LHC and, therefore, the share of non-CERN to CERN employees may even grow further.
- Persons who are resident in the region and active in CERN's operation and its research projects are not only scientists and engineers. Numerous jobs are maintained around the operation and management of the activities with diverse job profiles and create opportunities for persons with diverse skill sets, educational and cultural backgrounds and career histories.
- More than 8,000 jobs can be sustained by the activities on the FCC sites that are not science and engineering related. Thereof 1,100 would be directly located in the Ain and Haute-Savoie departments and about 300 would be active in the canton of Geneva.
- About 3,400 jobs per year can be linked to the operation of the FCC-ee infrastructures. Thereof, about 200 jobs would be maintained in the immediate vicinity in France and 100 in Switzerland.
- About 2,800 jobs per year can be attributed to CERN and FCC-related tourism and visitor activities. Thereof, 500 jobs would be maintained in the departments of Ain and Haute-Savoie and 300 in the canton of Geneva.

5.12. AWARENESS AND ATTITUDES TOWARDS FUTURE ACCELERATORS AT CERN

In 2022 the FCCIS EU co-founded H2020 project issued a survey in a subset of CERN member states and associated countries to a representative sample of the adult population (aged 18-75) in each country with a view to investigate the attitude of CERN taxpayers towards the funding of a new particle accelerator within the next decade. Specifically, the survey had the following main objectives:

- Assess public awareness of CERN and its research in both member and non-member states, particularly those that could contribute to the FCC.
- Evaluate if and how much a new particle accelerator constructed in the next decade and operating for at least twenty-five years is worth to a lay person. This is monetized through the concept of "Willingness to financially participate" (WTP) in a big research activity.
- Determine whether WTP is influenced by awareness of the per-capita annual contribution member states allocate to CERN. If WTP meets or exceeds this amount, it validates current funding levels. If it falls short, it suggests a gap between public perception and actual contributions

The survey was built on previous successful contingent valuation experiments conducted in France in 2017 and in Switzerland in 2019 (Florio and Giffoni, 2020; Giffoni and Florio, 2023) and enlarged the scope to seven additional countries. Five of the additional countries surveyed are CERN member states (UK, Italy, Germany, Israel and Poland) and two are not members of CERN, but they are significantly involved in the LHC research programme and in the FCC international feasibility study collaboration (USA and Japan). The fieldwork took place from September to November 2022 and involved 8,443 valid responses. In total, with the respondents of the previous surveys in France and Switzerland, 10,448 valid responses were considered in the analysis.

The full methodological details and results of the surveys are provided in a separate technical report (Secci, 2023). Below is a brief summary of the main findings:

- Public awareness of CERN is not negligible, in spite of the type of research in fundamental science, albeit lower than that of organizations like NASA, WHO, and UNESCO, but higher than that of the IMF, FAO, and ESA. Only 41% of respondents are to a certain extent familiar with CERN and its

mission, with awareness varying by country. It is highest in Switzerland (80%) and Italy (64%) but much lower in non-EU countries, such as the USA (27%) and Japan (13%).

- Public sentiment about CERN is generally positive. Most respondents recognize its role in advancing knowledge of the universe (79%–86%), developing life-improving technologies (70%), and providing valuable training for students and professionals (70%).
- A majority of respondents also support intensifying CERN’s scientific research in the coming decades (65%–75%) and believe its work benefits society as a whole, not just scientists or nearby communities. Nevertheless, CERN’s recognition is largely associated to individual iconic figures (e.g like Nobel laureates as Peter Higgs or Carlo Rubbia), as there is no coordinated awareness program across its member and associated states. from 29% in Japan to over 70% in the UK, Poland, Italy, Switzerland, and the USA. The specific WTP value varies significantly from country to country, with median values ranging from CHF 20 per person per year in Switzerland to CHF 2 in France. For non-member states, the median WTP varies from CHF 24 in the USA to zero in Japan. However, Japan's mean WTP is CHF 10, indicating that a significant fraction of the Japanese population values scientific research, despite cultural biases against funding science through public sources.
- The variability in WTP is explained by socio-economic characteristics of respondents, with key determinants being per capita GDP and the level of awareness of CERN in each country.
- In CERN member states, WTP is higher than the current per-capita tax-based contributions. This holds true even when using the median WTP, a more conservative measure than the mean. This indicates that current contributions are justified by the value the public places on CERN's activities.
- The survey results show that the perceived value of a scientific research program including a new particle accelerator - like for example FCC-ee - exceeds the tax amount transferred to CERN by each respective country. Therefore, no discrepancies exist between WTP and the contributions currently paid or those potentially paid by future contributing states.
- Increasing global awareness is crucial, as societal acceptance and willingness to fund CERN are directly linked to public understanding of its mission. A structured communication strategy should leverage web and social media, as these are the primary sources of information about CERN, ahead of traditional TV.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The socio-economic impact analysis conducted on the Future Circular Collider electron-positron (FCC-ee) has revealed numerous benefit potentials across various domains. The **total present value of quantified socio-economic benefits associated with the FCC-ee research infrastructures has been conservatively estimated at 24 billion CHF**. The core benefits quantified include pathways:

- The value of scientific products produced by scientists, engineers, and researchers, generating additional knowledge through citations;
- Positive impacts on supplier companies;
- Development of openly accessible simulation software;
- Training opportunities and salary increases for early-career researchers involved in the FCC-ee project;
- Impacts generated by on-site and online visitors.

These benefits have been appraised through a conservative methodology, drawing on the current understanding of the project, insights garnered from analogous past research infrastructures, and socio-economic impact analyses. Data collected between 2020 and 2025 has played a crucial role in shaping the new estimations for FCC-ee. To ensure a comprehensive perspective, data gathering efforts included over 16,000 respondents through online surveys, plus large sets of secondary data (such as on procurement orders, publications, etc).

On the costs side, investments and operational costs have been estimated on the basis of the current concept. Noteworthy negative externalities stemming from the project's construction (e.g. the consumption of agricultural land, the greenhouse gas footprint) have also been included into the analysis.

The core quantified benefits of the FCC-ee project exceed its total costs—associated with the design, construction, and operation—by a factor of 1.20, resulting in a net positive socio-economic impact. These findings highlight the project's potential benefits not only for the scientific community but for society as a whole, reinforcing its long-term sustainability.

These results reflect the likely costs and benefits based on current knowledge. Further sensitivity and uncertainty analysis, for instance based on Monte Carlo simulation can provide insight into the dependency of the net present value on key influencing factors, and determine the minimum threshold at which the benefit-to-cost ratio reaches a break-even point with high confidence.

Additional potential benefits have been identified and explored to some extent but were not included in the quantified results due to their current uncertainty, even if some of them are potentially significant, particularly if the FCC-hh will be implemented. Their realisation depends on dedicated planning, integration, and suitable contextual conditions being incorporated into the project's design. Moreover, this analysis intentionally excludes attempts to quantify the unpredictable societal impacts of knowledge generated by the science mission.

This document may be updated over time to reflect ongoing refinements in infrastructure design. It should be regarded as part of a living appraisal that continuously informs and supports the project's development. It serves as a tool for decision-making, user engagement, risk mitigation, and enhancing the social acceptability of the FCC-ee project.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

This study showed that a break-even of socio-economic costs and benefits (not to be confused with financial flows) can be achieved by the FCC-ee with the impact pathways documented so far. However, the potential can only be fully exploited if a continuous tracking of socio-economic impacts is integrated into the infrastructure's design, construction and operation phases. To achieve this objective, nine recommendations have been formulated.

1) The FCC programme should allocate personnel and material resources for the impact identification, design, planning, implementation, monitoring and assessment process to help fully leveraging the impact potentials and making FCC a socio-economically sustainable endeavour.

This personnel needs to be empowered to be able that the results of the impact assessment and the impact generation recommendations are indeed considered in the design where appropriate, that they are implemented and that the continuous, systematic monitoring and analysis is carried out with the help of all participating project members. This requires that socio-economic impact assessment is implemented as a cross-cutting activity across the entire organisation, with the direct involvement of the highest possible managerial level and reporting directly to CERN's key stakeholder, the Council. This approach is expected to secure the sustainability and effectiveness of the process, as well as help enhance project acceptance among financially contributing countries.

2) Concerning the impacts generated by scientific products, the FCC programme should encourage that scientific and engineering works are published via "gold open access" channels (as opposed to "self-publishing") and reputable outlets (not just to depositing information in preprint servers). This ensures proper identification of works for tracking purposes and increases their likelihood of uptake.

This socio-economic impact assessment study has revealed challenges in identifying all scientific outputs associated with the research infrastructure activities. It is essential to track the scientific production of researchers involved in experiments and monitor citations across papers and other scientific products. However, scientific outputs lacking proper unique digital identifiers and citation references, as it is often the case with workshop proceedings and presentations available in platforms like Indico, cannot be adequately identified and considered for socio-economic valuation. These types of outputs should, whenever possible, be replaced or supplemented by citable reports or papers. Establishing strategic partnerships with leading publishers, as exemplified by the SCOAP3 project, is a suitable approach to assure the presence of citable publications. Open access platforms used for dissemination could integrate download, citation and reference tracking, if they do not already offer those functions (e.g. Zenodo and ArXiv seems to lack part of these functions). Furthermore, additional research is necessary to expand monitoring and tracking of scientific content beyond scientific and engineering articles and presentations to include books to better understand the societal uptake of knowledge acquisition within the FCC programme. Finally, a better understanding of co-authorship practices in HEP large collaborations and their actual representation of the scientists' effort in publishing, would provide insights for refining and advancing the current methodology for the economic valuation of scientific output based on the marginal cost of production.

3) Concerning the value of training, the FCC programme should foresee a framework to monitor the career paths of people after they leave CERN, to facilitate the analysis of future career developments.

Every individual contributing to the FCC project for a minimum duration should be encouraged, on a voluntary basis, to engage in a comprehensive monitoring programme. Thanks to mechanisms to reconnect with them periodically, this initiative would entail long-term follow-up and periodic collection of a set of basis information on their current work position.

4) To ensure the effective analysis of industrial spillovers generated during project implementation, the FCC program should incorporate systematic monitoring of the economic impacts on suppliers resulting from procurement actions over multi-year periods.

Given that these effects may not manifest immediately and can extend beyond the duration of the procurement contract, it is crucial to obtain feedback from the involved companies. This necessitates the establishment of a comprehensive procurement monitoring framework that facilitates ongoing engagement. Such a framework should include provisions for storing information on the individuals initially involved in the contract, enabling periodic follow-up after the contract's conclusion. Additionally, it should facilitate the collection of essential information regarding the spillover effects generated by the procurement experience with CERN on the company.

This can be achieved through mechanisms such as short online surveys designed to gather pertinent data. By implementing this approach, the FCC program can gain valuable insights into the long-term economic impacts of its procurement activities, fostering continuous improvement and enhancing collaboration with industry partners.

5) Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) have been identified as a key impact pathway that should be better leveraged through targeted transition actions to society, accompanied by systematic monitoring of uptake.

CERN and the FCC represent a globally unparalleled environment for the development of software and platforms to serve the needs of global collaborations, which is in high demand across societal and industrial sectors, too. By identifying the specific requirements of such collaborations and initiating dedicated development projects, the potential for widespread adoption beyond the FCC project can be created. Examples include communication (both one-to-one and one-to-many), file sharing, information management, remote operation, cybersecurity, data storage, distributed computing and data processing. CERN and the member states should ensure that the developed technologies are accessible to users outside the high-energy and particle physics community, free of charge, while also guaranteeing long-term maintenance and improvement. This requires making software and tools available on platforms that support download and installation tracking.

6) With respect to the impact of spin-off companies, there is a need to establish a systematic method for tracking companies founded by former participants in the FCC programme, monitoring their evolution over time, and assessing their economic value.

The establishment of new companies leveraging knowledge acquired through the FCC programme represents an important societal benefit. Notably, spin-offs often emerge from participants' amalgamation of different skills and experiences, rather than the direct exploitation of a single licensed technology. In particular, the technologies developed in collaborative R&D projects cannot be attributed to CERN alone and CERN does not track the technologies of collaboration partners. However, to accurately gauge the economic and societal benefits generated, a voluntary, systematic tracking mechanism is essential. This tracking framework should facilitate a comprehensive assessment of the impact of spin-off companies. It could include the establishment of a centralised database to record information about spin-off companies (such as their founders, country, industry sector, products/services offered), and the possibility to periodically contact them to provide updates on their companies' progress.

7) Concerning the cultural impacts, the study revealed the relevance of economic benefits due to on site visitors. To ensure a sustainable monitoring of this impact pathway, CERN and the FCC collaboration should establish a unified framework to continuously collect essential data on visitor to CERN's exhibition centres, the experiments and any other relevant visit site.

A systematic tracking mechanism for visitors is indeed necessary to accurately report on the effects of on-site visitors. Visitors should be requested to provide a small set of basic information, including their country of origin, mode of transport to Geneva, main purpose of the visit, duration of stay, visitor spending, and feedback on the exhibitions and the visit sites (e.g. their level of satisfaction). By implementing this monitoring

framework, it will be possible to effectively track and evaluate the cultural impact of on-site visitors, as well as enabling continual enhancement of visitor experiences.

8) Reduction or mitigation of negative externalities should be prioritised as part of a comprehensive effort of reducing the environmental impact of large scientific investment programmes.

Identifying and analyzing environmental benefits is crucial for the social acceptability of scientific research and achieving a net-zero balance. The FCC study management team has begun assessing potential negative environmental impacts while also exploring the benefits of renewable energy sources, waste heat reuse, and the repurposing of excavated materials. As the project continues to evolve, this assessment must be updated accordingly to reflect new developments. Moreover, research and collaboration with project stakeholders, economists, and environmental experts may provide additional insights. This will be instrumental in understanding and mitigating potential adverse effects associated with the implementation of the FCC program, ensuring sustainability and the responsible use of natural resources.

9) Continuous monitoring of the public awareness and acceptance of major science investments is important to sense the expectations of funders, ultimately the taxpayers. This approach should be further intensified through surveys conducted in all potential funding countries and regularly repeated to enhance our understanding of how social acceptance can not only be maintained but also be improved.

A framework for streamlining this process has been developed within this project, enabling the activity to continue with only marginal additional resources. Expanding data collection to additional countries, beyond those already surveyed, can provide insights into the factors influencing the people's perception on the FCC programme. The findings should not be regularly shared with CERN management and the Council and summarised for broader dissemination to all stakeholders, including the public, through channels such as CERN's social media platforms and its main websites.

8. ANNEX

8.1. EXCHANGE RATES

Table 89: Exchange rates adopted in the socio-economic benefits study.

Currencies (EUR vs Others): es. 1 EUR = X amount of the corresponding currency	Average 2024	Currencies (CHF vs Others): es. 1 CHF = X amount of the corresponding currency	Average 2024
EUR vs USD (US Dollar)	1.08	CHF vs USD (US Dollar)	1.14
EUR vs GBP (British Pound)	0.85	CHF vs GBP (British Pound)	0.89
EUR vs INR (Indian Rupee)	90.56	CHF vs INR (Indian Rupee)	95.06
EUR vs BRL (Brazilian Real)	5.83	CHF vs BRL (Brazilian Real)	6.12
EUR vs CAD (Canadian Dollar)	1.48	CHF vs CAD (Canadian Dollar)	1.56
EUR vs CNY (Chinese Yuan)	7.79	CHF vs CNY (Chinese Yuan)	8.17
EUR vs PLN (Polish Zloty)	4.31	CHF vs PLN (Polish Zloty)	4.52
EUR vs CHF (Swiss Franc)	0.95	CHF vs CHF (Swiss Franc)	1.00
EUR vs AUD (Australian Dollar)	1.64	CHF vs AUD (Australian Dollar)	1.72
EUR vs SEK (Swedish Krona)	11.43	CHF vs SEK (Swedish Krona)	12.00
EUR vs JPY (Japanese Yen)	163.85	CHF vs JPY (Japanese Yen)	172.00
EUR vs CZK (Czech koruna)	25.12	CHF vs CZK (Czech koruna)	26.37
EUR vs DKK (Danish Krone)	7.46	CHF vs DKK (Danish Krone)	7.83
EUR vs ILS (Israeli Shekel)	4.01	CHF vs ILS (Israeli Shekel)	4.21
EUR vs COP (Peso Colombiano)	4,403.67	CHF vs COP (Peso Colombiano)	4,622.79
EUR vs AMD (Armenian Dram)	395.17	CHF vs AMD (Armenian Dram)	414.83
EUR vs HUF (Hungarian Forint)	395.30	CHF vs HUF (Hungarian Forint)	414.97
EUR vs THB (Thai baht)	38.18	CHF vs THB (Thai baht)	40.08

Source: Authors

8.2. ESTIMATES FOR THE SOCIAL DISCOUNT RATE BY COUNTRY

The SDR allows assigning one monetary figure of costs and benefits that occur over time using a mathematical expression that is valid at one specific point in time. This process is called "discounting", and the resulting value is called the "present value". The formula is:

$$\text{Present Value of Benefit } B = \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{B_t}{(1 + \text{SDR})^t}$$

where:

- t is one year of the observation period, running from 1 (first year of the analysis) to n (end of the observation period)
- B_t is the value of benefit B at time t
- SDR is the social discount rate value established for the analysis.

The SDR reflects how society values well-being today versus well-being in the future. This has important implications for resource allocation in investment projects. The proper discount rate should represent the opportunity cost of what else could be accomplished with those same funds¹²⁵. Relatively higher SDR values reflect the fact that people have preferences for consuming resources today instead of investing them and thus postponing consumption in the future (the present value decreases quickly and reflects the fact that it is not attractive for people to make long-term investments). In this case, society prefers to increase welfare now rather than later through increased consumption. Relatively over SDR values indicate that society is more ready to renounce part of its consumption today in favour of investing it for future benefits since the values will decrease slower. A zero SDR means that society has no time preferences in choosing between present and future consumption. In general, though, people tend to prefer to consume immediately to be able to profit from their investments today rather than later because there is less probability in the future to be able to profit from the investments (e.g. due to life expectancy or the risk of emerging crises and economic downturns). However, without investments no benefits would be possible at all in the future. Hence, a preference-stated equilibrium that is determined by external factors occurs, which applies to a particular socio-economic environment at a particular point in time. The SDR changes, therefore, over time as the preference of the society changes with evolving socio-economic boundary conditions (e.g. economic growth, recession, peace and war times, health and life-expectation or health crises such as the pandemic, accelerating or decelerating climate change, technological breakthroughs, trust, and distrust in the future).

Empirical evidence from the economic literature¹²⁶ shows that the SDR is higher in developing countries (a preference to profit from investments immediately), often characterised by a higher GDP growth rate, than in countries with more mature economic systems, where people are more willing to invest in the future since it is more stable and predictable and since their life expectancy is higher¹²⁷.

SDR values can be estimated with different methods¹²⁸. One of the most common methods used by international organisations is based on the social rate of time preference (SRTP)¹²⁹, which considers the social preferences

¹²⁵ See Gruber, Jonathan (2011)

¹²⁶ See for instance Zhuang, L., Liang, Z., Lin, T. and De Guzman, F. (2007), Lopez, H. (2008)

¹²⁷ In line with this argument, and to mention one example of SDR estimated for the period 2014-2020, European Commission, (2014) recommended that a 5% SDR is used for the appraisal of major investment projects in the Cohesion countries (EU Member States with a lower GDP level) and a 3% SDR for the other EU Member States.

¹²⁸ The social rate of return on private investments (SRRI), the social rate of time preference (SRTP), the weighted average approach (WAA), the shadow price of capital. See European Commission, (2014) for details. Moreover, a more detailed explanation of the rationale for using the SDR as well as of the different approaches for calculating it is reported in Catalano G. and Pancotti C. (2021).

¹²⁹ The theoretical foundation of the SRTP is the Ramsey–Cass–Koopmans model or Ramsey growth model (Ramsey, 1928; Cass, 1965; Koopmans, 1965). It is a neoclassical model of economic growth based primarily on the work of Ramsey (1928). According to the model, there is a social planner (the government) that solves an inter-temporal optimization problem of social utility with respect to

and welfare of both current and future generations. The SRTP captures three aspects for determining the discounting factor:

- i. The pure time preference of consumers: consumers prefer to receive the same amount of goods and services sooner rather than later.
- ii. The assumption of a steadily increasing level of income and consumption for society.
- iii. The opportunity cost of resources: the allocation of any type of resource (money, persons, time) to a project represents a lost opportunity for society since the funds could have been spent on other, potentially more beneficial investments.

For this analysis, the SDR is set according to the SRTP approach with the following formula:

$$SDR = SRTP = p + \varepsilon * g$$

where:

- p is the *pure time preference*. It captures the impatience and myopia of people to consume as soon as possible instead of delaying consumption to the future. It can be proxied with the annual mortality rate of the population, assuming that consumption is anticipated when the risk of death or human race extinction increases. For the purpose of calculation, we used the average crude death rate over the period 2022-2041 provided by Eurostat. Where missing, the World Bank value for 2021-2040 was used as an alternative
- ε is the *elasticity of marginal utility of consumption*. This parameter measures the extent to which the satisfaction (utility) from additional consumption decreases as the level of consumption rises. When the current level of consumption provides “saturation”, increasing consumption even more would still provide satisfaction but to a lower extent. Assuming there is some growth ($g > 0$), consumption has a lower unit utility in the future. The term ($\varepsilon * g$) will still be positive, but ε decreases as g increases. There are several methods to estimate ε . The most common ones are those based on (progressivity of) taxation models, which influence people’s demand for goods and services: as income increases, taxes increase more than proportionally, and available income for consumption decreases. We estimate the elasticity of marginal utility of consumption based on social preferences revealed by taxation. We used the 2022 OECD Taxation Database to determine ε . When data was not available, the value was estimated through value transfer (average between the regression and ML estimate considering data for 2000-2019).
- g is the expected per-capita growth rate of consumption. It is proxied by the real growth rate of the per-capita GDP under the assumption that the GDP properly reflects the dynamics of consumption over time. For the purpose of calculation, we used the expected per capita GDP growth rate over the period 2021-2042 calculated on the basis of data provided by OECD. When data were missing, the past growth 2000-2019 rate provided by the World Bank was used as an alternative.

By applying the formula above, we estimated the SDR in each country that contributes to the CERN budget today, including CERN member states and Associated Countries¹³⁰. We then estimated the average of the SDR in each country, weighted by the respective contribution to the CERN budget. The table below shows the data entering into the calculation along with the estimated SDR for each country and the weighted average value used for the socio-economic impacts assessment of the FCC-ee.

consumption, considering the welfare of both current and future generations. The Ramsey–Cass–Koopmans model differs from the Solow–Swan (Solow, 1956; Swan, 1956) model in that the choice of consumption is explicitly micro founded at a point in time and so endogenizes the savings rate.

¹³⁰ Final Budget of the Organisation for the seventieth financial year 2024, <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2888205>

Table 90: Data entering the SDR calculation

Country	P - Expected death rate (EUROSTAT, 2022-2041)	E (OECD 2022)	G - Expected per capita GDP growth rate (2021-2042)	Unweighted SDR	% Contribution to the CERN budget (2024)
CERN Member States					
Austria	0.88	1.63	0.88	2.47	2.2%
Belgium	1.02	1.78	1.02	2.82	2.7%
Bulgaria	1.90	1.00	1.90	3.47	0.4%
Czechia	1.59	1.39	1.59	3.40	1.2%
Denmark	1.00	1.23	1.00	2.29	1.8%
Finland	1.18	1.69	1.18	3.15	1.3%
France	1.01	1.69	1.01	2.70	13.1%
Germany	0.81	1.45	0.81	2.38	20.6%
Greece	1.54	1.63	1.54	3.77	1.0%
Hungary	1.68	1.00	1.68	3.05	0.7%
Israel	1.38	1.82	1.38	3.04	2.2%
Italy	0.82	2.10	0.82	2.93	9.6%
Netherlands	0.90	1.85	0.90	2.68	4.6%
Norway	0.88	1.78	0.88	2.44	2.1%
Poland	1.88	1.28	1.88	3.62	3.0%
Portugal	1.31	1.52	1.31	3.21	1.1%
Romania	2.18	1.00	2.18	3.58	1.3%
Serbia	3.72*	1.32**	3.72***	6.44	0.3%
Slovakia	1.67	1.28	1.67	3.28	0.5%
Spain	1.15	1.63	1.15	2.86	6.8%
Sweden	1.05	1.46	1.05	2.49	2.6%
Switzerland	0.93	1.61	0.93	2.40	3.7%
UK	0.95	1.47	0.95	2.36	14.7%
Associate Member States in the pre-stage to Membership					
Cyprus	1.38*	1.40**	1.38***	2.75	0.1%
Estonia	2.07	1.93	2.07	5.22	0.1%
Slovenia	1.30	1.35	1.30	2.89	0.2%
Associate Member States					
Croatia	2.68*	1.29**	2.68***	4.87	0.1%
India	4.20	1.44**	4.20	6.83	1.4%
Latvia	2.05	1.40	2.05	4.40	0.1%
Lithuania	1.86	1.22	1.86	3.69	0.1%
Pakistan	2.41*	1.46**	2.41***	4.18	0.2%
Türkiye	2.57	1.61	2.57	4.74	0.4%

Ukraine	1.328*	1.34**	1.32***	3.41	0.1%
Weighted average SDR	2.8			100%	

Note: * World Bank value for 2021-2040 ** value estimated through value transfer *** Past growth 2000-2019 rate provided by the World Bank was used as an alternative. **Source:** Authors

8.3. PROJECT PARTICIPANTS ESTIMATES

Table 91: Working hypothesis for the number of people involved in the FCC-ee programme including the particle accelerator and infrastructure domain as well as two experiment collaborations.

#	Phase	Cal.	Number of persons per year				
		Year	Experiment 1	Experiment 2	Experiment 3 + 4	Accelerator / infrastructure	Total
1	Design	2028	43	43	44	365	495
2	Design	2029	43	43	44	375	505
3	Design	2030	43	43	44	386	516
4	Design	2031	43	43	44	397	527
5	Design	2032	43	43	44	408	538
6	Construction	2033	73	73	54	419	619
7	Construction	2034	139	139	90	440	808
8	Construction	2035	252	252	134	470	1,108
9	Construction	2036	384	384	247	500	1,515
10	Construction	2037	648	648	363	550	2,209
11	Construction	2038	747	747	459	606	2,558
12	Construction	2039	858	858	530	666	2,912
13	Construction	2040	908	908	599	715	3,130
14	Construction	2041	959	959	730	744	3,392
15	Const./Inst.	2042	1,084	1,084	866	773	3,806
16	Const./Inst.	2043	1,124	1,124	932	815	3,994
17	Installation	2044	1,144	1,144	1,021	857	4,165
18	Installation	2045	1,219	1,219	1,090	910	4,437
19	Installation	2046	1,493	1,493	1,386	1,000	5,372
20	Transition	2047	1,802	1,802	1,660	1,035	6,299
21	Z	2048	2,305	2,305	1,896	1,020	7,526
22	Z	2049	2,599	2,599	2,122	960	8,280
23	Z	2050	2,743	2,743	2,324	900	8,710
24	Z	2051	3,017	3,017	2,536	900	9,470
25	WW	2052	3,191	3,191	2,788	900	10,070
26	WW	2053	3,440	3,440	2,990	900	10,770
27	HZ	2054	3,779	3,779	3,242	900	11,700
28	HZ	2055	3,989	3,989	3,542	900	12,420
29	HZ	2056	4,149	4,149	3,692	900	12,890
30	L.S.	2057	4,344	4,344	3,842	900	13,429
31	ttbar	2058	4,737	4,737	3,896	900	14,270
32	ttbar	2059	4,947	4,947	4,096	900	14,890
33	ttbar	2060	5,215	5,215	4,098	900	15,428
34	ttbar	2061	5,200	5,200	4,098	823	15,321
35	ttbar	2062	5,087	5,087	4,098	900	15,172
36	analysis	2063	4,937	4,937	3,998	780	14,652
37	analysis	2064	4,737	4,737	3,948	780	14,202
Totals			81,463	81,463	67,588	27,594	258,107

Note: The rightmost column indicates the total number of persons. The project starts with the first significant engagement of financial resources in 2028. For the purpose of socio-economic impact analysis, the project ends two years after the last data taking. This lead-out phase is dedicated to data analysis and scientific research. **Source:** Authors

Table 92: Number of personnel-years managed by CERN and by other institutions by categories

2024-2064	Accelerator & Infrastructure		Experiments (1+2+3+4)			Total	
	Managed by CERN	Managed by other institutions	Managed by CERN	Managed by other institutions	Managed by CERN	Managed by other institutions	Total FCC-EE Programme
<i>Scientists</i>	2,490	830	2,703	31,080	5,192	31,910	37,103
<i>Post docs</i>	5,084	1,606	4,916	56,537	10,001	58,143	68,143
<i>Engineers</i>	1,815	605	3,819	43,916	5,634	44,521	50,155
<i>Technicians</i>	5,616	1,872	16,270	-	21,886	1,872	23,759
<i>Administration</i>	977	326	170	1,954	1,147	2,280	3,427
<i>Doctoral students</i>	2,839	896	3,531	40,611	6,370	41,507	47,877
<i>Other students</i>	1,850	-	1,952	22,454	3,802	22,454	26,256
<i>Apprentices</i>	788	-	300	300	1,088	300	1,388
Total	21,460	6,135	33,661	196,852	55,121	202,986	258,107
SHARE					21%	79%	100%

Source: Authors

8.4. ESTIMATED DURATION OF ACTIVE WORKING LIFE

Bianchini et al. (2019) report on a recent survey conducted by the CERN Alumni initiative aimed at studying the career trajectories of people with a working experience in high-energy physics experiments at CERN. 2,692 responses were collected from both current and past members of LHC and other experiments at CERN. More than 85% of people hold a PhD and are experimental physicists, a share that is also confirmed by other studies.¹³¹ Moreover, Fig. 2.18 on page 15 in the Bianchini et al. (2019)'s study shows that the variety of sectors in which CERN people are likely to continue their careers after their experience at CERN is broad. Out of 1,937 participants who answered the question about the sector they work in, 55% of respondents answered "academia", followed by the information technology in the private sector (41%), government sector (17%), financial institutions (15%), high-tech companies (14%), and education in high school (13%). People working in experiments at CERN typically have a high educational level (doctoral degree) and are therefore likely to continue their professional career in academia and research and to a lower extent in the private industry and service sectors.

According to Eurostat, **the average expected total working life duration in the EU28 in 2019 was 36.4 years.** The gap between men and women is 4.8 years, with men at 38.6 years, and women at 33.8 years. The expected average duration among the EU Member States ranges from 32 years in Italy to 42 years in Sweden (Table 93, Column 1).¹³² This is in line with OECD (2020) figures as well. According to these figures, we have that on average:

- A person who has entered the labour market at the age of 15 is likely to retire at 52 years;
- A person who has entered the labour market at the age of 20 is likely to retire at 57 years;
- A person who has entered the labour market at the age of 30 is likely to retire at 67 years.

Retirement at the age of 65, and often earlier, is the norm in the EU (Eurofound, 2020 and column 2 in and blue lines in Figure 49) and for the OECD countries (64.2 for men and 63.5 for women) (OECD, 2019a).¹³³ There is no significant difference between the normal retirement age and the effective one. For instance, in the OECD countries the effective retirement age is 65.4 for men and 63.7 for women. There are no significant differences in the retirement ages between sectors as well. Apart from non-standard workers for whom specific pension rules are currently in force¹³⁴ and ad-hoc pension schemes for workers in arduous and hazardous jobs,¹³⁵ the normal retirement age is 65 years in the majority of EU countries in all sectors. For example, Column 3 in Table 93 reports the effective retirement age of the academic staff in the EU. It typically ranges from 65 to 67 years, with some exceptions to 70 years. There are no differences in terms of pension legislation between the education sector and other sectors of the economy.¹³⁶

¹³¹ Camporesi et al (2017).

¹³² European Commission (2020). Duration of working life -statistics. Available here: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/pdfscache/57155.pdf>. Last access on 25.05.2020. The discussion in the text above does not take into account the European Candidate Countries (Montenegro; North Macedonia, Albania, Serbia, Turkey) and EFTA Countries (Iceland, and Norway).

¹³³ Estimates derived from the European and national labour force surveys. See OECD (2019a).

¹³⁴ They are workers not covered by fulltime open-ended contracts, i.e. part-time, temporary or self-employed workers for whom specific pension rules are currently in force, even if efforts have been implementing on how to make pension systems more inclusive given transforming labour markets. (OECD, 2019a).

¹³⁵ Although there has been a debate on what are the "hard job" categories and the "generosity of pensions for workers in "hard jobs", in some rare cases, countries pushed through reforms creating more favourable conditions for these categories. For instance, Finland set up a new scheme for workers in arduous and hazardous jobs: the "years-of-services pension" (minimum pensionable age of 63). France established a "personal prevention account" which allow workers to acquire points as a result of exposure to six risk factors; while Italy has introduced special rules for workers in arduous and hazardous jobs, allowing them to retire prior to reaching the pensionable age, under certain conditions. On-going policy discussion along these lines are currently taking place in Belgium, Croatia, and Slovakia. See Cabral and Rodrigues (2019).

¹³⁶ See for instance the European Commission's Eurydice platform, which shares information and data on the European education systems updated to April 2020).

While retirement at the age of 65 and earlier has been the norm until now, **the age at which people retire is rising**. According to Eurofound (2020), as the "baby boom" generation approaches retirement, more workers will be retiring than those entering the labour market. With an increasing life expectancy and birth rates falling across Europe, a priority of EU policy is to encourage Europeans to extend their active work life to ensure the sustainability of pension systems and adequate social protection. Eurostat data show that in general and for all sectors, the average duration of working life in the EU28 is slowly increasing over time. In 2019, it was 0.5 years longer than in 2018 and 3.5 years longer than in 2000.¹³⁷ Some changes in retirement ages are scheduled to take place between 2020 and 2030 in most of the EU countries. Column 4 in Table 93 (orange lines in Figure 49) reports the future retirement age as scheduled by the EU Member States, **with 67 years of pension age on average**.¹³⁸

We chose to set the total average active working life for researchers and scientists to a range between 37 and 40 years based on the observation that pension ages are slowly rising and that a certain fraction of people in academia may work longer, but not likely more than 69 to 70 years.¹³⁹ Consider the following example: students are on average, between 26-28 years old when they enter a doctoral programme (OECD, 2019b; p. 345).¹⁴⁰ Considering that the average duration of a full-time doctoral program is 3-4 years,¹⁴¹ the person enters the labour market between 29 and 32 years. When working for at least 37 years, that person would retire between 66 and 69 years.

The range of 37 and 40 years is in line with the observed trend of increasing work duration and future pension plans across all the major developed countries and sectors, including academia. It is also in line with the literature on human capital, which often sets the maximum years of potential working experience at 40 years.¹⁴²

¹³⁷ In 2000, the average length of working life in the EU28 was 32.9 years. European Commission (2020; p.4).

¹³⁸ See Finnish Centre for Pensions (2022; 2020) and Eurofound (2020).

¹³⁹ <https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/sites/bb6ee273-en/index.html?itemId=/content/component/bb6ee273-en>. Positions in academia are finite, therefore is not likely to keep people so long to avoid that they block the positions of younger people.

¹⁴⁰ It depends on the age at which students graduate from a lower level of higher education and the flexibility of the national education system (OECD, 2019b).

¹⁴¹ Several European universities websites have been revised.

¹⁴² Psacharopoulos, G. and Patrinos, H.A. (2018); Lemieux, T. (2006). The range 37-40 is instead slightly lower than the duration of working life assumed in a recent OECD study which sets it, on average, at 44 years. The OECD (2019a; Table 5.2) reports cases of people entering in the labour market in 2018 at age 22 (birth cohort 1996). Although the pension age differs among countries because of national scheduled pension plans, on average, it is estimated that such people would retire at an age of 66, i.e., 44 years of active working life. The average career duration assumed for the LHC and HL-LHC socio-economic impact assessment, which was 42 years (see Bastianin and Florio (2018); Florio et al (2016)).

Table 93: Duration of working life and retirement age in EU member States and some extra-EU countries

Country/ Area	Column 1			Column 2	Column 3	Column 4
	Duration of working life (all sectors)			Current (2020) normal retirement age in all sectors (years)	Effective retirement age of academic staff (years)	Future normal retirement age (years)
	Total	Male	Female	Male/Female		
EU 27	35.9	38.3	33.4			
EU 28	36.4	38.7	33.9			
Belgium	33.6	35.4	31.6	65	65	67 (by 2030)
Bulgaria	34.0	35.6	32.3	66.5	65	67 (by 2023)
Czechia	36.3	39.2	33.2	63.7	63-65	65 (by 2036)
Denmark	40.0	41.7	38.2	67/66	65-70	68+ (by 2030)
Germany	39.1	41.1	36.9	65.7		67 (by 2031)
Estonia	39.0	39.5	38.5	63.7		68+ (by 2027)
Ireland	37.4	40.7	33.9	66	65-70	68 (by 2028)
Greece	33.2	36.6	29.6	67	67	67+ (by 2021)
Spain	35.3	37.4	33.1	65.8	65-70	67 (by 2027)
France	35.4	37.0	33.8	66.5	65-67	67 (by 2023)
Croatia	32.5	34.5	30.5	65/62.5	65	67 (by 2038)
Italy	32.0	36.4	27.3	67	65-70	67+ (by 2022)
Cyprus	37.5	40.5	34.4	65	67	65+ (by 2023)
Latvia	36.8	36.8	36.8	63.8	65	65 (by 2025)
Lithuania	37.1	36.7	37.5	64/63	65	65 (by 2026)
Luxembourg	33.9	36.0	31.6	65		
Hungary	34.4	37.4	31.2	64.5	65	65 (by 2022)
Malta	36.5	41.1	31.8	63	62-67	65 (by 2027)
Netherlands	41.0	43.3	38.6	64.3	66-67	67+ (by 2022)
Austria	37.6	39.8	35.3	65/60	65	65 (by 2033)
Poland	33.6	36.3	30.7	65/60	65	
Portugal	38.2	39.6	36.8	66.5	70	
Romania	33.8	37.0	30.3	65/61.5		
Slovenia	35.9	37.0	34.7	65	65	
Slovakia	34.2	36.6	31.6	62.5	70	63+ (by 2024)
Finland	38.9	39.6	38.3	68/65	65	65+ (by 2030)
Sweden	42.0	42.9	41.0	62-68/65	65-67	66+ (by 2026)
UK	39.4	41.5	37.2	65 o 66	65	68 (by 2046)
Iceland	45.8	47.8	43.7	67		
Norway	39.8	41.1	38.4	62-75/67		
Switzerland	42.6	44.6	40.4	65/64	64-65	
Montenegro	32.7	36.0	29.2		67	
N. Macedonia	31.7	36.8	26.4			

Serbia	33.4	36.4	30.2	65-68
Turkey	29.3	39.0	19.1	65-67
Australia			58/66	65 (by 2025)/ 67 (by 2023)
Canada			65	
Japan			65	
Russia			60.5/55.5	65 (by 2028)/60 (by 2028)
USA			66	67 (by 2027)

Source: Column 1, Duration of working life: Eurostat. Variable [lfsi_dwl_a]. Raw data are available here:

https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=lfsi_dwl_a&lang=en.

Columns 2 and 4: Finnish Centre for Pensions, <https://www.etk.fi/en/the-pension-system/international-comparison/retirement-ages/>

Column 3: European Commission's Eurydice platform. https://eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-policies/eurydice/home_en search for "Conditions of Service for Academic Staff Working in Higher Education")

Figure 49: Current and estimates for future duration of average working life in EU member states

Note: Ad-hoc pension schemes for workers in arduous and hazardous jobs are excluded. **Source:** Authors' elaboration on data in Table 93.

Considering that:

- retirement from paid work at the age of 65, and often earlier, is the norm in the EU and that, in line with that figure, the average expected duration of working life in the EU27 was **36.9 years in 2023** (Eurostat),
- no systematic differences exist in terms of normal retirement age between sectors, including academia (with the exception of non-standard workers and risky jobs) (European Commission, OECD),
- in the future, the compulsory retirement age is likely to increase in European countries to a range of 65-68 years (Eurofound, OECD) and as a result, the expected duration of working life will increase to 37 - 40 years (OECD),

we set the total average active working life for researchers and scientists working at FCC-ee between 37 and 40 years. This also fits with the characteristics of people who have had a working experience at CERN, i.e. with the fact that 85% of them have a PhD (Bianchin et al., 2019) and corresponds to an average increase of two years in the working life in line with CERN historical data from the '90 to '20.¹⁴³

Figure 50 shows the probability distribution of the total average active working life with probabilities associated with four periods: 37 years, 38 years, 39 and 40 years. Probabilities are calculated as the ratio between the number of countries with that total active working life out of the total number of countries (N = 29, including EU28 and USA).¹⁴⁴

¹⁴³ See also <https://tradingeconomics.com/european-union/retirement-age-men>

¹⁴⁴ It is important to include the USA because it represents the second country after Switzerland where people go to work after their experiential learning at CERN. For instance, the study by Bianchin et al. (2019) shows that out of 2,692 trained people at CERN who participated to the survey on career trajectories, 496 people work and reside in Switzerland, 416 in the US, 299 in Germany, 427 in Italy, and 2115 in France (Bianchin et al. 2019; Figure 2.5).

Figure 50: Probability distribution of the total active working life

Note: The period 37 years includes 13 countries out of 28. They have a future normal retirement age of maximum 37 years and are: MT, SI, ES, HU, SK, BG, LU, RO, BE, PL, GR, IT. The period 38 years includes 5 countries out of 29. They are: PT, CY, IE, LT, LV, CZ. The period 39 years include 6 countries: FR, DE, UK, EE, FI, AT, FR., The period 40 years includes 3 countries: Denmark, Sweden (assumption) and Netherlands (assumption). **Source:** Authors' elaboration on data in Table 93.

8.5. ESTIMATED SALARY FUNCTIONS BY PROFESSIONAL SECTOR

Salary functions were calculated considering the following data and geographical and sector scope.

- Data were extracted from Glassdoor (www.glassdoor.com), a job-related website where registered users from all over the world can anonymously submit and view salaries as well as search and apply for jobs on the platform. Glassdoor data cover the majority of countries (European ones and the USA) in which people at CERN are likely to continue their careers after their experience at the laboratory (see below). A possible alternative to Glassdoor is the US salary database PayScale, which has been used in previous works dealing with the value of training benefit at CERN.¹⁴⁵ While being a valuable source of information, the PayScale database has the disadvantage of reporting only the salaries in the US labour market and therefore it does not cover the European labour market, which is the main destination of CERN researchers.
- The geographical and sector scope of the analysis was driven by the evidence shown by the CERN report by Bianchin et al. (2019). That report investigates the career trajectories of 2,692 people with working experience in the CERN experiments, which represents an extremely valuable sample of respondents and information to our purpose. For instance, the report shows that respondents work in more than 17 countries, but the large majority of them works in five countries: Switzerland (496 out of 2,692), the USA (416), Germany (299), Italy (247), and the UK (183). The remaining countries count less than 60 respondents.¹⁴⁶ Moreover, out of 1,937 participants who answered the multiple-answer question about the sector they work, 55% of respondents answered “academia”, followed by the private sector (ICT - 41%; financial institutions - 15%; high-tech companies - 15%), public administration (17%), and education in high school (13%). As regards the job titles of people who left CERN, most of them are employed as software engineer, followed by analyst, manager, and consultant.¹⁴⁷ We used these findings to drive our data collection strategy.

Glassdoor reports gross salary data (i.e. they include taxes) and are in national currencies. Salaries were expressed in Swiss francs (CHF) by using 2019 average bilateral exchange rates provided by the European Central Bank. Data were collected in May 2020 and assembled in two databases with different pieces of information:

1. **The first database contains salary data at national level.** At that level, Glassdoor provides information on the average salary level by country and by job title, the minimum and maximum values. The website also informs about the reliability of data, through a 4-scale-point indicator (from very low to very high), which is linked to the number of records in that country. For instance, considering the job title “software engineer”, US salary records amount to 256,924 with a reliability “very high”; in the UK, they amount to 5,488, which is still “very high”; in Switzerland they were 386 with “high” reliability; in contrast, in Belgium there were only 30 records with a “low” reliability of salary data. **In total, 812,000 records of salary data from 16 countries and 13 job titles were processed.** Statistics at national level are reported in the Figure below. As mentioned above, the range of countries and job titles considered reflects the career profile of people with a working experience at CERN.
2. **The second database contains salary data at individual level.** Beyond salaries, the country, and the job title, Glassdoor users are asked to share the number of years of working experience, the sector and the city where they work, and whether they receive any bonus in addition to the basic

¹⁴⁵ Florio et al. (2016) and Bastianin and Florio (2018). The first paper uses salary functions calculated on the US PayScale database to estimate the benefit associated with a period of training at the CERN Large Hadron Collider (LHC); the second one uses the same functions but applied to the Hi-Luminosity LHC. Throughout the document, comparisons between the salary functions obtained from the two sources data, i.e. PayScale and Glassdoor, are analysed to investigate on differences e/o similarities.

¹⁴⁶ Bianchin et al (2019), page 6, Figure 2.5.

¹⁴⁷ Bianchin et al (2019), page 15, Figure 2.18 and Figure 2.19.

salary.¹⁴⁸ Personal information, and in particular the sector of employment and the years of working experience, can be only extracted for a limited number of records in a given country (the most recent records); therefore they are not available for the whole sample of records at national level. **In total, 1,004 records covering 16 countries** (on average 63 per country) **and 13 job titles** (about 77 per job title) were collected.

The figure below (Panel A) compares the geographical distribution of salaries from the national database (with reliable average salaries, but no individual information) and the individual database (smaller number of records and therefore potentially less reliable average salaries by country, but more individual information). There are no significant differences between the two distributions, suggesting that individual data are reliable as well. Employees in Switzerland earn the highest gross salary (CHF 110,082 per year), followed by those in the USA (CHF 80,647), Germany (CHF 73,197), and Canada (CHF 63,855). The lowest salaries are paid in India. The average annual salary in the database amounts to about CHF 51,000.¹⁴⁹ Similarly, Panel B shows the distribution by job titles. **The two distributions are similar to each other, confirming the reliability of salary data from the individual database.**¹⁵⁰ As expected, directors register the highest salaries (CHF 100,000 per year), professors the second highest (about CHF 64,000 per year), while educators the lowest ones (about 33,000 per year).

¹⁴⁸ For each salary reported, Glassdoor removes the name of the company for privacy reasons, while showing the sector, years of experience and the presence of bonus or other benefits in addition to the salary.

¹⁴⁹ In addition, these data were also cross-checked with salaries reported in the Inomics Salary Report (2018). INOMICS is a platform which provides information on the career of students in Economics and offer students, professors, professionals and recruiters in the economics job market a comprehensive online resource for their academic and career choices since 1998. The 2018 report (page 21) states that “*The highest salaries for almost all positions, both in academia and the private sector are earned in Switzerland, Canada and the United States. For instance, the highest salaries for PhD candidates are earned in Switzerland and Canada, with PhD candidates in Switzerland earning on average twice as much as those in Germany*”.

¹⁵⁰ The job title “director” shows slightly higher salaries when individual data are considered because of outliers in the data (in the public administration sector). The Team removed them to simulate salaries functions.

Figure 51: Distribution of salaries: database at national level (CHF, annual)

PANEL A: Distribution by country of employment

PANEL B: Distribution by job title

Note: The Figure shows the salary distribution by country and job title extracted from the Glassdoor national database. For each country and job title the mean (blue bar), the minimum (orange bar) and the maximum (green bar) are reported. **Source:** Authors' elaboration on Glassdoor data.

Figure 52: Distribution of salaries: national database vs. individual database (CHF, annual)

PANEL A: Distribution of salaries by country of employment

PANEL B: Distribution of salaries by job title

Source: Authors' elaboration on Glassdoor data.

The distributions of salaries by years of working experience and by sector are reported in Figure 53. Both are from the database at the individual level. People in the public administration sector report the highest salaries (CHF 61,162 per year), followed by employees in the industry e/o finance (CHF 53,271 per year) and finally academia or other research institutes (CHF 43,336 per year).

An average salary premium of 6% (ranging from a minimum of 2% to a maximum of 10%) **is gained for the average number of years an early-career researcher spends at CERN** (as from Table 40, 3.78 years, i.e. about 45 months).

Figure 53: Distribution of salaries by years of experience and sector (CHF, annual)

Source: Authors' elaboration on Glassdoor data.

Figure 54 shows the salary functions obtained by (log-)interpolating the salary data with the years of working experience; while Table 39 in Section 4.2 reports the formulas along with the parameters of the distributions of salaries by sector.¹⁵¹ The Figure shows that the distribution of salaries has a positive skew, i.e. the mean is higher than the median, which is a stylised fact in the empirical salary distribution. Moreover, and as mentioned above, the salary functions and the other parameters are reported for the three sectors where the majority of former project participants are likely to be employed: academia and research, industry/finance, and public administration. A fourth salary function grouping all the three sectors above and labelled “All sectors” is shown as a reference for the salary trajectory for those people where information about the sector of employed is lacking/or cannot be predicted.

¹⁵¹ Mincer (1974) modelled the natural logarithm of earnings as a function of years of education and years of (potential) labour market experience (age minus year of schooling minus six). The Mincer equation stems from the Ben Porath's lifecycle model “Human Capital Investment over the Lifecycle” (Ben Porath, 1967). Glassdoor data do not have information on the number of years of education of users. Interpolating salary data with years of experience is the best one can do with those data.

Figure 54: Salary functions developed for the FCC-ee socio-economic impact analysis

Note: Elaborations are net of outliers: 7 people out of 222 in the public administration sector were removed. They held “director” positions earning more than CHF 200,000 per year. The R^2 gives an indication of the goodness of the interpolation and ranges from 0 (the worst fit) to 1 (the best fit). It is as follows: Academia_Research ($R^2=0.93$); Industry/Finance ($R^2=0.78$); Public administration ($R^2=0.83$); All sectors ($R^2=0.89$).

Source: Authors’ elaboration on Glassdoor data.

Glassdoor data have some limitations. For instance, they do not report the education level of users, which is extremely important to explain the variability across individual salaries (years of experience only tell us part of the story) (Mincer, 1974). Moreover, primary data are needed to estimate more accurate salary functions (Psacharopoulos and Patrinos, 2018; Lemieux, 2006; Mincer, 1974). For that reason, CERN carried out a salary survey in April 2020 to people with working experience at CERN in order to collect more reliable information on job-related variables, including salaries.

8.6. VALUE OF LEISURE TIME

Table 94: Value of leisure time: a review of previous studies

VALUE OF TIME (CHF/HOUR) - 2021	SOURCE
9.36	HANDBOOK ON THE EXTERNAL COSTS OF TRANSPORT – JANUARY 2019
13.96	PELLETIER, M. C., HEAGNEY, E., & KOVAČ, M. (2021). VALUING RECREATIONAL SERVICES: A REVIEW OF METHODS WITH APPLICATION TO NEW SOUTH WALES NATIONAL PARKS. ECOSYSTEM SERVICES, 50, 101315.
14.40	MEUNIER, D., & QUINET, E. (2015). VALUE OF TIME ESTIMATIONS IN COST BENEFIT ANALYSIS: THE FRENCH EXPERIENCE. TRANSPORTATION RESEARCH PROCEDIA, 8, 62-71.
16.56	LUGANO, G., CORNET, Y., UNIZA, R. P., BERNARDINO, J., WARIS, H., & MILAKIS, D. (2018). D2. 2–MOBILITY AND TRAVEL TIME REPORT.
16.28	BOITEUX M. (2000) "CHOIX DES INVESTISSEMENTS AND PRISE EN COMPTE DES NUISANCES",
7.30 - 16.28	LEGAL BASIS SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACT STUDIES FRANCE
18.65	WARDMAN, M., CHINTAKAYALA, V. P. K., & DE JONG, G. (2016). VALUES OF TRAVEL TIME IN EUROPE: REVIEW AND META-ANALYSIS. TRANSPORTATION RESEARCH PART A: POLICY AND PRACTICE, 94, 93-111.
SUMMARY	
7.3	MINIMUM
14.1	AVERAGE
18.7	MAXIMUM

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